

D4.4 Needs-Policy Canvas

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Every effort has been made to ensure that all statements and information contained herein are accurate, however the PoliRural Project Partners accept no liability for any error or omission.

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Executive Summary

The purpose of this deliverable is to collect the results of Needs-Policy Mapping task (T4.4) that aims to match the rural needs of 12 PoliRural pilot regions against current policies and public or private strategies present in their region and if co-funded by EU match also these to the relevant EU's Structural and Investment Funds. This deliverable also presents the mission statements and rural policy structures in every PoliRural pilot regions and thus allows access to explore pilot areas more in-depth and use the information in the becoming steps of the project.

The legal and political framework conditions in the pilot regions involved vary and the uniqueness of the situation in every pilot region is respected in this analysis. Therefore, the analysis of the policy mix is based on a brief consideration of the respective governance structures related to rural policy and rural development. In this deliverable, Needs-Policy Canvases are presented in as tables that include the columns: need, title of the policy/programme, structural/investment fund, policy level, link to the policy document.

These Needs-Policy Canvases will be used in later stages of the PoliRural project next in the last task of Work Package 4 *Current Rural Situation T4.5. Policy Evaluation* to address the needs and policies and measures covered in the regions at the moment and then also as an important baseline for the work in WP5 *Future Rural Outlook*.

Keywords

Rural needs, rural policy, policy mapping, rural development

1 Introduction

The purpose of this deliverable is to collect the results of Needs-Policy Mapping task (T4.4) that aims to match the rural needs of 12 PoliRural pilot regions against current policies and public or private strategies present in their region. The goal is to understand how the needs recognized in *T4.3 Needs gathering and analysis* are being addressed and whether there is a corresponding measure for every need or barrier. Deliverable D1.3 Needs Gathering & Policy Mapping Template has provided preliminary guidelines and templates for policy mapping task. Deliverable D1.3 provided an overview of possible approaches leaving the pilots the autonomy to perform the policy-mapping in the manner best suited for each individual pilot.

Policy is usually intended as being led by public bodies (i.e. European Commission, national ministries, local authorities etc.). In the context of PoliRural it is, however, considered important to include also private and third sector (i.e. NGOs) initiatives that may have an impact or provide a response to identified needs. In this context, both public and private bodies and organisations are included in the notion of policy makers. In this policy mapping exercise pilots should try to reach out to policy makers at different levels (local, regional and national).

In chapter 2 the methodology and schedule for needs-policy mapping is explained. The aim of the chapter 2 is to give all 12 pilot regions common guidelines for conducting policy mapping task and give to the pilots an overview of the relevant EU policy programmes. This methodology was later refined accordingly to monitor comments from the 1st official review. The legal and political framework conditions in the pilot regions involved vary. An analysis of the policy mix must therefore be based on a brief consideration of the respective governance structures. The planned policy mapping builds on the recognised preliminary work at EU and OECD level in classifying policy instruments and measures.

The policy matching process takes place in close collaboration with regional policy actors, who will be briefed on the needs of grassroot populations during face-to-face meetings or online meetings with the research team of every pilot. Their main role is to provide information about existing policy measures. At the same time, they will be able to comment on the identified needs and alert the team to new ones that may have been missed in T4.3. Needs without a matching measure will be addressed in starting work packages at later stages of the project through design thinking at a dedicated workshop session.

In chapter 3 all pilot regions present the results of their policy mapping exercise. Pilot presentations begin with an overview of political structures related to rural policy and rural development (chapters 3.X.1). In earlier phases of PoliRural pilots have set the mission statement for PoliRural work and recognised the needs and factors of rural attractiveness in their region. Mission statements and needs are described in chapters 3.X.2 to set the context for policy mapping. The most relevant needs and matching policies are recognised using excel template (annex 1) and collected to needs-policy canvases (chapters 3.X.3).

Chapter 4 gives the conclusion of policy mapping exercise and explains the next steps of PoliRural project.

2 Schedule and methods for needs-policy mapping

The duration of previous task T4.3 Needs Gathering & Analysis was extended with three months to last until the end of May 2020 as deviation to original project plan in the Grant Agreement (the original due date for T4.3 was the end of February 2020). Therefore, this Policy mapping task (T4.4) was made simultaneously with the Needs gathering task. The process of the extension of T4.3 is described in detail in D4.2 Grassroot Needs and Factors of Rural Attractiveness. The fact that these two tasks were ongoing simultaneously did not affect the work because of the good communication and coordination with the responsible task leaders.

Policy mapping task began at the beginning of March 2020. Schedule in policy mapping task was:

- Guidelines for pilot partners 1.3.-13.3.2020 (HAMK)
- Work in pilot regions 13.3.-12.5.2020 (Pilots)
- First version of the deliverable D4.4 to Redmine 17.4.2020 (HAMK)
- Collecting input from pilots to D4.4: 11.5.-14.5.2020 (HAMK)
- Draft version of D4.4 for internal reviewers and pilots, uploaded to Redmine 15.5.2020 (HAMK, internal reviews)
- Final version to Redmine 24.5.2020 (HAMK, 7 days before due date)
- Final report 31.5.2020 (M12)

2.1 Description of respective governance structures related to rural development

The legal and political framework conditions in the pilot regions involved vary. An analysis of the policy mix must therefore be based on a brief consideration of the respective governance structures related to rural policy and rural development. Which institutions make/influence policies on rural development?

Pilots were advised to find their country in the list of AKIS reports below and reflect on the network's relevance to the task. The purpose of this reference to PRO-AKIS project is to be a background material for the policy structures for the pilots and to facilitate the work. Bearing in mind that these reports were prepared several years ago (2014), pilots were encouraged to think about missing actors, obsolete actors, new actors that emerged and therefore don't show up in these reports.

<https://430a.uni-hohenheim.de/please-change-url-alias-114438429>

2.2 Mission statement and the needs of pilot regions

In earlier phases of the project all pilot regions have created a pilot description and mission statement. These statements set the goal for PoliRural work in each pilot regions. Statements drive from each pilot regions individual mission statement, an overall ambition which comes from regions unique circumstances, challenges, and opportunities. Due to the uniqueness of the pilots, the relevant policy measures assessed are also measures that each pilot has experienced in their own area as the most significant influencer in relation to the needs-gathering, pilot theme and overall ambition.

In preceding task *T4.3 Regional needs gathering and analysis* pilot regions have identified the main needs of their regions through SWOT analyses. The needs have been discussed together with regional panels and ranked according to their relevance and importance. These different needs between pilot areas leads to differences in matching needs canvas between pilots. However, each pilot is the best expert in their region with their wide range of stakeholders engaged throughout the process. These needs are shortly described in this report and listed to excel table (Annex 1).

2.3 Matching needs with policy measures in Needs-Policy canvas

The identified needs are matched against current EU policies and public or private strategies present in the pilot region. Pilots will match the EU-co-funded programs with their national/regional level implementation. The EU provides several funding schemes to support policy measures on

regional & urban development
employment & social inclusion
employment & social inclusion
agriculture & rural development
maritime & fisheries policies
research & innovation
humanitarian aid.

Table 1. Themes EU provides policy measures on

Management of funds is politically strictly managed by the EU Commissioners but the member states are responsible of the control and annual audits of the funds in their own governments.

Almost 80% of the EU budget is managed jointly with national and regional authorities. This is done by five (5) major funds which are called the Structural and Investment Funds. All of this funding aims to help the implementation of the Europe2020 strategy in every Member State. These 5 big funds have focus on:

European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) – regional and urban development
European Social Fund (ESF) – social inclusion and good governance
European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD)
Cohesion Fund (CF) – economic convergence by less-developed regions
European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF)

Table 2. Structural and Investment funds

All pilots will match the programs to EU-funding schemes when programs are funded under these funds. Aim is to understand how the needs are being addressed and whether there is a corresponding measure for every need or barrier. PoliRural is particularly keen to know how barriers specific to new entrants are addressed. Work on this will continue in WP5 *Future Rural Outlook* as a part of pilot’s foresight initiative.

2.3.1 Excel template for policy mapping

All 12 PoliRural pilots have collected the rural needs with matching policy measures to an Excel template (Annex 1) that was developed to support pilots in needs policy mapping. First version of the template was presented in *D1.3 Needs Gathering and Policy Mapping Template*. The excel template includes following columns and instructions:

- A. Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)
 - a. Needs that are recognised in T4.3 and ranked most important. You can choose 3-6 most relevant needs to this exercise. Pilot regions can decide how many needs they want to take to this stage of the project.
- B. Target group (socio-demographic group)
 - a. Choose from drop down menu (established populations, new entrants, young people, women, other, N/A), use option N/A, if not possible to define
- C. Title of the policy/programme/strategy
 - a. Name of the policy/programme/strategy. There can be several policies related to one need (international level, EU level, regional level and local/grassroot level). Put each policy to its own row.

- D. Level at which the policy is launched
 - a. choose from drop down menu
- E. Category of the policy/programme/strategy
 - a. this refers to the initiators/owners of the policy/programme
 - b. options: Public policy/Public programme/Private sector measure (what businesses, big and small, are doing to help rural areas, farmers etc.)/Third sector measures (what charities and NGOs are doing)/Private and local initiatives (activities implemented by a single person or a group of residents)
- F. Responsible organisation
- G. Duration / Starting date of the policy
- H. How policy addresses the needs? (e.g. providing money, technology, training)
- I. Other comments
- J. Contact/Website of the policy

2.3.2 Needs-Policy Canvas

In the chapter 3 of this deliverable, Needs-Policy Canvases are presented as tables that include the columns: need, title of the policy/programme, structural/investment fund, policy level, link to the policy document (Table 1). The Excel document “Need_policy_mapping_all_pilots.xls” (Annex 1) includes the complete information related to needs-policy mapping. The needs-policy canvases can be transformed to more visual format for dissemination in later stages of the project. Figure 1 presents an example of more visual canvas presentation.

Table 3. Example of the needs-policy canvas table

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
Need 01	Policy A	National level	www.linktowebsite.eu
	Policy B	Regional level	
	Policy C	Local level	
Need 02	Policy A	National level	
	Policy B	Regional level	
	Policy C	Local level	
	Policy D	EU level	

Figure 1. Example of needs-policy canvas visualisation.

2.3.3 Discussions with policy actors and regional panels during policy mapping process

The matching process in 12 pilot regions took place in close collaboration with regional policy makers, who were briefed on the needs of grassroots populations during online meetings with the research team of every pilot. Their main role is to provide information on existing policy measures, first and foremost in the public sector.

To identify private or third sector initiatives, pilots crowdsourced information from their stakeholder panels, and did additional desk research if necessary. At the same time, policy makers and stakeholder panels were able to comment on the identified needs and alert the team to new ones that may have been missed in T4.3.

According to project plan in Grant Agreement, discussions with policy makers and stakeholders was planned to do during face-to-face meeting. Because of global COVID19 pandemic and restrictions for meetings, communication was made online using teleconferences, online meetings, online workshops of phone interviews.

3 Needs-Policy mapping in 12 pilot regions

3.1 Pilot 1 Flanders, Belgium

3.1.1 Description of respective governance structures

Flanders is the northern region of Belgium. It covers an area of 13 521 km² and counts approximately 6.35 million inhabitants. The region has a very high population density (475 inhabitants per km²) which is more than four times the average density of the European Union. Only 7% of the area is rural and 2.5% of the population lives in the rural area. The average age

of farmers is more than 50 years (only 5% of farmers are younger than 35 years).¹ Few farmers have a successor. Young farmers suffer from a lack of funds when starting up and therefore need some support.

The Flemish countryside is highly urbanised with a very fragmented landscape and strong links between countryside and cities. From a geographical, functional and cultural points of view, rural and urban areas are increasingly interlinked. Forests and nature cover a mere 1 850 km². Agricultural land comprises 6 230 km² out of which 70% is arable. Meadows, pasturelands and fodder crops account for 56% of the total area. Representing a regional share of 36 to 50% of the utilised agricultural area, grasslands are a dominant land feature of the rural landscape. The agricultural land is 36% owned, the rest is on lease.

With high land pressures, agriculture in Flanders (Belgium) is highly industrialised. The largest portion is taken by intensive sectors such as pig breeding, poultry and dairy farming, horticulture and ornamental plant culture. Farming in Flanders is intensive, with high yields per hectare. This is inevitably linked to higher consumption of fertilisers and plant protection products, negative impacts on soil and water quality, and biodiversity loss. Horticulture, comprising fruit, vegetables and potatoes, have increasingly suffered from the effects of adverse weather conditions.

Agriculture and rural development is under regional responsibility in Belgium. In Flanders there are several institutions responsible for agriculture governance:

- **Flemish Land Agency (VLM):** This agency is committed to enhance the countryside and open spaces to enable them to better endure urbanisation, fragmentation and climate change. The agency is collaborating on policy and investing in soil and water quality, biodiversity and infrastructure. The agency is actively shaping the rural policy in Flanders. The key objectives are area-specific rural policy, supporting local initiatives and improving the quality of life in rural areas.²
- **Department of Agriculture and Fisheries (DLV):** deals with the development, implementation, control and evaluation of all matters in the field of agriculture, horticulture, fisheries and the countryside. The department works in close cooperation with the Minister of Agriculture. The application of the European agriculture policy is one of the main tasks of this department. They work in collaboration with Flanders' Agricultural Marketing Board (**VLAM**), the Institute for Agricultural and Fisheries Research (**ILVO**) and the Strategic Advisory Council for Agriculture and Fisheries (**SALV**) for the development of the agriculture and fishery policy in Flanders³

¹ <https://www.statistiekvlaanderen.be/nl/leeftijd-bedrijfshoofd-van-landbouwbedrijven>

² <https://www.vlm.be/en>

³ <https://lv.vlaanderen.be/en>

- **VLAM:** Aims to promote the sale, the added value and the consumption of products and services from Flemish agriculture.⁴
- **ILVO:** Performs research in agriculture and fisheries.⁵
- **SALV:** The main task of SALV is to give advice to the regional Flemish government and the Flemish Parliament concerning agriculture and fisheries. The board of SALV consists of representative from 19 stakeholder organizations of the agriculture and horticulture sector.⁶
- **Department of Environment (DO):** deals with the quality of the environment, in which sustainable use is made of various resources and the available space for the development of an integrated environmental policy (space, environment, nature and energy) that focuses on policy preparation and implementation, broadening support, regulatory enforcement and policy evaluation cooperation with cities, municipalities and provinces for local environmental policy. Cities and municipalities are the first point of contact for citizens.⁷
- **Farmer's Unions:** There are three main farmer unions in Flanders: Boerenbond, Bioforum (organic farming) and Algemeen Boerensyndicaat. The farmer union Boerenbond is the biggest union in Flanders. It is a professional association of farmers active in Belgium's Flemish and German-speaking communities. Founded in 1890 and based in Leuven, the organisation promotes the interests of farmers working within their regions of activity.⁸
- **Regional Landscapes Associations:** There are 16 regional landscapes associations in Flanders. The aim of these associations is to promote the development and character of landscapes in Flanders, emphasizing their cultural, historical and natural value.⁹

3.1.2 Mission statement and the needs of pilot regions

Pressure on open space is increasing in Flanders. Open space is the place for food production, nature, water, energy generation and recreation. In places where open space prevails, the challenge is to better align the landscape and urbanisation and find a robust balance between water, agriculture and nature. In the open space numerous challenges simultaneously come to the foreground: climate change, water management, food production, renewable energy, and biodiversity. The overall regional goal for rural Flanders is to reach sustainable intensification of productive landscapes by balancing increased production with environmental concerns and climate resilience. Emerging from this goal is the need to focus on climate resilient productive landscapes.

⁴ <http://www.agrifood-promotion.eu/our-members/flanders-agricultural-marketing-board-vlam/>

⁵ <https://www.ilvo.vlaanderen.be/language/en-US/EN/About-ILVO.aspx#.Xs5T8WgzZPY>

⁶ <https://www.salv.be/salv/pagina/wat-doen-we>

⁷ <https://omgeving.vlaanderen.be/missie-en-visie>

⁸ <https://www.boerenbond.be/over-ons/missie>

⁹ <https://www.regionalelandschappen.be/regional-landscapes-flanders/7993>

The overall ambition is to create sustainable climate resilient productive landscapes, balancing agricultural intensification with environmental concerns and climate resilience. The ambition is to develop (1) strategies for supporting climate resilient productive rural landscapes, (2) more inclusive regulatory tools for land and water management, (3) a better functioning system of aligning landscape and urbanisation.

The following specific needs were identified:

Priority	Need
7	N01 Improve (public) transport
8	N02 Further develop rural tourism
5	N03 Enhance social inclusion, reduce poverty and improve economic development in rural areas e.g. need for specialized housing and other services for elderly and poor people
6	N04 Actions to avoid conflicts between newcomers in rural areas and inhabitants of rural areas.
3	N05 Support farmers, and encourage young and new farmers
4	N06 Enhance and ensure the heritage and patrimony of rural areas, rural landscape as cultural heritage (e.g. small landscape elements)
2	N07 Find a balance between nature and agriculture in highly fragmented rural landscape
1	N08 Climate smart and innovative agriculture: agricultural sector needs to deal with the challenges and opportunities related with climate change e.g. drought

3.1.3 Matching needs with policy measures in Needs-Policy Canvas

Table 4. Needs-Policy canvas in Flanders, Belgium

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
N08 Climate smart and innovative agriculture: agricultural sector needs to deal with the challenges and opportunities related with climate change e.g. drought	PDPO III: Measure 4: aid for on-farm investment	EAFRD	Regional level	https://lv.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/attachments/pdpo_iii_maatregel_4.pdf
	PDPO III: Measure 10: agri-environment measures	EAFRD	Regional level	https://lv.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/attachments/pdpo_iii_maatregel_10.pdf
	PDPO III: Measure 16: collaboration	EAFRD	Regional level	https://lv.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/attachments/pdpo_iii_maatregel_16.pdf
	Innovatiesteunpunt	Farmer union (Boerenbond), landelijke gilden, national bank (cera & KBC)	Regional level	https://www.innovatiesteunpunt.be/nl/landbouw/over/isp
N07 Find a balance between nature and agriculture in highly fragmented rural landscape	PDPO III: Measure 7: basic facilities and investments in rural areas	EAFRD	Regional level	https://lv.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/attachments/pdpo_iii_maatregel_7.pdf
	PDPO III: Measure 8: forest area development and viability of forests	EAFRD	Regional level	https://lv.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/attachments/pdpo_iii_maatregel_8.pdf
	PDPO III: Measure 10: agri-environment measures	EAFRD	Regional level	https://lv.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/attachments/pdpo_iii_maatregel_10.pdf
	PDPO III: Measure 11: organic farming	EAFRD	Regional level	https://lv.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/attachments/pdpo_iii_maatregel_11.pdf
N05 Support farmers, and encourage young and new farmers	PDPO III: Measure 1: knowledge transfer and information	EAFRD	Regional level	https://lv.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/attachments/pdpo_iii_maatregel_1.pdf
	PDPO III: Measure 2: business advisory services, business management services and business care services	EAFRD	Regional level	https://lv.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/attachments/pdpo_iii_maatregel_2.pdf
	PDPO III: Measure 6: farm and business development	EAFRD	Regional level	https://lv.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/attachments/pdpo_iii_maatregel_6.pdf
	PDPO III: Measure 9: establishment of producer organizations	EAFRD	Regional level	https://lv.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/attachments/pdpo_iii_maatregel_9.pdf
	vzw boeren op een kruispunt	Farmer unions, agriculture department, national bank (cera), provinces	Local /grassroot level	https://www.boerenopeenkruispunt.be/

N06 Enhance and ensure the heritage and patrimony of rural areas, rural landscape as cultural heritage (e.g. small landscape elements)	PDPO III: Measure 7: basic facilities and investments in rural areas	EAFRD	Regional level	https://lv.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/attachments/pdpo_iii_maatregel_7.pdf
N03 Enhance social inclusion, reduce poverty and improve economic development in rural areas e.g. need for specialized housing and other services for elderly and poor people	PDPO III: Measure 7: basic facilities and investments in rural areas	EAFRD	Regional level	https://lv.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/attachments/pdpo_iii_maatregel_7.pdf
	PDPO III: Measure 16: collaboration	EAFRD	Regional level	https://lv.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/attachments/pdpo_iii_maatregel_16.pdf
	Innovatiesteunpunt	Farmer union (Boerenbond), landelijke gilden, national bank (cera & KBC)	Regional level	https://www.innovatiesteunpunt.be/nl/landbouw/over/isp
	Landelijke gilden	Farmer union	Regional level	https://www.landelijkegilden.be/over-ons
N01 Improve (public) transport	PDPO III: Measure 7: basic facilities and investments in rural areas	EAFRD	Regional level	https://lv.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/attachments/pdpo_iii_maatregel_7.pdf
N02 Further develop rural tourism	PDPO III: Measure 7: basic facilities and investments in rural areas	EAFRD	Regional level	https://lv.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/attachments/pdpo_iii_maatregel_7.pdf

3.2 Pilot 2 Monaghan, Ireland

3.2.1 Description of respective governance structures

County Monaghan is a mainly rural county in the Republic of Ireland, on the border with Northern Ireland which is in the UK. Monaghan County Council¹⁰ is the local authority for the county. However, most agriculture and rural development policies and programmes are centrally driven and funded by Ireland's Government and the EU. County Monaghan is the fifth smallest of the Irish Republic's 26 counties in area (1295km²) and fourth smallest by population (61,386), with 63% of the county's population living in a rural area¹¹. The county is strategically located on the Donegal/Derry – Dublin corridor, adjacent to the M1 corridor and has strong links to Northern Ireland.

¹⁰ <https://monaghan.ie/>

¹¹ <https://monaghan.ie/communitydevelopment/monaghan-economic-community-monitor/>

During the period 1991-2018, the population of Ireland grew from 3.5 million to 4.8 million, however the number of people living in rural Ireland (areas outside the cities and towns) remained relatively constant at about 1.8 million, representing a drop from 51% of the population nationally to 38%. There was substantial spatial variation over the period, with some areas experiencing very large increases in population, while others experienced declines in population. County Monaghan grew by just over 9,300 to 61,386 (in 2016), or just under 1% compound each year, during this period.

The rural and agricultural sector in the Republic of Ireland is characterised by one of the highest proportions of family farms in Europe, producing mostly commodity products for export. The average age of farmers is lower than in most European countries¹². Dairy, beef and sheep are dominant in the livestock sector, with crops occupying less than 10% of the farmed area. The Republic of Ireland is unique in having a substantial component of its Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System within a single organisation (Teagasc, the Agriculture and Food Development Authority¹³). Teagasc undertakes activities in research, extension services and education, supported by an elaborate infrastructure, with on-going investment in buildings, facilities and equipment in research centres, analytical facilities and pilot plants, that spans the entire Agri-Food chain, from farm production through to food processing¹⁴. In addition, Teagasc runs, 12 local advisory service offices, about 90 farmer-run demonstration farms (so-called BETTER farms and Monitor Farms), and 800 discussion groups with about 12,000 members. Teagasc activities are complemented by private agricultural consultants and veterinarians, private research entities, universities and Institutes of Technology, government departments, various public agencies and numerous other actors and works closely with Local Development Companies at a local level. Ireland has retained a strong, largely publicly funded advisory service based on a model of recovering 33 per cent of its cost from farmers. Teagasc is the national body providing advisory services through its 250 field advisors. Public funded and private funded services coexist. There is a recognition that Government no longer needs to provide the sole source of finance for all of the services offered by a public advisory service, but it does need to support the provision of public goods which otherwise would not be provided due to market failures.¹⁵

The Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System in Ireland is summarised in the following¹⁶:

¹² <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/DDN-20180719-1?inheritRedirect=true>

¹³ <https://www.teagasc.ie/>

¹⁴ <https://www.teagasc.ie/food/research-infrastructure>

¹⁵ "AKIS and advisory services in the Republic of Ireland", Katrin Prager & Ken Thomson, The James Hutton Institute, 2014, https://430a.uni-hohenheim.de/fileadmin/einrichtungen/430a/PRO_AKIS/Country_Reports/Final_Draft-Country_Report_Ireland_4_.pdf

¹⁶ file:///C:/Active%20EU%20Projects/PoliRural/WP4%20Current%20Rural%20Sitn%20-%20Pilot%20Pha1/AKIS%20Ireland_poster_16_06_2014_to_print.pdf, while this is from 2005 the situation is still quite similar in Ireland.

Figure 2. AKIS diagram for Ireland

The current governance structures and institutions that make/influence policies on rural development in County Monaghan are summarised in the following table:

Table 5. Governance structures related to rural policy and rural development in county Monaghan

Status of organisation	Type of organisation	Organisation
Public sector	Government Departments	Department of Rural and Community Development Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine Department of Business, Enterprise and Innovation Department of the Taoiseach
	Local Authority	Monaghan County Council
	Government Agencies	Teagasc (Agriculture and Food Development Authority) Bord Bia – Irish Food Board Food Safety Authority Environment Protection Agency Irish Cattle Breeding Federation Animal Health Ireland Enterprise Ireland - government organisation responsible for the development and growth of Irish enterprises IDA Ireland – agency responsible for overseas investment Health Research Board Higher Education Authority Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland
	Local/regional agencies	Monaghan Integrated Development CLG - LEADER Implementing Partner (MIDL) Teagasc <i>Monaghan Local Advisory Office</i>

Status of organisation	Type of organisation	Organisation
		Local Enterprise Office Monaghan (LEO) Monaghan LCDC Local Action Group
Research and Education	Vocational/ Further Education	Monaghan Institute, Monaghan Vocational Education Committee (VEC) Ballyhaise Agricultural College, Cavan,
	Universities & Higher Education Institutes	Various Universities and Institutes of Technology across Ireland and Northern Ireland with the Dundalk Institute of Technology being the closest to Monaghan.
	Research Institutes & Foundations	Teagasc Food Research Centres at Ashtown (Dublin 15) and Moorepark (Fermoy, Co. Cork) COFORD Council for Forest Research and Development (Dublin) Science Foundation Ireland Various Universities and Institutes of Technology across Ireland and Northern Ireland
Private sector	Food chain actors	Commercial advisors of input supply, service and food processing companies (but only a fraction of their time is spent on advice) Veterinarians AHI Animal Health Ireland Farm Relief Services (FRS)
	Private agricultural consultants	Independent advisors, represented by Agricultural Consultants Association of Ireland
	Cooperatives	Irish Milk Quality Co-operative Society Irish Co-operative Organisation Society (ICOS) - 2 dairy co-ops, a fishing and food co-op, 3 community co-ops, but no marts co-op in county Monaghan) IFAC Monaghan - Accountants Tax Advisors (also a farmer-based organisation)
	Other	Advisors employed by banks
Farmer based Organisations & NGOs	Farmers' circles/groups	Teagasc demonstration farms 800 Discussion groups (supported mainly by Teagasc)
	Land manager representative bodies	Irish Farmers' Association (IFA) Macra na Feimre – Irish Young Farmers ICMSA Irish Creamery Milk Suppliers Association ICSA The Irish Cattle and Sheep Farmers' Association
	Charitable trusts, foundations, NGOs	Irish Shows Association (national representative body of Agricultural Shows) National Ploughing Championships Grain and Feed association The Fertilizer Association of Ireland Irish Grain and Feed Association

Rural Development in Ireland is managed nationally through **one Rural Development Programme (RDP)**, funded under the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD)¹⁷ and national contributions. The RDP sets out priority approaches and actions to

¹⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/cap-funding_en

meet the needs of the specific geographical area it covers.¹⁸ Nationally, rural development funding through the EAFRD is part of a broader framework of European Structural and Investment Funds (ESI Funds)¹⁹, including also Regional Development, Social, Cohesion, and Fisheries Funds. These are managed nationally, by each EU Member State, based on **Partnership Agreements**, strategic plans outlining the country's goals and investment priorities.

The LEADER programme supports many local projects in County Monaghan²⁰. The programme is administered by Monaghan Local Action Group (LAG) with the County Monaghan Local Community Development Committee (LCDC) operating as the LAG for the County. Monaghan Integrated Development CLG (MIDL), the Local Development Company for County Monaghan is the implementing partner and Monaghan County Council is the financial partner.

The funding is awarded based on a Local Development Strategy (LDS) which sets out the priority areas for the programme in Co. Monaghan. The priorities in the strategy were identified through extensive consultation with the local community and include the following:

1. **Economic Development, Enterprise Development and Job Creation.** This includes the sub-themes; Rural Tourism, Enterprise Development, Rural Towns and Broadband
2. **Social Inclusion.** This includes the sub-themes; Basic services targeted at hard to reach communities and Rural Youth.
3. **Rural Environment.** This includes sub-themes; Protection and sustainable use of water resources; Protection and improvement of local biodiversity; and Development of Renewable Energy.

The LEADER programme²¹ accepts applications based on projects which improve:

- rural tourism
- enterprise development
- broadband
- basic services targeted at hard-to-reach communities
- rural youth
- protection and sustainable use of water resources
- local biodiversity
- renewable energy

¹⁸ https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/country/ireland_en

¹⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/european-structural-and-investment-funds_en

²⁰ See "LEADER Delivering For Co Monaghan" for a flavour of local projects funded at <https://www.nationalruralnetwork.ie/leader-news/leader-delivering-for-county-monaghan/>. The MIDL website provides updates on the projects being funded, at <https://www.midl.ie/index.php/programmes/leader-framework/press>

²¹ <https://www.gov.ie/en/policy-information/179274-leader-rural-development/>

In addition to the core themes outlined above there is also a set of cross-cutting objectives; 1) Innovation, (2) Climate Change and (3) Environment. These cross-cutting objectives form an integral part of the Monaghan LDS with a view to developing projects in keeping with its natural environment, encourage innovative approaches whilst striving to mitigate the impacts of climate change. The LEADER programme remains one of the key development programmes working with local communities to stimulate and advance rural development.

Regarding policies, programmes and funding, *“Realising our Rural Potential”* is the Irish Government’s current Action Plan for Rural Development²². Through a framework of supports at national and local level, the Action Plan takes a coordinated approach across Government Departments to both the economic and social development of rural Ireland. The Plan covers a three-year period and contains a series of time-bound actions which are monitored and reported on regularly.

The key objectives of the plan are to:

- support sustainable and vibrant rural communities,
- support enterprise and employment;
- maximise rural tourism and recreation potential;
- foster culture and creativity in rural communities; and
- improve rural infrastructure and connectivity.

The Plan contains over 270 time-bound actions with responsibility for each action assigned to a relevant Department and/or Agency.

The Irish Government’s Department of Rural and Community Development is currently developing “Rural Development Policy 2020+” a new, whole-of-Government rural development policy for Ireland, but it has not yet been finalised and published²³. This will follow on from the current Action Plan which was published in January 2017. The new rural policy will have a 5-year timeframe, and will focus on strengthening Ireland’s rural communities and economies, taking account of:

- emerging economic, societal and international developments, including changing demographics within rural communities
- the increasing focus on climate change adaptation, diversification in the agri-food sector
- the next version of rural funding schemes (for example, CAP²⁴ and LEADER²⁵)
- new ways of working and the changing nature of jobs
- BREXIT

²² <https://www.gov.ie/en/publication/091dba-realising-our-rural-potential-action-plan-for-rural-development/>

²³ <https://www.gov.ie/en/consultation/966394-public-consultation-on-rural-development-policy-2020>

²⁴ <https://www.agriculture.gov.ie/agri-foodindustry/euinternationalpolicy/commonagriculturalpolicycap/>

²⁵ <https://www.gov.ie/en/policy-information/179274-leader-rural-development/>

The new plan will in particular consider:

- Sustainable Communities - As part of Project Ireland 2040²⁶ the Irish government has committed to providing an additional €1 billion over the period 2019 to 2027 for the Rural Regeneration and Development Fund²⁷. This will provide investments to renew towns and villages with a population of less than 10,000 people.
 - The fund will provide opportunities to revitalise rural Ireland, make significant impacts on rural communities, and address de-population. Funding will be awarded through a competitive bid process, based on the objectives in the Irish National Planning Framework²⁸.
 - Targeted action is needed to support the regeneration of towns and villages. The Town and Village Renewal Scheme²⁹ covers a range of projects to support and promote rural areas. The projects that receive funding will be decided by local authorities, businesses and communities.
- Enterprise and Employment - Future employment opportunities in rural areas will require measures to support rural entrepreneurship.
 - Under the LEADER Rural Development Programme³⁰, €250 million in grant aid is available to rural communities and businesses. This is provided to projects focused on economic and enterprise development, job creation, social inclusion and supporting the rural environment. Funding is allocated to 28 sub-regional areas based on administrative or county boundaries, of which County Monaghan is one.
 - The Ceantair Laga Árd-Riachtanais, or CLÁR³¹, is an investment programme for small-scale infrastructural projects in depopulated rural areas. CLÁR supports the development of identified areas by attracting people to live and work there. Most of County Monaghan is included in this programme³².
- Tourism and Recreation - Tourism is Ireland's largest indigenous industry-employing 230,000 people nationally. Growing this industry is a key priority, as outlined in "Tourism Development and Innovation: A Strategy for Investment 2016-2022"³³.

²⁶ <https://www.gov.ie/en/campaigns/09022006-project-ireland-2040/>

²⁷ <https://www.gov.ie/en/policy-information/c77144-rural-regeneration-and-development-fund/>

²⁸ <http://npf.ie/>

²⁹ <https://www.gov.ie/en/policy-information/01125e-town-and-village-renewal-scheme/>

³⁰ <https://www.gov.ie/en/policy-information/179274-leader-rural-development/>

³¹ <https://www.gov.ie/en/policy-information/91ba52-clar/>

³² <https://assets.gov.ie/2969/151118163917-fa538ab9bd894d9c9ccef5dcea48a5a.pdf>

³³ <https://www.gov.ie/en/publication/57ace4-tourism-development-innovation-a-strategy-for-investment-2016-2022/>

- Infrastructure and Connectivity - The protection and promotion of the Irish landscape and making rural Ireland more attractive to live, work and visit is a major part of the Action Plan for Rural Development³⁴

The Local Improvement Scheme³⁵ provides funding for improvements to private and non-publicly maintained roads. Such roads can lead to multiple residences, farmland or amenities like lakes, rivers or beaches.

Delivering high speed broadband to every citizen and business in Ireland is the remit of Ireland's National Broadband Plan (NBP)³⁶.

At county level the key policy document is the Monaghan County Development Plan 2019-2025³⁷ developed by Monaghan County Council, which aims to

1. Develop to its full potential each part of County Monaghan in economic, social and environmental terms.
2. Sustain traditional settlement patterns while developing the role and function of each town, village and settlement throughout the County in accordance with the settlement strategy.
3. Realise the potential of County Monaghan in the context of its strategic location along the border, adjacent to the eastern economic corridor and to improve linkages and communications between Monaghan and its neighbouring counties.
4. Support balanced economic development throughout the county by delivering improved infrastructure and services.
5. Protect and nurture the County's rich natural resources, heritage, tourism assets and amenities along with the environmental quality of the natural and built environment in both the urban and rural areas.
6. Plan for greater social inclusion and to improve the quality of life of all who live and work in County Monaghan.
7. Provide a framework for the management and regulation of development and use of land that will guide day to day planning decisions.
8. Maintain the strategic capacity and safety of the national roads network and to safeguard the investment in national roads.

At the local community level, the "Monaghan Local Economic and Community Plan 2015-2021" plan³⁸ sets out the objectives and actions needed to promote and support the economic development as well as the local and community development of the County both by the Council and in partnership with other economic and community development stakeholders.

³⁴ <https://www.gov.ie/en/publication/091dba-realising-our-rural-potential-action-plan-for-rural-development/>

³⁵ <https://www.gov.ie/en/policy-information/d309ea-local-improvement-scheme/>

³⁶ <https://www.gov.ie/en/policy-information/64ad0b-the-national-broadband-plan/>

³⁷ <https://monaghan.ie/planning/wp-content/uploads/sites/4/2019/04/Monaghan-County-Development-Plan-2019-2025---Written-Statement.pdf> <https://monaghan.ie/planning/new-county-development-plan/>

³⁸ <https://assets.gov.ie/30330/cabe9d3122594e9ca02ad52d3fc8dc95.pdf>

3.2.2 Mission statement and the needs of pilot regions

The Monaghan Irish PoliRural Pilot's Mission was agreed with its User Panel to be:

To explore the potential of non-traditional entrants to enter farming or employment in rural Monaghan. The pilot will look at what supports they will need to succeed. The goal is to build upon existing programs to ensure the availability of the needed support.

From the PoliRural D4.2 Monaghan Pilot's SWOT/Needs analysis and User Panel feedback, the needs of the pilot were identified to be in ranked order (with their "N" code number from the D4.2 analysis) as follows:

- 1 Provide support schemes that encourage new entrants & young people into farming (N06)
- 2 Improve the financial security of farming through greater diversification, access to finance & alternatives to land purchase. (N07)
- 3 Proactive promotion of the rural area to attract newcomers (N01)
- 4 Encourage more sustainable agriculture, production of vegetables & forestry development (N09)
- 5 Address BREXIT uncertainty (N05)
- 6 More sustainable rural development planning, & proactive response to climate change. (N10)
- 7 Increase employment opportunities in rural areas (N04)
- 8 CAP reform, e.g. LEADER & European Innovation Partnership (EIP) Farmer Groups should be flexible enough to respond to local needs (N08)
- 9 Improve broadband access & ICT skills. (N03)
- 10 Provide better access to public services and public transport in all remote dispersed rural areas. (N02)

3.2.3 Matching needs with policy measures in Needs-Policy Canvas

After further phone discussions with members of the Monaghan Pilot's User Panel the top ranked list of needs from section 3.2.2 was modified slightly and reduced to the following top 6 needs in the PoliRural pilot:

- 1 Provide support schemes that encourage new entrants & young people into farming (N06)
- 2 Improve the financial security of farming through greater diversification, access to finance & alternatives to land purchase. (N07)
- 3 Proactive promotion of the rural area to attract newcomers (N01)
- 4 Encourage more sustainable agriculture, production of vegetables & forestry development (N09)
- 5 Address BREXIT uncertainty (N05)
- 6 Increase employment opportunities in rural areas (N04)

Table 6. Needs-Policy Canvas, Monaghan, Ireland

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
1. Provide support schemes that encourage new entrants & young people into farming (N06)	CAP, LEADER/EIP	ERDF, EAFRD	Regional level	www.midl.ie , https://www.gov.ie/en/campaigns/955114-rural-development-policy-2020
2. Improve the financial security of farming through greater diversification, access to finance & alternatives to land purchase. (N07)	Rural Development Programme (RDP)	ERDF	National level	https://www.gov.ie/en/policy-information/179274-leader-rural-development
3. Proactive promotion of the rural area to attract newcomers (N01)	Rural Development Policy 2020+ - LEADER	EAFRD, ERDF	Regional level	www.midl.ie , https://www.gov.ie/en/campaigns/955114-rural-development-policy-2020
4. Encourage more sustainable agriculture, production of vegetables & forestry development (N09)	Vegetable Production & Forestry development Plans	EAFRD	Regional level	https://www.teagasc.ie/crops/horticulture/vegetables https://www.agriculture.gov.ie/forests/forestrydevelopmentprogramme
5. Address BREXIT uncertainty (N05)	Rural Development Policy 2020+	ERDF	National level	https://www.gov.ie/en/campaigns/955114-rural-development-policy-2020
6. Increase employment opportunities in rural areas (N04)	Rural Development Policy 2020+ LEADER	EAFRD, ERDF	Regional level	www.midl.ie , https://www.localenterprise.ie/Monaghan , https://www.gov.ie/en/campaigns/955114-rural-development-policy-2020

3.3 Pilot 3 Segóbriga, Spain

3.3.1 Description of respective governance structures

Spain is a sparsely populated country with different rural settings, with varied characteristics. The rural areas are diversified, and the countryside does not fit to a single, clear-cut definition. National level rural areas cover 90% of the territory but only 20% of the Spanish population. Average population density is 19,79 persons/km².¹ The Spanish rural environment is masculinized and aged. 27% of the rural population is mainly dedicated to the agrarian sector,

being the main source of income in rural Spain. 35% of the rural population lives at risk of poverty or social exclusion³⁹.

As regards cohesion policy and EAFRD, the RDC currently distinguishes three categories of regions, based on the GDP per capita. The map (figure 3), shows the Spanish classification and Castilla-La Mancha region as a region “in transition”.

Less developed regions	GDP per capita is less than 75% of the EU-27 GDP average. (Red coloured in the map)
Regions in transition	GDP per capita is between 75% and 90% of the average GDP from the EU-27; (Orange coloured in the map)
More developed regions	GDP per capita is more than 90% of the EU-27 GDP average. (Pink coloured in the map)

Figure 3. Map of Spanish regional classification.

In Castilla-La Mancha region, rural population has decreased by 10% between 2000 and 2018, while the population of these rural areas represent 45% of the entire Castilian-La Mancha population. Segobriga pilot area is located in Cuenca province.

Cuenca, is the province in Castilla-La Mancha region with a higher % of decrease of the registered population since 2013, with a loss of 5.3% of the population of origin.

39

https://www.eapn.es/estadodepobreza/ARCHIVO/documentos/Informe_AROPE_2017_Resumen_Ejecutivo.pdf

Table 7. Evolution of the established population by provinces in Castilla- La Mancha. Source: INE (Spanish Statistical Institute)

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	% variation
Albacete	399.510	396.684	394.928	392.958	391.574	390.337	-2,3%
Ciudad Real	522.749	518.051	514.143	508.409	504.117	498.549	-4,6%
Cuenca	211.796	208.663	206.594	204.000	202.037	200.596	-5,3%
Guadalajara	257.101	255.240	254.558	254.280	255.332	256.029	-0,4%
Toledo	703.236	696.560	692.544	689.253	687.879	687.084	-2,3%
Castilla-la Mancha	2.094.392	2.075.198	2.062.767	2.048.900	2.040.939	2.032.595	-3,0%

According to the OECD classification, the territories could be:

- «Predominantly Rural Region»: regions where more than 50% of the population lives in communities considered rural.
- «Intermediate region»: when between 15 and 50% of the population it is rural.
- «Predominantly Urban Region»: less than 15% of the population lives in rural communities.

It is considered “rural” a local community with a density less than 150 inhab. / km²

More than 80% of the total municipalities in the province of Cuenca have densities below 10 inhabitants / km². So, it has a remarkable rural character.

Figure 4. Population density in Castilla-La Mancha region

In Spain, the regional governments of the Regional Departments (Comunidades Autónomas) are competent of agriculture matters according to article 148.1 of the Spanish Constitution.

Thus, Regional Governments are empowered to develop their own agrarian policy, aimed at satisfying their own interests, as long as it is taken into account that "political action must move within the guidelines and basic interventions and coordination that the National Government has for the agricultural sector".

However, it is the responsibility of the national Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food, to draw up state legislation in agricultural, fishing and food matters; the proposal and execution of the general guidelines of the Government on the agrarian, fishing and food policy; the representation of the State in the international organizations corresponding to these matters, without prejudice to the competences of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, European Union and Cooperation; as well as the coordination of actions, cooperation and consultation in the design and application of all policies that affect the sphere of competence of the autonomous communities and the other public administrations, promoting their participation through the cooperation bodies and suitable instruments.

Figure 5. Administration of rural policy in Segobriga's area

The Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food⁴⁰ is the competent Department within the scope of the General State Administration for the proposal and execution of the Government's policy regarding agricultural, livestock and fishing resources, the agri-food industry, rural development and feeding.

The General Secretary of Agriculture and Food is the directive organ of the Ministry directly responsible for the Common Agricultural Policy (PAC), rural development policy, irrigation policy and the development and coordination of multilateral relations in the framework of agri-food policies, innovation in the agricultural, food and rural sectors, and the food system.

In accordance with the 2014-2020 rural development policy of the EU, and with the national competence framework, 18 Rural Development Programs (RDPs) coexist in Spain:

- A National Rural Development Program (NRDP)
- 17 Regional Rural Development Programs (RDP)

Each Regional Government (Comunidad Autónoma), has prepared a Rural Development Program with specific measures to respond to different regional situations.

These RDP (17 RDP+1NRDP) are included in addition, the horizontal measures and the common elements established in the National Rural Development Framework, whose aims is

⁴⁰ Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food. <https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/>

to simplify the programming of the Spanish PDRs, reducing the administrative burden and, establishing common provisions.

The Ministry acts as the Coordination Body for the Spanish Management Authorities.

The National Rural Network (NRN)⁴¹ is a platform made up of the main actors related to the rural environment, whose mission is to promote rural development. The NRN creates a common scenario with the aim of disseminating information about Rural Development Programs (RDPs), communicating the opportunities they offer to their potential beneficiaries and strengthening alliances between people, entities and administration. At the same time, it has the responsibility of informing and raising awareness among the Spanish population about the importance of the rural environment for all, from the economic, social and environmental point of view. Its funding comes from the European Agrarian Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food.

Department of agriculture, water and rural development of Castilla- La Mancha⁴²

The General Directorate of Rural Development of Castilla- La Mancha, has the following functions:

- The planning and programming of rural development policy.
- Infrastructure for Rural Development and irrigation whose beneficiary is the Administration.
- Promotion of adaptation and endogenous development of rural areas.
- Experimentation, training and agricultural dissemination. Project management and agricultural research teams of the Ministry.
- Coordination of the Regional Network of Agricultural and Food Research and Technology Centers.
- The authorization and registration of laboratories that work with genetically modified organisms, as well as their contained use and voluntary release.
- Territorial property management.
- The direction of the Project Supervisory Office.
- Promotion of the improvement of the structures of commercialization and transformation of the agri-food products.
- Community aid to producer groups in the fruit and vegetable sector.
- Organization, guidance, defense and promotion of the Castilla-La Mancha Agrifood Quality Mark and of agrifood quality figures and other indications and certifications on specific characteristics of agrifood products, without prejudice to the powers of the

⁴¹National Rural Network <http://www.redruralnacional.es/inicio>

⁴²Department of Agriculture, Water and Rural Development. Regional Government of Castilla- La Mancha. <https://www.castillalamancha.es/gobierno/agriaguaydesrur>

General Directorate of Production Agriculture in the management of integrated production.

- Authorization and supervision of entities that control agri-food products. Relations with accreditation and standardization bodies.
- Recognition and supervision of the groups of fruit and vegetable producers and of the wine sector, as well as of the inter-professional agri-food organizations and of the management bodies of the quality figures. Processing of extension files of the norm of interprofessional agri-food organizations.
- Promotion of the cooperatives of production, transformation and commercialization of agricultural and livestock products.

Provincial Deputation of Cuenca⁴³. The task is the maintenance and support of the key productive sectors of agriculture and livestock in the province. All with realistic and commercial approaches, in order to support the development and promotion of local products.

Leader Local Group ADESIMAN⁴⁴ finance projects and investments of enterprises in line with the local development strategy ADESIMAN is the only Leader group operating in Segobriga pilot region. ADESIMAN comprises, through two associations (ADIMMAC and SEDECUCE), a total of 56 municipalities, and a large number of partners (youth, culture stakeholders, women, senior citizens, entrepreneurs), as well as cooperatives and agrarian organizations, companies, and a high number of self-employed professionals and individuals, among others.

ADESIMAN designs, implements and manages local development strategies for the territory of Segobriga since 1997. During the 2014-2020 period ADESIMAN has implemented a strategy whose objectives are:

- OB1 Improve innovation and human capital training in the territory
- OB2 SMEs, diversification and maintenance of productive and employment activities.
- OB3 Promotion of agri-food companies and marketing
- OB4 Consolidation of the tourism sector and enhancement of the resources related to it
- OB5 Provision of municipal infrastructure and services contributing to the reduction of the carbon footprint.
- As transversal objectives we would have.
- OT1 Environment.
- OT2 Mitigation of climate change and adaptation to it
- OT3 Innovation.

⁴³ Provincial Deputation of Cuenca. <https://www.dipucuenca.es/desarrollo-rural>

⁴⁴ ADESIMAN. LEADER LAG: <http://www.adesiman.org/>

Local government authorities Municipalities offer public services that help meet the needs and aspirations of neighbors.

The municipalities have, among others, competences in these matters: security in public places, urban planning, housing promotion and management, parks and gardens, supplies, social services and social promotion and reintegration, water supply and public lighting, street cleaning, waste collection and treatment, cultural and sports activities or facilities, ecc.

3.3.2 Mission statement and the needs of pilot regions

Mission statement for Segobriga's pilot (updated in stakeholder meeting 27.9.2019):

The pilot will use PoliRural results to boost the region's attractiveness by introducing policies that contribute to an activation of the economy of the territory, so that the living conditions of the inhabitants are improved as well as contributing to a more attractive territory for new settlers to come.

In that sense, it's important to promote economic diversification and maintenance of productive and employment activities, boosting the implementation of new technologies, related to the interpretation of heritage and nature, to reinforce the tourist sector generating an economic effect not only in the tourism sector but also in other industrial and business sectors of the territory.

After discussing with the regional panel, the most important issues in Segobriga's region are:

- N01 Avoid the exodus of young people and women from the territory and fight against depopulation
- N02 Promote job creation in rural areas, for the general population, with special emphasis on young people and women, promoting employment niches related to the circular economy, among others.
- N03. Guarantee quality access to the internet in the territory and improve the training of the population in the use of the internet and telematic services
- N04 Facilitate business development and entrepreneurship
- N05 Improve transportation service both within the territory and from the territory to urban areas, with particular attention to transportation to health services.
- N06 Improve the quality of health care service
- N07 Encourage vocational and higher education and training, particularly for youth and women
- N08 Guarantee sufficient and quality services (nurseries, electricity, drinking water, commercial services, fairgrounds, waste treatment services, etc.).
- N09 Promote economic diversification in a jointly organized way from the institutions and the private sector, through the tourist development of the area, taking advantage of the heritage and natural resources existing in the territory, correctly defining a tourist package as well as promoting a complementary offer.

- N10 Favour the profitability of the agricultural sector and promote economic diversification by promoting the development of agribusiness from existing raw materials, especially cereals with transformation, commercialization, organic products, local market, etc.

3.3.3 Matching needs with policy measures in Needs-Policy Canvas

Table 8. Needs-Policy Canvas, Segóbriga, Spain

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/s strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
N01 Avoid the exodus of young people and women from the territory and fight against depopulation	Local Development Strategy 2014-2020 ADESIMAN	EAFRD	Municipality level	http://www.adesiman.org/programa_de_desarrollo/Programa%20Desarrollo.html
	Integra 22	ESF	Municipality level	https://www.integra22.es/
	CUENCA PIEMSA "Information and Strategy Plan for the Improvement and Environmental Sustainability of the province of Cuenca"	ERDF	Municipality level	https://www.dipucuenca.es/cuenca-piensa
	Zone development strategy with depopulation and decline socioeconomic in Castilla-La Mancha	ERDF	Regional/county level	https://pagina.jccm.es/europa/pdf/PUBLICACIONES/2017%20folieto_informativo_itl.pdf
	National Strategy against the Demographic Challenge	NGEU	National level	https://www.google.es/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=3&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=2ahUKEwjOzLi0m8zoAhU6DGM BHd6ZDpkQFjACegQIAhAB&url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.mptfp.gob.es%2Fdam%2Fes%2Fportal%2Freto_demografico%2FEstrategia_Nacional%2Fdirectrices_generales_estrategia.pdf.pdf&usq=AOvVaw1DoyeL1y0Ijep9FH2plbYp
	Rural Development Program PDR 2014-2020 Castilla-La Mancha (EAFRD)	EAFRD	EU level	https://pdr.castillalamancha.es/
N02 Promote job creation in rural areas, for the general population, with	Local Development Strategy 2014-2020 ADESIMAN	EAFRD	Municipality level	http://www.adesiman.org/programa_de_desarrollo/Programa%20Desarrollo.html

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/s strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
special emphasis on youth and women.	Employment and Local Development Agents Network		Municipality level	https://www.dipucueca.es/aedl
	Castilla-La Mancha Circular Economy Strategy	NGEU/EAFRD	Regional/county level	https://www.castillamancha.es/gobierno/desarrollosostenible/estructura/dgecoci/actuaciones/consulta-p%C3%BAblica-sobre-la-estrategia-de-econom%C3%ADa-circular-de-castilla-la-mancha
	Digitalization Strategy of Castilla-La Mancha	EAFRD/NGEU	Regional/county level	https://adelanteempresas.castillamancha.es/sites/adelanteempresas.castillamancha.es/files/documentos/pdf/20200206/estrategia_soydigital_castilla-la_mancha_def_2.pdf
	Youth Employment Shock Plan	NGEU	National level	https://www.sepe.es/HomeSepe/Personas/encontrar-trabajo/plan-de-choque-empleo-joven-2019-2021.html
	Common Agrarian Policy (PAC)	EAGF	EU level	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/pac/
	Operational Program for Youth Employment of the European Social Fund	ESF	EU level	http://www.mitramis.gob.es/ficheros/garantiajuvenil/documentos/Programa Operativo Empleo Juvenil.pdf
	Rural Development Program PDR 2014-2020 Castilla-La Mancha (EAFRD)	EAFRD	EU level	https://pdr.castillamancha.es/
N03 Guarantee quality internet access in the territory and improve the training of the population in the use of the internet and telematic services	SUBSIDIES: "RED @ MAYORES 2019"	-	Municipality level	https://www.dipucueca.es/ayudas-y-subsenciones
	Local Development Strategy 2014-2020 ADESIMAN	EAFRD	Municipality level	http://www.adesiman.org/programa_de_desarrollo/Programa%20Desarrollo.html
	COLLABORATION AGREEMENT FOR THE PROVISION OF THE ELECTRONIC ADMINISTRATION SERVICE	-	Municipality level	https://www.dipucueca.es/asistencia-tecnica-a-municipios

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/s strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
	New Generation Broadband Extension Program (PEBA-NGA)	ERDF	National level	http://www.mincotur.gov.es/PortalAyudas/banda-ancha/Paginas/Index.aspx
	National Plan for Smart Territories	EAFRD/NGEU	National level	https://avancedigital.mineco.gob.es/es-es/Novedades/Documentos/Plan_Nacional_Territorios_Inteligentes.pdf
	National Strategy for Science and Technology	EFRD/NGEU/Horizon Europe	National level	http://www.ciencia.gob.es/portal/site/MI_CINN/menuitem.26172fcf4eb029fa6ec7da6901432ea0/?vgnnextoid=1387571a3db06610VgnVCM1000001d04140aRCRD
	Strategy for the Digitization of the agri-food and forestry sector in rural areas	EAFRD	National level	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/ministerio/planes-estrategias/estrategia-digitalizacion-sector-agroalimentario/
	Connected Schools	ERDF/NGEU	National level	https://www.red.es/redes/es/que-hacemos/e-educaci%C3%B3n/escuelas-conectadas
	Strategy Spain Nation Entrepreneur	NGEU	National level	http://www.mineco.gob.es/portal/site/mineco/menuitem.ac30f9268750bd56a0b0240e026041a0/?vgnextoid=661927b8442c7610VgnVCM1000001d04140aRCRD&vgnextchannel=67f3a570b4ee3610VgnVCM100001d04140aRCRD
	Horizon Europe	-	EU level	https://ec.europa.eu/info/horizon-europe_en
	EFRD Castilla-La Mancha Operational Program 2014-2020	EFRD	EU level	https://fondosestructurales.castillalamancha.es/programacion-2014-2020/programa-operativo-feder-castilla-la-mancha-2014-2020
N04 Facilitate business	DIMPULSA business project competition	-	Municipality level	https://www.lanzaderadipucuenca.com/es

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
development and entrepreneurship	Local Development Strategy 2014-2020 ADESIMAN	EAFRD	Municipality level	http://www.adesiman.org/programa_de_desarrollo/Programa%20Desarrollo.html
	General Guidelines of the New Spanish Industrial Policy 2030	-	National level	https://industria.gob.es/es-es/Documents/Directrices%20Generales%20de%20la%20Pol%C3%ADtica%20industrial%20espa%C3%B1ola%2025.02.19%20FINAL.pdf
	ICO Lines	-	National level	https://www.ico.es/web/ico/lineas-ico
	Rural Development Program PDR 2014-2020 Castilla-La Mancha (EAFRD)	EAFRD	EU level	https://pdr.castillalamancha.es/
	RIS3 Castilla- La Mancha	-	EU level	https://ris3.castillalamancha.es/que-es-la-ris3
	EFRD Castilla-La Mancha Operational Program 2014-2020	EFRD	EU level	https://fondosestructurales.castillalamancha.es/programacion-2014-2020/programa-operativo-feder-castilla-la-mancha-2014-2020
N05 Improve the transport service both within the territory and from the territory to urban areas, with particular attention to transport to health services.	Conservation of the public road domain	-	Municipality level	https://www.dipucuenca.es/carreteras
	Local Development Strategy 2014-2020 ADESIMAN	EAFRD	Municipality level	http://www.adesiman.org/programa_de_desarrollo/Programa%20Desarrollo.html
	III Highway Plan 2015-2026	EFRD	Regional/county level	https://www.castillamancha.es/gobierno/fomento/estructura/dgfcartera/actuaciones/iii-plan-de-carreteras-2015-2026
N06 Improve the quality of health care service	Castilla-La Mancha Health Plan	-	Regional/county level	https://www.castillamancha.es/sites/default/files/documentos/pdf/20191230/borrador_plan_de_salud_dic_2019.pdf
	Local Development Strategy 2014-2020 ADESIMAN	EAFRD	Municipality level	http://www.adesiman.org/programa_de_desarrollo/Programa%20Desarrollo.html

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
	SNS common database and SNS interoperability map	-	National level	https://www.mscbs.gob.es/organizacion/sns/e_salud.htm
N07 Promote vocational and higher education and training, particularly for young people and women	Local Development Strategy 2014-2020 ADESIMAN	EAFRD	Municipality level	http://www.adesiman.org/programa_de_desarrollo/Programa%20Desarrollo.html
	III Professional Training Plan of Castilla-La Mancha	ESF/NGEU	Regional/county level	https://www.castillamancha.es/sites/default/files/documentos/pdf/20180717/iii_plan_de_formacion_profesional_clm_2018_2020.pdf
	MAPA Training Plan	EAFRD	National level	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/desarrollo-rural/formacion/cursos/
	Rural Development Program PDR 2014-2020 Castilla-La Mancha (EAFRD)	EAFRD	EU level	
	Youth Guarantee Plan	ESF	EU level	http://www.educa.jcml.es/es/consejeria-educacion-cultura-deportes/planes-programas-consejeria/plan-garantia-juvenil
N08 Guarantee sufficient and quality services (nurseries, electricity, drinking water, waste treatment services, etc.).	Local Development Strategy 2014-2020 ADESIMAN	EAFRD	Municipality level	http://www.adesiman.org/programa_de_desarrollo/Programa%20Desarrollo.html
	Call for aid for the Maintenance of Basic Commercial Structure in Small Municipalities	-	Municipality level	https://www.dipucuenca.es/estructura-comercial
	URBAN WASTE TREATMENT SERVICE THROUGH PROVINCIAL COUNCIL	-	Municipality level	https://www.dipucuenca.es/convenios-para-los-servicios-de-bomberos-y-tratamiento-de-rsu

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/s strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
	Integrated Waste Management Plan of Castilla-La Mancha	-	Regional/county level	https://www.castillalamancha.es/gobierno/desarrollosostenible/estructura/vicmedamb/actuaciones/plan-integrado-de-gesti%C3%B3n-de-residuos-de-castilla-la-mancha
	Retail Trade Plan	-	National level	https://www.comercio.gob.es/es-ES/comercio-interior/Ayudas-al-Comercio-Interior/Descripcion-general-de-los-Planes/Paginas/Actuaciones-de-apoyo-a-la-Competitividad-del-Comercio-Minorista-de-Espana-2019.aspx
	Rural Development Program PDR 2014-2020 Castilla-La Mancha (EAFRD)	EAFRD	EU level	https://pdr.castillalamancha.es/
N09 Promote economic diversification in a jointly organized way from the institutions and the private sector, through the tourist development of the area, taking advantage of the heritage and natural resources existing in the territory, correctly defining a tourist package as well as promoting a complementary offer.	Plan of Archaeological Parks of Castilla-La Mancha	NGEU	Regional/county level	https://www.castillalamancha.es/gobierno/educacionculturaydeportes/estructura/viccultura/actuaciones/plan-de-parques-arqueol%C3%B3gicos-de-castilla-la-mancha
	Local Development Strategy 2014-2020 ADESIMAN	EAFRD	Municipality level	http://www.adesiman.org/programa_de_desarrollo/Programa%20Desarrollo.html
	Agreement for the opening of Tourist Offices	-	Municipality level	
	Strategic Tourism Plan	-	Regional/county level	http://www.turismocastillalalamancha.es/PLAN-ESTRATEGICO-TURISMO-CASTILLA-LA-MANCHA-2020-2023.pdf

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/s strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
	Land and Landscape Planning Law of Castilla-La Mancha	-	Regional/county level	https://www.castillamancha.es/gobierno/fomento/estructura/dgfplatersos/actuaciones/consultap%C3%ABblica-previa-la-elaboraci%C3%B3n-del-anteproyecto-de-la-ley-de-ordenaci%C3%B3n-del-territorio-y-del
	Sustainable Tourism Strategy of Spain 2030	NGEU	National level	https://turismo.gob.es/es-es/estrategia-turismo-sostenible/Paginas/Index.aspx
	Rural Development Program PDR 2014-2020 Castilla-La Mancha (EAFRD)	EAFRD	EU level	https://pdr.castillalamancha.es/
N10 Favor the profitability of the agricultural sector and promote economic diversification by promoting the development of agribusiness from existing raw materials, especially cereals with transformation, commercialization, organic products, local markets, etc-	C.I.E.S., (Mushroom Research, Experimentation and Services Center)	-	Municipality level	https://www.dipucuenca.es/cies
	Local Development Strategy 2014-2020 ADESIMAN	EAFRD	Municipality level	http://www.adesiman.org/programa_de_desarrollo/Programa%20Desarrollo.html
	Rural Development Program PDR 2014-2020 Castilla-La Mancha (EAFRD)	EAFRD	EU level	https://pdr.castillalamancha.es/
	STRATEGY FOR ENHANCING THE ECOLOGICAL PRODUCTION SECTOR IN CASTILLA LA MANCHA	-	Regional/county level	https://www.castillamancha.es/gobierno/agriaguaydesrur/actuaciones/estrategia-de-potenciaci%C3%B3n-del-sector-de-la-producci%C3%B3n-ecol%C3%B3gica-castilla-la-mancha-2019-2023

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/s strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
	Agrifood Industries Plan PDR 2024-2020- Support program for the wine sector	-	Regional/county level	https://www.castillalamancha.es/gobierno/agriaguaydesrur/actuaciones/plan-de-industrias-agroalimentarias
	Strategy for ecological production 2018-2020	-	National level	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/alimentacion/temas/produccion-ecologica/estrategiaproduccionecologica2018-2020_tcm30-440543.pdf

3.4 Pilot 4 Vidzeme, Latvia

3.4.1 Description of respective governance structures related to rural development

Vidzeme Planning Region (VPR) lies in the North East of Latvia and borders on Latgale planning region in the South East, Zemgale Planning Region in the South and Riga Planning Region in the West. Vidzeme Planning Region is the biggest of the planning regions according to its territory. It covers 15 257 km² or 24% of the territory of Latvia. The number of population in the region is around 240 thousand.

Agriculture keeps a strategic position in the Latvian economy and employment structure, especially in rural areas. Although farm sizes and intensification of agricultural production are increasing, Latvian agriculture is dominated by small scale, low-input and low-output production pattern which also shapes the agricultural knowledge demand. Many of these farms have limited financial means to pay for professional agricultural advice and their needs have not been well addressed in the existing agricultural policy. Taking into account their large share in Latvian agriculture, they are strategically important for maintaining the vitality of rural areas and communities, rural and agricultural diversity. The Rural Development Programme for 2014-2020 initially proposed measures to better target (specifically) small farms, but they have been reduced⁴⁵. In turn, financially more sound big commercial farms need more technological knowledge appropriated for their scale of farming, but it happens to be unavailable in Latvia due to the lack of local experts or they are under-qualified or -equipped to provide such knowledge. It should also be added that agricultural production is diversifying: Next to traditional crops production and dairy farming, there have been new or

⁴⁵ Hauka, A. (2013) Vai mazās un vidējās saimniecības tiks atbalstītas? <http://lzf.lv/node/119> Accessed 22.07.2013.

alternative agricultural branches developing like organic farming and energy crops. Agriculture is also coupled with other rural economy activities - tourism, processing, catering etc. These new types and forms of farming also demand specific knowledge⁴⁶.

Meanwhile, policy and planning documents for the next planning period (2021-2027) shows a turning point in Rural Development by highlighting the necessity of diversification of rural economy and integrated territorial development. Even if agriculture and forestry remain the most important industries in rural areas, research for new added values is emerging.

Governance structures related to rural development

National level: The Ministry of Agriculture (MoA) is responsible for rural and agricultural policy, agricultural education at university level, agricultural research and extension, as well as for support to producer organizations. For regional development and environmental issues are responsibility of The Ministry of Environmental Protection and Regional Development of Latvia. The Ministry of Education is responsible for the policy of science and education (however, the single agricultural university is supervised by the Ministry of Agriculture). Responsibilities for innovation and R&D policies and science links with industry are delegated to the Ministry of Economics. For media, culture and civic society policies is responsible the Ministry of Culture.

National Rural Network is another major national platform for information and knowledge exchange among rural and agricultural actors.

Regional level: Five regional development agencies in Latvia, responsible for territorial planning and coordination of regional development, also attracts and allocates funding, initiates and takes part in projects facilitating agricultural innovation and knowledge. Vidzemes planning region is the regional development agency in Vidzeme region. **VPR ensures following services at regional level:** (1) **Ensure the planning** - organization and implementation of territorial development planning at the regional level, involving all stakeholders; issuing adjudgements on local planning documents; (2) **Representing interests** - representation of the regional development interests on the national and international levels; (3) **Supporting development and partnership** - organizing cooperation events, providing consultations, organizing project competitions, involvement of other regions and foreign partners, implementation of projects for local governments, NGOs, entrepreneurs and other groups; (4) **Providing information** – compiling statistical information, management of different kinds of research, compiling and publishing information on various current issues; (5) **Coordinating the work of local governments** - promoting cooperation of local authorities

⁴⁶ Šūmane S., Grīviņš M., Tisenkopfs T. (2014): AKIS and advisory services in Latvia. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the PROAKIS Project https://430a.uni-hohenheim.de/fileadmin/einrichtungen/430a/PRO_AKIS/Country_Reports/Country_Report_Latvia_20_06_14.pdf

by organizing events and ensuring successful work of the Development Council; (6) **Implementing specific functions** - strategy for the period - public transport planning in the region⁴⁷.

Local level:

VPR comprises the former district municipalities of Aluksne, Cesis, Gulbene, Madona, Valka and Valmiera. There are 25 local municipalities (novads) and one city - Valmiera. There is an Administrative territorial reform (ATR) in view for 2021 – it projects to reduce the number of local municipalities in VPR from 25 to 7.

The local governments provide facilities and co-fund the work of the local rural development advisers of The Latvian Rural Advisory and Training Centre (LRATC) which is the largest agricultural and rural advisory organisation operating an advisors' network in Latvia. LRATC is both publicly and privately funded.

There are 8 Local Action groups (LAG) in VPR territory: Madonas Novada fonds, Vidzemes lauku partnerība "Brasla", Cēsu rajona lauku partnerība, Abulas Lauku partnerība, biedrība "Sateka", Alūksnes lauku partnerība, No Salacas līdz Rūjai, Lauku partnerība "Ziemeļgauja".

⁴⁷ http://www.vidzeme.lv/en/about_vidzeme

Figure 6. Summary of The Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System in Latvia⁴⁸

Table 9. Summary of Governance structure (2020)

Status of organisation	Type of organisation	Organisation
Public sector	National Government	Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of Environmental Protection and Regional Development of Latvia, Ministry of Education, Ministry of Economics, Ministry of Culture,
	Local Authorities	City of Valmiera, Municipality of Madona, Municipality of Gulbene, Municipality of Cesis, Municipality of Aluksne, Municipality of Smiltene, Municipality of Valka, Municipality of Priekuli, Municipality of Burtnieki, Municipality of Koceni, Municipality of Amata, Municipality of Rujiena, Municipality of Vecpiebalga, Municipality of Pargauja, Municipality of Ape, Municipality of Strenci, Municipality of Rauna, Municipality of Ligatne, Municipality of Mazsalaca, Municipality of Ergli, Municipality of Beverina, Municipality of Cesvaine, Municipality of Varaklani, Municipality of

⁴⁸ Figure 1- Šūmane S., Grīviņš M., Tisenkopfs T. (2014): AKIS and advisory services in Latvia. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the www.proakis.eu/publicationsandevents/pubs

Status of organisation	Type of organisation	Organisation
	Government Agencies	Lubana, Municipality of Jaunpiebalga, Municipality of Naukseni (All until Administrative territorial reform in 2021)
		Cross-Sectoral Coordination Centre
		Investment and Development Agency of Latvia
		Nature Conservation Agency
		Latvian Rural Advisory and Training Centre
		State Employment Agency of Latvia
		Rural Support Service
		Development finance institution "ALTUM"
		National Rural Network.
		National Fisheries Network
	Latvian State Forests	
Regional agencies	Vidzeme planning region	
Research and Education	Universities & Higher Education Institutes	Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences
		Latvian University of Agriculture
		Latvian University
	Research Institutes & Foundations	Institute of Agricultural Resources and Economics
		Baltic Studies Center
	Institute for Environmental Solutions	
Private sector	Cooperatives	<i>Agroeconomic Cooperative of Vidzeme</i>
		<i>Agricultural service cooperative society VAKS</i>
		<i>Agricultural service cooperative society Straupe</i>
		<i>Forestry service cooperative society Vidzeme</i>
		<i>Forestry service cooperative society Vidzemes ekomežs</i> etc. ⁴⁹
	Private agricultural, entrepreneurial consultants	Numerous private actors
Rural development and farmers NGOs	Environmental NGOs	Latvian Fund for Nature
		World Wide Fund for Nature
		Green Freedom
		Foundation for Environmental Education
		Baltic Environmental Forum etc.
	Farmer based NGOs	Young Farmers Club
		Latvian Agricultural Organization Cooperation Council
		Latvian Association of Agricultural Cooperatives
		Farmers' Parliament
		Latvian Farmers' Federation
		Latvian Association of Organic Agriculture
	Rural Development NGOs	Latvian Rural Forum
		LAGs :Madonas Novada fonds, Vidzemes lauku partnerība "Brasla", Cēsu rajona lauku partnerība, Abulas Lauku partnerība, biedrība "Sateka", Alūksnes lauku partnerība, No Salacas līdz Rūjai, Lauku partnerība "Ziemeļgauja"
	Other	Latvian Association of Local and Regional Governments
		The Latvian Federation of Food Enterprises

⁴⁹ Registered cooperatives, 2020. <http://www.llka.lv/atbilstibas-lpks/2020/>

Rural development planning documents and priorities:

EU Common Agriculture Policy in Latvia is nationally through Rural Development Programme (RDP)⁵⁰ developed by Ministry of Agriculture which is currently together with different stakeholders working on Transition Regula and the Rural Development Programme 2021-2027. The Elements of the EU multiannual budget that falls under the competence of Ministry of Agriculture are: common agriculture policy, direct payments, market mechanisms, rural development and are mainly encompassed in the management of natural resources of the EU budget.

The focus of the RDP in Latvia 2014-2020 was on⁵¹:

- increasing competitiveness of Latvian farmers and rural entrepreneurs by improving infrastructure and providing advice, and training services. Support for farm modernisation and restructuring and diversification of production;
- supporting transition to organic farming;
- supporting 35 Local action groups covering 94% of rural population;
- support for risk management and introduction of preventive measures for natural disasters.

Rural development funding through the EAFRD is part of European Structural and Investment Funds (ESI Funds)⁵², including also Regional Development, Social, Cohesion, and Maritime and Fisheries Funds. These are managed EU Member States following **national strategic plans outlining the country's goals and investment priorities**.

Sustainable Development Strategy of Latvia until 2030 (Latvia 2030)⁵³ is hierarchically the highest national-level, long-term planning document. It enumerates the main tasks of the state and society to achieve balanced and sustainable development. Latvia 2030 outlines 7 development priorities (development of culture space, investment in human capital, change of paradigm in education, innovative and eco-efficient economy, nature as future capital, perspective of spatial development, innovative government and participation of the society), 7 strategic indicators (natural population growth, the GINI coefficient, GDP per capita, the ecological footprint, the Human Development Index, the Global Competitiveness Index,

⁵⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/info/food-farming-fisheries/key-policies/common-agricultural-policy/rural-development/country/latvia_lv

⁵¹ Rural Development Programme 2014-2020, https://www.zm.gov.lv/public/files/CMS_Static_Page_Doc/00/00/01/76/83/Programme_2014LV06RDNP001_8_1_lv.pdf

⁵² https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/european-structural-and-investment-funds_en

⁵³ Sustainable Development Strategy of Latvia until 2030 (LV 2030) <http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file16857.pdf>

dispersion of regional GDP per capita), 11 objectives, 11 development directions, 42 areas of action and 27 performance indicators.

National Development Plan 2021-2027 (NDP2027)⁵⁴ is Latvia's main medium-term development planning document. It programmes Latvia's seven year commitments to achieve the Latvian Sustainable Development Strategy 2030 (Latvia2030), the UN Sustainable Development Goals and to improve the quality of life in Latvia over the next seven years. In 2020 National Development Plan 2014-2020 (NDP2020) is still in power⁵⁵.

NDP2027 Direction's Balanced regional development objective is unleashed regional development potential and reduced economic disparities are through localised solutions

Planned measures:

- Provision of public infrastructure for business in accordance with territorial development plans;
- Coordinated system and a regional growth fund for targeted investments in the regions;
- Increasing cooperation and capacity of the planning regions and local governments to ensure the mobility of citizens, an investment-friendly environment and services;
- Innovative micro-mobility solutions and infrastructure for employment and services;
- Aligning public services with demographic changes;
- Government support function deployment outside of the capital city;
- Strengthening cooperation in the border area with neighboring local and national governments and rural territories.

The Ministry of Environmental Protection and Regional Development of Latvia manages EU ERAF and ESF funds for Regional Development following elaborated Regional Policy Guidelines 2021 – 2027 (RPG2027)⁵⁶. Main thematic directions of RPG2027 are:

- Regional economic development that is based on active involvement of planning regions and municipalities, including providing support to municipalities for development of business environment, raising productivity and attracting human resources in the regions, as well as building regional innovation and knowledge systems;
- Improvement of the efficiency of services, taking into account demographic trends, providing support for raising the energy efficiency of municipal service buildings,

⁵⁴ National Development Plan of Latvia 2021-2027, https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/The%20Latvian%20National%20Development%20Plan%202021-2027%20-%20Summary_pdf.pdf

⁵⁵ National Development Plan of Latvia 2014-2020, https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/inline-files/NDP2020%20English%20Final_.pdf

⁵⁶ Regional Policy Guidelines 2021-2027, http://www.varam.gov.lv/eng/darbibas_veidi/regional_development/

access to pre-school education, implementation of smart solutions, development of public outdoor space and improving mobility for accessibility of services;

- Capacity building of planning regions, municipal administrations and other stakeholders involved in territorial development planning, including civil society groups, providing methodological support for development of mutually agreed territorial development planning documents and implementation of initiatives.

At regional and local level the main policy documents are Vidzeme Planning Region Development Program 2015 – 2020⁵⁷ and Sustainable Development Strategy 2030 of the Vidzeme Planning Region⁵⁸, local municipalities elaborates their own planning documents⁵⁹ following the strategic goals described in the policy documents mentioned above.

3.4.2 Mission statement and the needs of pilot regions

The Latvian pilot is managed by the Vidzeme Planning Region in cooperation with Latvian Rural Forum, Institute of Agricultural Resources and Economics and Baltic Open Solutions Centre. Group of stakeholders will be gathered for the Advisory board to support piloting team during the project lifetime.

Priority issues: Attractiveness of the region, rural planning, skilled workforce and talent attraction, rural development, policymaking.

Mission statement: *Overall ambition is to embed pilot results into the region's long-term and mid-term planning documents along with the development of a comprehensive guide for diversification of rural economy. With the help of local stakeholders, a dynamic toolbox will be prepared that is considering the newest and latest socioeconomic trends, agricultural and related industry foresight & analysis insights as well as findings.*

Expected outputs:

- Input for Vidzeme Planning Region Development programme for 2021-2027;
- New measures and services with a special focus on newcomers;
- Tool for local authorities for collaboration-oriented policy development;
- Actions for developing rural attractiveness are defined, based on the scenarios modelled, collection, processing and mapping of qualitative and quantitative data on rural attractiveness.

Expected impact (qualitative):

⁵⁷ http://www.vidzeme.lv/lv/regiona_attistibas_planosanas_dokumenti

⁵⁸

http://jauna.vidzeme.lv/upload/VIDZEMES_PLANOSANAS_REGIONA_ILGTSPEJIGAS_ATTISTIBAS_STRATEGIJA.pdf

⁵⁹ <https://raim.gov.lv/lv/node/37>

Rural places and professions are becoming more attractive for established rural populations and recent or potential newcomers, and they've been integrated into the regional development process. Interest of regional inhabitants in traditional fields such as agriculture, forestry and fishery has raised because of the cross-industry collaboration. Rural attractiveness serves as a factor for existing and / or potential entrepreneurs to develop their businesses in rural areas.

Pilot's needs

Vidzeme Pilot's needs were gathered in D4.2 Vidzeme Pilot's SWOT/Needs analysis based on questionnaire and discussions with Stakeholder Panel. Together 31 needs were identified structured in following thematic groups:

- Availability of public and other services
- Recreation / social activities
- Living condition, quality of life and standard of living
- Demographic & human capital
- Business, economy & innovation
- Social and cultural aspects of rural areas
- Environment & Biodiversity

3.4.3 Matching needs with policy measures in Needs-Policy Canvas

From the PoliRural D4.2 Vidzeme Pilot's SWOT/Needs analysis and discussions with Panel, following 6 main pilot's needs were identified:

- 1 Increasing the level of civic participation and public involvement in the promotion of territorial development and implementation of initiatives, incl. Greater involvement of LAGs and other NGOs (compiled N13, N14, N27)
- 2 Development of high value-added products and services within the framework of implementation of various existing and new EU funds and EC priorities, in smart specialization areas important for Vidzeme region (N15)
- 3 Lifelong learning and the development of skills and knowledge appropriate to the needs, incl. digital competences, social and professional skills (N04)
- 4 Diversification of business, especially in the framework of the implementation of existing and new CAP, RDP and EC priorities in rural areas, incl. circular economy (compiled N30, N3, N29, N28, N16, N15)
- 5 Housing availability, quality and energy efficiency (N08)
- 6 Accessibility of public transport and provision of road infrastructure (N01)

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
Increasing the level of civic participation and public involvement in the promotion of territorial development and implementation of initiatives, incl. Greater involvement of LAGs and other NGOs	The Youth Policy Implementation Plan	ESF, EAFRD, also RRF, ERASMUS+, ESC	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/7995327137443335159.docx
	ERASMUS+	-	EU level	https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/about_en
	Rural Development Programme (RDP)	EAFRD	National level	https://www.zm.gov.lv/public/files/CMS_Static_Page_Doc/00/00/01/76/83/Programme_2014LV06RDNP001_8_1_lv.pdf
	Declaration of the Intended Activities of the Cabinet of Ministers headed by Arturs Krišjānis Kariņš	ESF, ERDF, CF, EMFF, EAFRD	National level	ENG: https://www.mk.gov.lv/sites/default/files/editor/declaration_of_the_intended_activities_of_the_cabinet_of_ministers.pdf LV: https://www.mk.gov.lv/sites/default/files/editor/final_mkrik_pielikums_vrp_preciz_250419.xlsx
	Latvia's Fourth National Open Government Action Plan for 2020-2021	-	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/400599392245966234.docx
	Public administration reform plan	-	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/3302259687398140477.pdf
	National Identity, Civil Society and Integration Policy Guidelines	ERDF, ESF	National level	https://www.km.gov.lv/uploads/ckeditor/files/Sabiedribas_integracija/KM_130515_Prec_Nac_ident_pils_on_sab_un_itegr_polit_pamatnost_2012-2018.pdf
	Regional Policy Guidelines	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/4077967561200800882.docx
	CLLD Local Development Strategies	EAFRD, EMFF	Local /grassroot level	http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/svva_strategija_alp_grozijumi_30_01_2019.pdf http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/brasla_svva_strategija_2019.docx http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/crlp_strategija_17122019.pdf http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/sateka_svva_strategijas_grozijumi_01-2020.doc http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/ziemelgauja_svva_strategija_02042019_ar_virssaist.docx http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/alp_strategija_2015-2020_ar_2019_gada_grozijumiem.pdf http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/mnf_svastrategija_102019.docx http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/svva_nosalacas_lidz_rujai_032019.docx
	Territorial Development Strategy	Cohesion Fund, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	Local /grassroot level	e.g. https://aluksne.lv/ilgtspejiga_strategija/strategija%202030.gala.pdf More links in annex 1.
Vidzeme Planning Region Development documents	ESF, ERDF, CF, EMFF, EAFRD	Regional level	http://www.vidzeme.lv/upload/Attstbas_programma_2015-2020.pdf	

				<p>http://jauna.vidzeme.lv/upload/VIDZEMES_PLANOSANAS_REGIONAL_ILGTSPEJIGAS_ATTISTIBAS_STRATEGIJA.pdf</p> <p>http://jauna.vidzeme.lv/upload/VP_R_Ricibu_plans_2017_2020_AKTUALIZTS09122016.pdf</p>
	European Economic Area Financial Mechanism (EEA FM) and the Norwegian Financial Mechanism (NFM)	EEA FI	International level	https://www.eeagrants.lv/files/Mou_EEA_2014-2021_ENG.pdf
	European Union Structural Funds and Cohesion Fund Operational Program "Growth and Employment"	CF, ERDF, ESF, EMFF	National level	LV: http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/173621642877332077.docx ENG: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/atlas/programmes/2014-2020/latvia/2014lv16maop001
	Sustainable Development Strategy of Latvia until 2030 (LV 2030)	-	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/16857.pdf
	National Development plan of Latvia	ESF, ERDF, CF, EMFF, EAFRD	National level	LV: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/inline-files/20121220_NAP2020%20apstiprinats%20Saeima_4.pdf ENG: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/inline-files/NDP2020%20English%20Final_1.pdf
	National Development Plan of Latvia	ESF, ERDF, CF, EMFF, EAFRD	National level	LV: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/inline-files/NAP2027galaredakcija.pdf ENG: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/The%20Latvian%20National%20Development%20Plan%202021-2027%20-%20Summary.pdf
Development of high value-added products and services within the framework of implementation of various existing and new EU funds and EC priorities, in smart specialization areas important for Vidzeme region	EU Strategy for Baltic Sea Region	ESF, ERDF, CF, EMFF, EAFRD	EU level	https://www.balticsea-region-strategy.eu/
	EU 2020 Strategy	ESF, ERDF, CF, EMFF, EAFRD	EU level	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/4411192/4411431/Europe_2020_Targets.pdf
	Vidzeme Planning Region Development documents	ESF, ERDF, CF, EMFF, EAFRD	Regional level	<p>http://www.vidzeme.lv/upload/Attstbas_programma_2015-2020.pdf</p> <p>http://jauna.vidzeme.lv/upload/VIDZEMES_PLANOSANAS_REGIONAL_ILGTSPEJIGAS_ATTISTIBAS_STRATEGIJA.pdf</p> <p>http://jauna.vidzeme.lv/upload/VP_R_Ricibu_plans_2017_2020_AKTUALIZTS09122016.pdf</p>
	Rural Development Programme (RDP)	EAFRD	National level	https://www.zm.gov.lv/public/files/CMS_Static_Page_Doc/00/00/01/76/83/Programme_2014LV06RDNP001_8_1_lv.pdf
	Declaration of the Intended Activities of the Cabinet of Ministers headed by Arturs Krišjānis Kariņš	ESF, ERDF, CF, EMFF, EAFRD	National level	ENG: https://www.mk.gov.lv/sites/default/files/editor/declaration_of_the_intended_activities_of_the_cabinet_of_ministers.pdf LV:

				https://www.mk.gov.lv/sites/default/files/editor/final_mkrik_pielikums_vrp_preciz_250419.xlsx
Plan of Alternative Measures for Energy Efficiency Policy Target for Energy End-Use Savings	ERDF, EAFRD, EMFF, CF	National level		http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/145091081123636871.DOCX
The National Guidelines for Science, Technology Development and Innovation	ERDF, ESF	National level		http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/8915.doc
Smart Specialization Strategy	ESF, ERDF, CF, EAFRD	National level		https://www.izm.gov.lv/images/zinatne/Ekosist_kopsavilkums_RIS3.pdf
Baltic Sea Region Program	ERDF	International level		http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/9195.doc
Estonian-Latvian cross-border co-operation program	ERDF	International level		http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/25949.doc
National Industrial Policy Guidelines	ERDF, ESF	National level		http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/34401.doc
Regional policy guidelines	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	National level		http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/4077967561200800882.docx
European Union Structural Funds and Cohesion Fund Operational Program "Growth and Employment"	CF, ERDF, ESF, EMFF	National level		LV: http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/173621642877332077.docx ENG: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/atlas/programmes/2014-2020/latvia/2014lv16maop001
Territorial Development Strategy	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	Local /grassroot level		e.g. https://aluksne.lv/ilgtspejiga_strategija/strategija%202030.gala.pdf More links in Annex 1.
European Economic Area Financial Mechanism (EEA FM) and the Norwegian Financial Mechanism (NFM)	-	International level		https://www.eeagrants.lv/files/Mou_EEA_2014-2021_ENG.pdf
Latvian Bioeconomy Strategy	-	National level		LV: https://www.llu.lv/sites/default/files/2018-07/Bioeconomy_Strategy_Latvia_LV.pdf ENG: https://www.zm.gov.lv/public/files/CMS_Static_Page_Doc/00/00/01/46/58/E2758-LatvianBioeconomyStrategy2030.pdf
Sustainable Development Strategy of Latvia until 2030 (LV 2030)	-	National level		http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/16857.pdf
National Development plan of Latvia	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	National level		LV: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/inline-files/20121220_NAP2020%20apstiprinats%20Saeima_4.pdf ENG: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/inline-files/NDP2020%20English%20Final_1.pdf
National Development Plan of Latvia	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	National level		LV: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/inline-files/NAP2027galaredakcija.pdf

				ENG: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/The%20Latvian%20National%20Development%20Plan%202021-2027%20-%20Summary_pdf.pdf
Lifelong learning and the development of skills and knowledge appropriate to the needs, incl. digital competences, social and professional skills	Digital Education Action Plan	-	EU level	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52018DC0022&from=EN
	New Skills Agenda for Europe	ESF, ERASMUS, InvestEU, ESC, AGAF	EU level	https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1223
	ERASMUS+	ERASMUS	EU level	https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/about_en
	Vidzeme Planning Region Development documents	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	Regional level	http://www.vidzeme.lv/upload/Attstbas_programma_2015-2020.pdf http://jauna.vidzeme.lv/upload/VIDZEMES_PLANOSANAS_REGIONALIGTSPEJIGAS_ATTISTIBAS_STRATEGIJA.pdf http://jauna.vidzeme.lv/upload/VP_R_Ricibu_plans_2017_2020_AKTUALIZS09122016.pdf
	European Solidarity Corps	ESC	EU level	https://europa.eu/youth/solidarity_en
	The Youth Guarantee, incl. Youth Employment Initiative	ESF	EU level	https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1079&langId=en
	Cultural Policy Guidelines "Creative Latvia"	ERDF, ESF, EAFRD	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/41041.doc
	Improvement Plan for Service Environment	ERDF	National level	https://likumi.lv/ta/id/312410-par-pakalpojumu-vides-pilnveides-planu-20202023-gadam
	Rural Development Programme (RDP)	EAFRD	National level	https://www.zm.gov.lv/public/files/CMS_Static_Page_Doc/00/00/01/76/83/Programme_2014LV06RDNP001_8_1_lv.pdf
	Inclusive Employment Guidelines	EDF, ERDF	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/24304.docx
	Implementation Plan of the Adult Education Management Model	ESF	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/3359418791609949415.docx
	Guidelines for the Development of Education	ERDF	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/39192.pdf
	Career Education Implementation Plan in State and Municipal General and Vocational Education Institutions	ESF	National level	https://likumi.lv/ta/id/278999-par-karjeras-izglitiba-istenosanas-planu-valsts-un-pasvaldibu-visparejas-un-profesionalas-izglitiba-iestades-2015-2020
	Guidelines for Information Society Development	ERDF, ESF	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/5586.doc
	Conceptual Report "Active Aging Strategy for a Longer and Better Working Life in Latvia"	-	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/3254572317819534915.docx
	The Youth Policy Implementation Plan	ESF	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/7995327137443335159.docx
	European Union Structural Funds and Cohesion Fund Operational Program "Growth and Employment"	CF, ERDF, ESF, EMFF	National level	LV: http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/173621642877332077.docx ENG: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/atlas/programmes/2014-2020/latvia/2014lv16maop001
Territorial Development Strategy	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	Local /grassroot level	E.g.	

				https://aluksne.lv/ilgtspejiga_strategija/strategija%202030.gala.pdf More links in Annex 1.
	CLLD Local Development Strategies	EAFRD	Local /grassroot level	http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/svva_strategija_alp_grozijumi_30_01_2019.pdf http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/brasla_svva_strategija_2019.docx http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/crlp_strategija_17122019.pdf http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/sateka_svva_strategijas_grozijumi_01-2020.doc http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/ziemelgauja_svva_strategija_02042019_ar_virssaist.docx http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/alp_strategija_2015-2020_ar_2019_gada_grozijumiem.pdf http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/mnf_svastrategija_102019.docx http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/svva_nosalacas_lidz_rujai_032019.docx
	National Industrial Policy Guidelines	ERDF, ESF	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/34401.doc
	Declaration of the Intended Activities of the Cabinet of Ministers headed by Arturs Krišjānis Kariņš	ESF, ERDF, CF, EMFF, EAFRD	National level	ENG: https://www.mk.gov.lv/sites/default/files/editor/declaration_of_the_intended_activities_of_the_cabinet_of_ministers.pdf LV: https://www.mk.gov.lv/sites/default/files/editor/final_mkrik_pielikums_vrp_preciz_250419.xlsx
	Sustainable Development Strategy of Latvia until 2030 (LV 2030)	-	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/16857.pdf
	National Development plan of Latvia	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	National level	LV: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/inline-files/20121220_NAP2020%20apstiprinats%20Saeima_4.pdf ENG: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/inline-files/NDP2020%20English%20Final_1.pdf
	National Development Plan of Latvia	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	National level	LV: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/inline-files/NAP2027galaredakcija.pdf ENG: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/The%20Latvian%20National%20Development%20Plan%202021-2027%20-%20Summary_pdf.pdf
Diversification of business, especially in the framework of the implementation of existing and new CAP, RDP and EC priorities in rural areas, incl. circular economy	Regional policy guidelines	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/4077967561200800882.docx
	Territorial Development Strategy	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	Local /grassroot level	e.g. https://aluksne.lv/ilgtspejiga_strategija/strategija%202030.gala.pdf More links in Annex 1.
	Vidzeme Planning Region Development documents	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	Regional level	http://www.vidzeme.lv/upload/Attstbas_programma_2015-2020.pdf http://jauna.vidzeme.lv/upload/VIDZEMES_PLANOSANAS_REGIONA_

				<p>ILGTSPEJIGAS_ATTISTIBAS_STRATEGIJA.pdf</p> <p>http://jauna.vidzeme.lv/upload/VP_R_Ricibu_plans_2017_2020_AKTUALIZTS09122016.pdf</p>
CLLD Local Development Strategies	EAFRD	Local /grassroot level		<p>http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/svva_strategija_alp_grozijumi_30_01_2019.pdf</p> <p>http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/brasla_svva_strategija_2019.docx</p> <p>http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/crlp_strategija_17122019.pdf</p> <p>http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/sateka_svva_strategijas_grozijumi_01-2020.doc</p> <p>http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/ziemelgauja_svva_strategija_02042019_ar_virssaist.docx</p> <p>http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/alp_strategija_2015-2020_ar_2019_gada_grozijumiem.pdf</p> <p>http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/mnf_svastrategija_102019.docx</p> <p>http://www.lad.gov.lv/files/svva_nosalacas_lidz_rujai_032019.docx</p>
National Industrial Policy Guidelines	ERDF, ESF	National level		http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/34401.doc
Latvian-Russian cross-border cooperation program	ERDF	International level		http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/3307042367912288499.docx
Rural Development Programme (RDP)	EAFRD	National level		https://www.zm.gov.lv/public/files/CMS_Static_Page_Doc/00/00/01/76/83/Programme_2014LV06RDNP001_8_1_lv.pdf
Declaration of the Intended Activities of the Cabinet of Ministers headed by Arturs Krišjānis Kariņš	ESF, ERDF, CF, EMFF, EAFRD	National level		<p>ENG: https://www.mk.gov.lv/sites/default/files/editor/declaration_of_the_intended_activities_of_the_cabinet_of_ministers.pdf</p> <p>LV: https://www.mk.gov.lv/sites/default/files/editor/final_mkrik_pielikums_vrp_preciz_250419.xlsx</p>
Business environment improvement action plan	-	National level		http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/1569848123589066232.docx
Conceptual Report on the Business Start-up and Small Business Ecosystem and Future Support Incentives	-	National level		http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/7074568074118110810.docx
Estonian-Latvian cross-border co-operation program	ERDF	International level		http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/25949.doc
European Union Structural Funds and Cohesion Fund Operational Program "Growth and Employment"	CF, ERDF, ESF, EMFF	National level		<p>LV: http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/173621642877332077.docx</p> <p>ENG: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/atlas/programmes/2014-2020/latvia/2014lv16maop001</p>

	Sustainable Development Strategy of Latvia until 2030 (LV 2030)	-	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/16857.pdf
	National Development plan of Latvia	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	National level	LV: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/inline-files/20121220_NAP2020%20apsti prinats%20saeima_4.pdf ENG: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/inline-files/NDP2020%20English%20Final__1.pdf
	National Development Plan of Latvia	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	National level	LV: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/inline-files/NAP2027galaredakcija.pdf ENG: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/The%20Latvian%20National%20Development%20Plan%202021-2027%20-%20Summary.pdf.pdf
Housing availability, quality and energy efficiency	Declaration of the Intended Activities of the Cabinet of Ministers headed by Arturs Krišjānis Kariņš	ESF, ERDF, CF, EMFF, EAFRD	National level	ENG: https://www.mk.gov.lv/sites/default/files/editor/declaration_of_the_intended_activities_of_the_cabinet_of_ministers.pdf LV: https://www.mk.gov.lv/sites/default/files/editor/final_mkrik_pielikums_vrp_preciz_250419.xlsx
	The National Energy and Climate Plan	CF, ERDF, ESF	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/5117695515458451103.docx
	Plan of Alternative Measures for Energy Efficiency Policy Target for Energy End-Use Savings	CF, EAFRD, ERDF, EMFF	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/145091081123636871.DOCX
	Regional policy guidelines	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/4077967561200800882.docx
	Vidzeme Planning Region Development documents	ESF, ERDF, CF, EMFF, EAFRD	Regional level	http://www.vidzeme.lv/upload/Attstbas_programma_2015-2020.pdf http://jauna.vidzeme.lv/upload/VIDZEMES_PLANOSANAS_REGIONALIGTSPEJIGAS_ATTISTIBAS_STRATEGIJA.pdf http://jauna.vidzeme.lv/upload/VP_R_Ricibu_plans_2017_2020_AKTUALIZTS09122016.pdf
	European Union Structural Funds and Cohesion Fund Operational Program "Growth and Employment"	CF, ERDF, ESF, EMFF	National level	LV: http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/173621642877332077.docx ENG: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/atlas/programmes/2014-2020/latvia/2014lv16maop001
	Territorial Development Strategy	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	Local /grassroot level	e.g. https://aluksne.lv/ilgtspejiga_strategija/strategija%202030.gala.pdf More links in Annex 1.
	Sustainable Development Strategy of Latvia until 2030 (LV 2030)	-	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/16857.pdf
	National Development plan of Latvia	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	National level	LV: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/inline-files/20121220_NAP2020%20apsti

				<p>prinats%20Saeima_4.pdf</p> <p>ENG: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/inline-files/NDP2020%20English%20Final_1.pdf</p>
	National Development Plan of Latvia	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	National level	<p>LV: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/inline-files/NAP2027galaredakcija.pdf</p> <p>ENG: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/The%20Latvian%20National%20Development%20Plan%202021-2027%20-%20Summary_.pdf</p>
Accessibility of public transport and provision of road infrastructure	Rural Development Programme (RDP)	EAFRD	National level	https://www.zm.gov.lv/public/files/CMS_Static_Page_Doc/00/00/01/76/83/Programme_2014LV06RDNP001_8_1_lv.pdf
	Territorial Development Strategy	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	Local /grassroot level	https://aluksne.lv/ilgtspejiga_strategija/strategija%202030.gala.pdf More links in Annex 1.
	Vidzeme Planning Region Development documents	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	Regional level	<p>http://www.vidzeme.lv/upload/Attstbas_programma_2015-2020.pdf</p> <p>http://jauna.vidzeme.lv/upload/VIDZEMES_PLANOSANAS_REGIONA_ILGTSPEJIGAS_ATTISTIBAS_STRATEGIJA.pdf</p> <p>http://jauna.vidzeme.lv/upload/VP_R_Ricibu_plans_2017_2020_AKTUALIZTS09122016.pdf</p> <p>http://jauna.vidzeme.lv/upload/TENTacle/Vidzeme_regional_mobility_investment_plan_2030_Latvian_language.pdf</p>
	Declaration of the Intended Activities of the Cabinet of Ministers headed by Arturs Krišjānis Kariņš	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	National level	<p>ENG: https://www.mk.gov.lv/sites/default/files/editor/declaration_of_the_intended_activities_of_the_cabinet_of_ministers.pdf</p> <p>LV: https://www.mk.gov.lv/sites/default/files/editor/final_mkrik_pielikums_vrp_preciz_250419.xlsx</p>
	Indicative railway infrastructure development plan	-	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/2802284028774646364.docx
	Baltic Sea Region Program	ERDF	International level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/9195.doc
	Transport development guidelines	ESF, ERDF	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/8063722795811369165.doc
	European Union Structural Funds and Cohesion Fund Operational Program "Growth and Employment"	CF, ERDF, ESF, EMFF	National level	<p>LV: http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/173621642877332077.docx</p> <p>ENG: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/atlas/programmes/2014-2020/latvia/2014lv16maop001</p>
	Sustainable Development Strategy of Latvia until 2030 (LV 2030)	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	National level	http://polsis.mk.gov.lv/api/file/file/16857.pdf
	National Development plan of Latvia	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	National level	<p>LV: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/inline-files/20121220_NAP2020%20apstiprinats%20Saeima_4.pdf</p>

				ENG: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/inline-files/NDP2020%20English%20Final__1.pdf
	National Development Plan of Latvia	CF, ERDF, ESF, EAFRD, EMFF	National level	LV: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/inline-files/NAP2027galaredakcija.pdf ENG: https://www.pkc.gov.lv/sites/default/files/The%20Latvian%20National%20Development%20Plan%202021-2027%20-%20Summary_pdf.pdf

Communication with policy actors and regional panels during policy mapping process is presented in table 9.

Table 10. Communication with policy makers and stakeholders in Vidzeme

Date	Topic of the meeting	Type of the meeting (face-to-face, online, workshop)	Target group	Number of attendees
25.03.2020	Stakeholder meeting	Online workshop via Zoom platform	Stakeholder Panel	31
30.04.2020 – 6.05.2020.	Policy mapping	Online meeting on zoom platform and Phone conversations	Pilot partners	6
30.04 – 08.05.2020	Policy mapping	Phone calls-consultations	Policy makers	7

Table 11. Needs-Policy canvas, Vidzeme, Latvia

3.5 Pilot 5 Mazowieckie, Poland

3.5.1 Description of respective governance structures

Rural areas account for about 93% of Poland's surface area and comprise almost 40% of the country's population.⁶⁰ Rural areas are characterised by great diversity in terms of both the

⁶⁰ Kania J., Vinohradnik K., Tworzyk A. (2014): AKIS and advisory services in Poland. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the PRO AKIS project. Online resource: https://430a.uni-hohenheim.de/fileadmin/einrichtungen/430a/PRO_AKIS/Country_Reports/Country_Report_Poland_17_07_14.pdf

state of the natural environment and the level of social and economic development. One of the basic features of the rural settlement network is a high degree of fragmentation.

For fifteen years now, the agricultural sector and rural areas in Poland have been covered by mechanisms of the EU Common Agricultural Policy. Apart from access to the huge EU internal market, support systems provided for under the CAP play a key role in the process of transformation and development of the Polish food economy.

The most important institution having an impact on the development of villages and agriculture is the **Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development**, whose task is to create and implement long-term state policy in cooperation with governmental and non-governmental stakeholders. The Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development is an office of government administration. It provides services to the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development, who heads three departments of government administration: agriculture, rural development, agricultural markets.

The role of governmental organisations is to make decisions on various aspects of activity in rural areas in accordance with democratic and market economy principles contained in specific normative acts.

Until the end of August 2017, there were four agricultural executive agricultural agencies in Poland, two of which were accredited paying agencies of the European Union, i.e. the Agency for Restructuring and Modernisation of Agriculture (ARiMR) and the Agricultural Market Agency (ARR), the Agricultural Property Agency (ANR) and the Central Centre for Crop Plant Variety Research. Since 2017, under two laws, the Agricultural Market Agency and the Agricultural Property Agency have been liquidated, and KOWR - National Centre for Agricultural Support - has been established in place of them. At the same time, the Agency for the Restructuring and Modernisation of Agriculture (Agencja Restrukturyzacji i Modernizacji Rolnictwa) became the only European Union paying agency in the Republic of Poland.

Since 1994 the **Agency for the Restructuring and Modernisation of Agriculture (ARiMR)** has been supporting activities aimed at developing agriculture and rural areas. In the first years of its activity, it continued the tasks started by the Fund for Restructuring and Debt Management, providing support mainly from domestic funds, mainly in the form of interest rate subsidies for investment and working capital loans. After Poland's accession to the EU, both the scale of aid granted and the number of available support instruments increased. Another increase in the scope of activity took place on 1 September 2017, when ARMA took over the tasks related to the implementation of EU mechanisms of the common organisation of agricultural markets. The most important instrument of the common agricultural policy, implemented by ARMA, are payments under direct support schemes, which in recent years have been used annually by about 1.32 million farmers.

The **National Agricultural Support Centre (KOWR)** is an executive agency and a state legal entity operating since 1 September 2017 on the basis of the Act of 10 February 2017 on the

National Agricultural Support Centre (Journal of Laws of 2018, item 1154, as amended) and the statute of the National Agricultural Support Centre granted by the Ordinance of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development of 21 April 2017. The task of the NAC is to implement and apply instruments to support active agricultural policy and rural development for the benefit of Polish farmers and entities operating in the agri-food sector. KOWR operates in several areas. The tasks in the scope of: management of agricultural real estate of the Treasury Agricultural Property Stock (WRSP), shaping the agricultural system, supervision over companies.

Kasa Rolniczego Ubezpieczenia Społecznego (**Agricultural Social Insurance Fund - KRUS**) is an institution which implements a separate social insurance system for farmers from the general insurance. KRUS was established to carry out tasks resulting from the Act of 20 December 1990 on social insurance of farmers (Journal of Laws of 2019, item 299, as amended) and commissioned tasks resulting from separate acts. Social insurance of farmers, in accordance with the principles set out in the Act on Social Insurance of Farmers, applies to farmers and their employees.

As of 31 December 2018, 1 233 685 persons were subject to social insurance for farmers, including: a farmer - 739 973 persons, a farmer's spouse - 332 419 persons, a householder - 152 896 persons, guardians of disabled persons - 7 909 persons, a farmer's helpers - 3 117 persons, family members taking care of a child - 13 persons. In terms of division into voivodships, the largest number of insured persons as of 31 December 2018 was in Mazowieckie (about 173.1 thousand persons).

The **General Veterinary Inspectorate** acts for the benefit of activities and improvement of the existing control systems with respect to specific zoonotic pathogens. In Poland, tasks in the area of safety of products of animal origin and food containing, at the same time, food of non-animal origin and products of animal origin found in agricultural retail trade are performed in particular by the Veterinary Inspectorate.

The Inspection of Commercial Quality of Agricultural and Food Articles (IHARS) performs the tasks specified in the Act on Commercial Quality of Agricultural and Food Articles and in other laws and regulations, both national and EU.

Agricultural Advisory Services: An important role in the modernisation of agriculture is played by Agricultural Advisory Services, which has a very long tradition in Poland. Advisory services are provided by voivodeship agricultural advisory centres, chambers of agriculture, private entities, research institutes, trade unions of agricultural producers. However, due to their human and material potential and organisational structure, voivodeship agricultural advisory centres (ODRs) are the institutions with the greatest importance and scope of providing advisory services. The activity of ODRs is supported by the Agricultural Advisory Centre in Brwinów (CDR), whose main task is to improve the knowledge and skills of advisory staff. All agricultural advisory units, i.e. 16 voivodeship ODRs and CDRs, are subordinated to the

minister in charge of rural development. Both CDR and ODRs are state organisational units with legal personality.

Regional Level

The **Marshal of the Mazowieckie Voivodeship** and the Self-Government of the Voivodeship play a key role in the implementation of the development strategy. As an entity obliged to programme and manage development at the regional level, the Self-Government is responsible for the implementation of the provisions of the Strategy which are decisive for the development of the voivodeship. Assignment of specific tasks, including activities and investments to specific self-government units ensures transparency of the policy implementation system.

The development activities are included in the Strategy for the development of the voivodeships until 2030, which provides for comprehensive activities in various areas and at all levels of management, while the self-government of the voivodeship will not be the only entity playing an important role in its implementation. According to the principles of partnership, cooperation and subsidiarity, the system of multi-level management of development processes will include partners from all levels of administration and private entities. The cooperation will be supported by the Mazovian Territorial Forum (MFT), whose work will complement the activities of the Mazovian Territorial Observatory (MOT).

The administrative unit of the voivodeship self-government is responsible for the comprehensive rural and agricultural development policy at the regional level: Department of Agriculture and Rural Development.

Regional development is the responsibility of the Mazovia Development Agency (Agencja Rozwoju Mazowsza), which was established in 2005 by a decision of the Mazovian Voivodeship Board.

The main document used to implement the regional policy is the “The Mazowieckie Voivodeship Development Strategy until 2030” - the basic and leading strategic document of the region, determining the directions of the voivodeship's policy pursued by the voivodeship's self-government, as well as transferring to the regional level the findings of national and EU documents and establishing a framework for creating more detailed documents at the regional level. The strategy is part of the future programming perspective of the European Union: 2014-2020 and transfers to the regional level the provisions of documents adopted by the government of the Republic of Poland and the European Commission.

The Office of the Marshal of the Mazowieckie Voivodeship in Warsaw is responsible for implementation of the main regional, EU-funded under cohesion policy, programme: **Regional Operational Programme of the Mazowieckie Voivodeship 2014-2020**, whose main objective is intelligent, sustainable development increasing social and territorial cohesion using the Mazovian potential The Labour Market, is a tool for the implementation of the development

policy pursued by the Local Government of the Mazovian Voivodeship. The document takes into account the thematic objectives defined by The European Commission and responds to the identified challenges of the region in terms of stimulating social and economic development, in conjunction with the objectives outlined by The Europe 2020 strategy.

At the local level, local governments implement their own policies defined in the municipal development strategies. Local development is supported by a network of Local Development Groups, established under the LEADER programme, which implement local development strategies.

3.5.2 Mission statement and the needs of pilot regions

The general mission is to strengthen the attractiveness of the region/well-being of the rural population, minimizing intra-regional disparities, sustainable development of rural areas, policy-making and good governance. The region has a high positive migration balance every year. Despite the large influx of people of working age, it has one of the highest demographic load indicators in the country. There are 57 people of non-productive age per 100 working-age persons, and this problem is increasing in the peripheral areas. Trends in migration show strong population flows from villages to cities and from large agglomerations to suburbia. This is a challenge for the attractiveness of agriculture for rural newcomers. The current state policy favours rural newcomers, especially young farmers.

The ambition is to go beyond the existing approaches and develop new, effective techniques to promote rural areas as a place of living and working for newcomers, in the context of strong impact produced by the agglomeration of rural areas, as well as changing patterns in food consumption (demand), health awareness and lifestyles. This should lead to the development of new policy strategies regarding rural development with special regard to development of new services for local communities, access to local food, quality of life, better infrastructure.

3.5.3 Matching needs with policy measures in Needs-Policy Canvas

Discussions with policy actors and regional panels during policy mapping process included online Stakeholder meeting and online policy mapping exercise with representatives of LAG and stakeholders involved in Pilot.

Pilot's needs

Mazowieckie Pilot's needs were gathered in D4.2 SWOT/Needs analysis based on questionnaire and discussions with Stakeholder Panel. Following needs have been identified:

- N01 Waste and water infrastructure
- N02 Development of transportation network in remote areas
- N03 More diverse recreational and social offer for all the age groups, and most welcome of events joining different generations

-
- N04 Establishment of cooperation/new schemes to attract relevant stakeholders in the region with cultural offer, with a special focus on integration of women, youth and potential newcomers.
 - N05 Mediation for resolving, diminishing social and political conflicts
 - N06 Diminishing income inequalities – especially in the context of educational opportunities, access to healthcare and access to public services and public goods
 - N07 Tackling unemployment
 - N08 Creating business-friendly environment
 - N09 - Provide support schemes that encourage new young people into farming
 - N10 Lack of gender and age equality in public decision-making
 - N11 Need to find solutions for problems with the integration of certain groups (young, senior policy) in remote areas
 - N12 Need to improve the farming practices and processing towards promotion of the environmentally friendly food production.
 - N13 Environmentally friendly business activities and public services

Table 12 Needs-Policy canvas, Mazowieckie, Poland

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
N01 Waste and water infrastructure	Rural Development Programme (RDP) incl. LEADER, The Mazowieckie Voivodeship Development Strategy until 2030, Regional Operational Programme Of The Mazowieckie Voivodeship 2014-2020	ERDF, ESF EAFRD	National/ Regional/ Local level	https://www.funduszedlamazowsza.eu/dokument/zapoznaj-sie-z-prawem-i-dokumentami/regional-operational-programme-of-the-mazowieckie-voivodeship-2014-2020/ https://www.gov.pl/web/rolnictwo
N02 Development of transportation network in remote areas	Rural Development Programme (RDP), The Mazowieckie Voivodeship Development Strategy until 2030, Regional Operational Programme 2014-2020	EAFRD, ERDF, ESF	National/ Regional level	https://www.funduszedlamazowsza.eu/dokument/zapoznaj-sie-z-prawem-i-dokumentami/regional-operational-programme-of-the-mazowieckie-voivodeship-2014-2020/ https://www.gov.pl/web/rolnictwo
N03 More diverse recreational and social offer for all the age groups, and most welcome of events joining different generations	LEADER, The Mazowieckie Voivodeship Development Strategy until 2030, Regional Operational Programme 2014-2020	EAFRD, ERDF, ESF	Regional/ Local level	https://www.gov.pl/web/rolnictwo https://www.funduszedlamazowsza.eu/dokument/zapoznaj-sie-z-prawem-i-dokumentami/regional-operational-programme-of-the-mazowieckie-voivodeship-2014-2020/
N05 Mediation for resolving, diminishing social and political conflicts (local level)	none	-	Local level	https://www.gov.pl/web/rolnictwo
N06 Diminishing income inequalities – especially in the context of educational opportunities, access to healthcare and access to public services and public goods	Rural Development Programme (RDP) incl. LEADER, The Mazowieckie Voivodeship Development Strategy until 2030, Regional Operational Programme Of The Mazowieckie Voivodeship 2014-2020	EAFRD, ERDF, ESF	National level	https://www.gov.pl/web/rolnictwo
N07 Tackling unemployment	Rural Development Programme (RDP) incl. LEADER, The Mazowieckie Voivodeship Development Strategy until 2030, Regional Operational Programme Of The Mazowieckie Voivodeship 2014-2020	EAFRD, ERDF, ESF	Regional level	https://www.gov.pl/web/rolnictwo

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
N08 Creating business-friendly environment	Rural Development Programme (RDP) incl. LEADER, The Mazowieckie Voivodeship Development Strategy until 2030, Regional Operational Programme Of The Mazowieckie Voivodeship 2014-2020	EAFRD, ERDF, ESF	National/ Regional/ Local level	https://www.funduszedlamazowsza.eu/dokument/zapoznaj-sie-z-prawem-i-dokumentami/regional-operational-programme-of-the-mazowieckie-voivodeship-2014-2020/
N09 - Provide support schemes that encourage new young people into farming	Rural Development Programme (RDP)	EAFRD	National level	https://www.gov.pl/web/rolnictwo
N10 Lack of gender and age equality in public decision-making	Rural Development Programme (RDP)	EAFRD	National level	https://www.gov.pl/web/rolnictwo
N11 Need to find solutions for problems with the integration of certain groups (young, senior policy) in remote areas	Rural Development Programme (RDP) incl. LEADER, The Mazowieckie Voivodeship Development Strategy until 2030, Regional Operational Programme Of The Mazowieckie Voivodeship 2014-2020	EAFRD, ERDF, ESF	National/ Regional/ Local level	https://www.gov.pl/web/rolnictwo
N12 Need to improve the farming practices and processing towards promotion of the environmentally-friendly food production.	Rural Development Programme (RDP)	EAFRD	National level	https://www.gov.pl/web/rolnictwo
N13 Environmentally friendly business activities and public services	Rural Development Programme (RDP), LEADER	EAFRD	National/ Local level	https://www.gov.pl/web/rolnictwo

3.6 Pilot 6 Central Bohemian Region, Czech Republic

3.6.1 Description of respective governance structures

The state authority responsible for agriculture as an integral part of rural environment and development is **the Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic**. In connection with the reform of the Common Agricultural Policy, the ministry is striving to increase the competitiveness of European agriculture and to make an associated reduction in the administrative burden both for farmers and government.

The Czech Republic was one of the first countries to agree a Rural Development Programme, under which funding may primarily be drawn by farmers, food producers, owners and tenants of forest land and municipalities.⁶¹ The **Rural Development Programme** co-financing tool under the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national contributions, is subject to numerous regulations spearheaded by Regulation (EU) No 1303/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 laying down common provisions on the European Structural and Investment Funds (the Common Provisions Regulation). The rural development policy, drawn up by reference to the Common Provisions Regulation, has been devised to bolster farmers' competitiveness, the sustainable management of natural resources, climate-related measures and balanced rural development. Rural development funding through the EAFRD is part of a broader framework of European Structural and Investment Funds (ESI Funds), including also European Regional Development, European Social, Cohesion, and Fisheries Funds. These are managed nationally, by each EU Member State, on the basis of Partnership Agreements, strategic plans outlining the country's goals and investment priorities.⁶²

Local Action Groups (LAGs) represent a community instrument for the management of local development in rural areas. According to the standards of the Common Provisions Regulation, the LAGs have to prove that they have the capacity to contribute to the implementation of programmes financed by ESI Funds. A partnership agreement has made the Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic responsible for setting these standards. LAGs passing the standardisation process are able to submit subsidy applications in support of their community-led local development strategy (SCLLD) to the Ministry of Regional Development of the Czech Republic, as the body responsible for this area.⁶³

Czech Rural Network is a part of National Rural Networks which operate in each EU Member State to support and enhance rural development objectives, enable and facilitate exchange

⁶¹ Ministry of Agriculture (2013). Supporting our rural tradition & development.

http://eagri.cz/public/web/file/214061/publikace_mze_A4_rozvoj_venkova_ENG_FINAL.pdf

⁶² ENRD (2020). Czech Republic. https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/country/czechrepublic_en

⁶³ The State Agricultural Intervention Fund (2020). Rural Development Programme 2014-2020. https://www.szif.cz/en/rdp_2014_2020

and learning among all partners involved in rural policy implementation. The Czech Rural Network was established by the Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic as a communication platform to support appropriate and effective communication and to share best practices and other related information as the most important elements for successful rural development.⁶⁴

In the area of regional policy, the state authority is **the Ministry of Regional Development of the Czech Republic**. The development of regions focused on their cohesion and boosting competitiveness belongs among basic objectives of the regional policy - each region should have an opportunity for its own balanced development complying with the potential and specific features thereof. The Ministry of the Regional Development of the Czech Republic is also the Managing Authority of the Integrated Regional Operational Programme (IROP). The priority of IROP is to enable a balanced territorial development, improvement of the infrastructure, improvement of public services and public administration and ensuring sustainable development in municipalities, cities and regions.

Regional policy gives particular attention to specific issues of the development of towns and rural areas. Concerning rural development, the Ministry of Regional Development of the Czech Republic is a coordinator of its strategic planning and it is also responsible for important tools of rural development, e.g. CLLD or specific national funding programmes.

The **Strategy of the Regional Development of the Czech Republic 2014 – 2020** constitutes the basic instrument of the regional policy. It secures coherence of the national regional policy with the regional policy of the European Union and with other sectoral policies having impact on the development of territory, and **regionally targeted development programmes** financed from national sources or co-financed from the European Union.

Specific attention is paid to using of new technologies in urban and regional development with the general aim of improving quality of life. The Ministry of Regional Development provides methodological support for the implementation of the Smart Cities concept in urban governance, coordinates networking and sharing of good practice examples, including the best practice from abroad.⁶⁵

Many other state institutions are also involved in rural and development policy-making processes. From the perspective of new global trends, the Ministry of the Environment of the Czech Republic is responsible for issues related to global changes in the environment, the Ministry of the Interior of the Czech Republic and the Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Czech Republic are responsible for issues related to digitalisation. The Ministry of Industry and

⁶⁴ ENRD (2020). Czech Rural Network. https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/networking/nrn-profiles/czech-rural-network_en

⁶⁵ Ministry of Regional Development (2018). Regional Policy. <https://www.mmr.cz/en/ministerstvo/regionalni-rozvoj>

Trade of the Czech Republic and the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports are responsible for Research, Development and Innovation policy.

Healthy Cities of the Czech Republic is an association of Czech municipalities that stipulates in its statutes to consistently work towards sustainable development, health, and the quality of life in cities, municipalities and regions of the Czech Republic.⁶⁶

Union of Towns and Municipalities of the Czech Republic is a voluntary, apolitical and non-governmental organisation founded as an interest group of towns and municipalities. The Union is a partner to governmental and parliamentary political representation and therefore participates in the preparation and creation of draft legislative measures in areas pertaining to the competencies of municipalities. The Union associates more than 2 700 municipalities and towns, which represent more around 80% of the total population of the Czech Republic.⁶⁷

The activity of the Union is primarily based on the participation of mayors, lord mayors and municipal representatives who, beyond the framework of their duties, are also devoted to general self-government issues. Under the Union was released one of the key current strategy related to the rural development - **Strategic framework of the Union of Towns and Municipalities in the field of Smart City**⁶⁸. This long-term strategy with the outlook to 2035/2050 is based on global trends and it is focused to wellbeing and improvement of quality of life via new technologies and innovative solutions and approaches. The strategy is conceived for municipalities of different sizes and needs and it is adapted to the specific settlement structure of the Czech Republic with many small villages.

Local governments are responsible for the regional development. The key policy document of **The Central Bohemian Region Authority is the Development program of the territorial district of the Central Bohemian Region, for the period 2018-2024 (outlook to 2030)**, which aims and matches the vast majority or identified needs of the region.

3.6.2 Mission statement and the needs of pilot regions

The Central Bohemian Region is the biggest region of the Czech Republic (according to the dimension - 10 929 km²/ 14 % of the Czech Republic and population - 1 377 000 inhabitants/12,86 % of the Czech Republic). The Central Bohemian Region has no natural center (as other regions), but for this region the natural center is the capital city. The region is separated into two parts - the metropolitan and peripheral areas (mostly rural). There is a very specific settlement structure in the region - even in the European context - with many

⁶⁶ Healthy Cities of the Czech Republic (2020). HCCZ Basic Info. <https://www.healthycities.cz/en/basic-info>

⁶⁷ Svaz měst a obcí České republiky (2020). Official websites. <https://www.smocr.cz/cs>

⁶⁸ Svaz měst a obcí ČR (2020). SMART Česko. www.smartcesko.cz

small villages (1140 in total; 1031 municipalities with less than 2000 inhabitants⁶⁹), which is related to many infrastructural challenges and issues.

The overall ambition of the pilot is to support the sustainability and resilience of rural areas via using new modern technologies/methods, to boost the attractiveness of rural areas for current rural population and newcomers and to make policy-making processes in these fields more effective with the ability to respond flexibly to current and new challenges and issues.

In relation to the characteristics of the Central Bohemian Region, needs bellow were identified as crucial:

- N01 Need to ensure accessibility of services for all inhabitants of the region
- N02 Need to enhance high-speed internet to the whole region
- N05 Need to create a resilient region
- N09 Need for boosting of the attractiveness of the region for tourism and agrotourism
- N11 Need to minimize of intra-regional disparities
- N12 Need to support wellbeing of all inhabitants
- N15 Need to attract young professionals to work in high-tech/innovative companies and research organizations located in the region
- N16 Need to have sufficient social and health services for aging population
- N17 Need to establish new high-tech/innovative companies and their connection with research organizations, support of develop start-ups and spin off companies
- N25 Need for adaptation to the climate change
- N26 Need to use of soil and land in the sustainable way
- N27 Need for transition to the circular economy and bioeconomy

3.6.3 Matching needs with policy measures in Needs-Policy Canvas

Needs and policy matching was discussed with stakeholders personally, via phone call or online.

Table 13. Needs-policy canvas, Central Bohemian Region, Czech Republic

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
N01 Need to ensure accessibility of services for all inhabitants of the region	Strategic framework of the Union of Towns and Municipalities in the field of Smart City	-	Municipality level	http://prosperujiciobecbudoucnosti.cz/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Strategicky-ramec-Svazu-mest-a-obci-v-oblasti-Smart-City_implementation-cast.pdf

⁶⁹ Český statistický úřad (2020). Města a obce. https://www.czso.cz/csu/xs/mesta_a_obce

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
N01 Need to ensure accessibility of services for all inhabitants of the region	Development programme of the territorial district of the Central Bohemian Region, for the period 2018-2024 (outlook to 2030)	-	Regional level	https://s-ic.cz/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/Program-rozvoje-kraje_podklady-pro-aktualizaci-strategie-v2.pdf
N01 Need to ensure accessibility of services for all inhabitants of the region	State policy in electronic communications - Digital Czech Republic v. 2.0	-	State	https://www.databaze-strategie.cz/cz/mpo/strategie/statni-politika-v-elektronickych-komunikacich-digitalni-cesko-v-2-0-cesta-k-digitalni-ekonomice-statni-politika-v-elektronickych-komunikacich-digitalni-cesko-v-2-0-cesta-k-digitalni-ekonomice
N01 Need to ensure accessibility of services for all inhabitants of the region	Digital Czech Republic: The Concept of Digital Economy and Society (2018)	-	State	https://www.databaze-strategie.cz/cz/mpo/strategie/digitalni-ekonomika-a-spolecnost
N02 Need to enhance high-speed internet to the whole region	Strategic framework of the Union of Towns and Municipalities in the field of Smart City	ERDF	Municipality level	http://prosperujiciobecbudoucnosti.cz/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Strategicky-ramec-Svazu-mest-a-obci-v-oblasti-Smart-City_implementation-cast.pdf
N02 Need to enhance high-speed internet to the whole region	Digital Czech Republic: The Concept of Digital Economy and Society (2018)	ERDF	State	https://www.databaze-strategie.cz/cz/mpo/strategie/digitalni-ekonomika-a-spolecnost
N03 Need to reconstruct/build the transport infrastructure	Strategic framework of the Union of Towns and Municipalities in the field of Smart City	ERDF, CF	Municipality level	http://prosperujiciobecbudoucnosti.cz/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Strategicky-ramec-Svazu-mest-a-obci-v-oblasti-Smart-City_implementation-cast.pdf
N03 Need to reconstruct/build the transport infrastructure	Development program of the territorial district of the Central Bohemian Region, for the period 2018-2024 (outlook to 2030)	ERDF, CF	Regional level	https://s-ic.cz/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/Program-rozvoje-kraje_podklady-pro-aktualizaci-strategie-v2.pdf
N04 Need to strengthen the cooperation between education and business	Strategic framework of the Union of Towns and Municipalities in the field of Smart City	ESF, ERDF	Municipality level	http://prosperujiciobecbudoucnosti.cz/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Strategicky-ramec-Svazu-mest-a-obci-v-oblasti-Smart-City_implementation-cast.pdf
N04 Need to strengthen the cooperation between education and business	Development program of the territorial district of the Central	ESF, ERDF	Regional level	https://s-ic.cz/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/Program-rozvoje-kraje_podklady-pro-aktualizaci-strategie-v2.pdf

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
	Bohemian Region, for the period 2018-2024 (outlook to 2030)			
N04 Need to strengthen the cooperation between education and business	Strategy of digital education in the Czech Republic until 2020	ESF, ERDF	State	https://www.databaze-strategie.cz/cz/msmt/strategie/strategie-digitalniho-vzdelavani
N05 Need to create a resilient region	Development program of the territorial district of the Central Bohemian Region, for the period 2018-2024 (outlook to 2030)	-	Regional level	https://s-ic.cz/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/Program-rozvoje-kraje_podklady-pro-aktualizaci-strategie-v2.pdf
N05 Need to create a resilient region	Concept for protection against the consequences of drought for the territory of the Czech Republic (2017)	-	State	https://www.databaze-strategie.cz/cz/mze/strategie/koncepce-na-ochranu-pred-nasledky-suchoa-pro-uzemi-ceske-republiky
N06 Need to establish functional e-government/public administration and other digital services	Strategic framework of the Union of Towns and Municipalities in the field of Smart City	ERDF, ESF	Municipality level	http://prosperujiciobecbudoucnosti.cz/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Strategicky-ramec-Svazu-mest-a-obci-v-oblasti-Smart-City_implementation-cast.pdf
N06 Need to establish functional e-government/public administration and other digital services	Strategic framework for the development of public administration in the Czech Republic for the period 2014-2020	ERDF, ESF	State	https://www.mvcr.cz/clanek/strategicky-ramec-rozvoje.aspx
N07 Need to establish integrated health and social care (especially related to aging population)	Strategic framework of the Union of Towns and Municipalities in the field of Smart City	ESF	Municipality level	http://prosperujiciobecbudoucnosti.cz/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Strategicky-ramec-Svazu-mest-a-obci-v-oblasti-Smart-City_implementation-cast.pdf
N07 Need to establish integrated health and social care (especially related to aging population)	Development program of the territorial district of the Central Bohemian Region, for the period 2018-2024 (outlook to 2030)	ESF	Regional level	https://s-ic.cz/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/Program-rozvoje-kraje_podklady-pro-aktualizaci-strategie-v2.pdf
N08 Need to preserve cultural landscape and cultural heritage	Development program of the territorial district of the Central Bohemian Region, for the period	-	Regional level	https://s-ic.cz/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/Program-rozvoje-kraje_podklady-pro-aktualizaci-strategie-v2.pdf

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
	2018-2024 (outlook to 2030)			
N09 Need for boosting of the attractiveness of the region for tourism and agrotourism	Development program of the territorial district of the Central Bohemian Region, for the period 2018-2024 (outlook to 2030)	-	Regional level	https://www.databaze-strategie.cz/cz/mmr/strategie/politika-uzemniho-rozvoje-cr-ve-zneni-aktualizace-c-1-2015?typ=download
N10 Need to develop and support community activities	Strategic framework of the Union of Towns and Municipalities in the field of Smart City	-	Municipality level	http://prosperujiciobecbudoucnosti.cz/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Strategicky-ramec-Svazu-mest-a-obci-v-oblasti-Smart-City_implementation-cast.pdf
N11 Need to minimizing of intra-regional disparities	Development program of the territorial district of the Central Bohemian Region, for the period 2018-2024 (outlook to 2030)	-	Regional level	https://s-ic.cz/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/Program-rozvoje-kraje_podklady-pro-aktualizaci-strategie-v2.pdf
N12 Need to support wellbeing of all inhabitants	Strategic framework of the Union of Towns and Municipalities in the field of Smart City	ERDF, ESF, CF	Municipality level	http://prosperujiciobecbudoucnosti.cz/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Strategicky-ramec-Svazu-mest-a-obci-v-oblasti-Smart-City_implementation-cast.pdf
N13 Need to support the local identity	Strategic framework of the Union of Towns and Municipalities in the field of Smart City	-	Municipality level	http://prosperujiciobecbudoucnosti.cz/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Strategicky-ramec-Svazu-mest-a-obci-v-oblasti-Smart-City_implementation-cast.pdf
N14 Need to boost the attractiveness of all parts of the region for new entrants	Development program of the territorial district of the Central Bohemian Region, for the period 2018-2024 (outlook to 2030)	-	Regional level	
N15 Need to attract young professionals to work in high-tech/innovative companies and research organizations located in the region	Development program of the territorial district of the Central Bohemian Region, for the period 2018-2024 (outlook to 2030)	-	Regional level	https://s-ic.cz/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/Program-rozvoje-kraje_podklady-pro-aktualizaci-strategie-v2.pdf
N15 Need to attract young professionals to work in high-tech/innovative companies and research organizations located in the region	National Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialization (RIS3 strategy)	-	State	

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
N16 Need to have sufficient social and health services for aging population	Strategic framework of the Union of Towns and Municipalities in the field of Smart City	ERDF	Municipality level	http://prosperujiciobecbudoucnosti.cz/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Strategicky-ramec-Svazu-mest-a-obci-v-oblasti-Smart-City_implementacni-cast.pdf
N17 Need to establish new high-tech/innovative companies and their connection with research organizations, support of develop start-ups and spin off companies	Development program of the territorial district of the Central Bohemian Region, for the period 2018-2024 (outlook to 2030)	ERDF	Regional level	https://s-ic.cz/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/Program-rozvoje-kraje_podklady-pro-aktualizaci-strategie-v2.pdf
N18 Need to implement the quadruple helix model and support of the cooperation between research organizations and municipalities	Strategic framework of the Union of Towns and Municipalities in the field of Smart City	-	Municipality level	http://prosperujiciobecbudoucnosti.cz/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Strategicky-ramec-Svazu-mest-a-obci-v-oblasti-Smart-City_implementacni-cast.pdf
N19 Need to shorten of supply chains and support of the local economy	Strategic framework of the Union of Towns and Municipalities in the field of Smart City	-	Municipality level	http://prosperujiciobecbudoucnosti.cz/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Strategicky-ramec-Svazu-mest-a-obci-v-oblasti-Smart-City_implementacni-cast.pdf
N20 Need to support remote working and other job opportunities related to the local economy	Strategic framework of the Union of Towns and Municipalities in the field of Smart City	-	Municipality level	http://prosperujiciobecbudoucnosti.cz/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Strategicky-ramec-Svazu-mest-a-obci-v-oblasti-Smart-City_implementacni-cast.pdf
N21 Need to support of precision agriculture and other innovative solutions	Strategic framework of the Union of Towns and Municipalities in the field of Smart City	EAFRD	Municipality level	http://prosperujiciobecbudoucnosti.cz/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Strategicky-ramec-Svazu-mest-a-obci-v-oblasti-Smart-City_implementacni-cast.pdf
N22 Need for the coherent community	Strategic framework of the Union of Towns and Municipalities in the field of Smart City	-	Municipality level	http://prosperujiciobecbudoucnosti.cz/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Strategicky-ramec-Svazu-mest-a-obci-v-oblasti-Smart-City_implementacni-cast.pdf
N23 Need to sustain the gender equal society	Strategic framework of the Union of Towns and Municipalities in the field of Smart City	ESF	Municipality level	http://prosperujiciobecbudoucnosti.cz/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Strategicky-ramec-Svazu-mest-a-obci-v-oblasti-Smart-City_implementacni-cast.pdf

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
N24 Need to develop open society and strong communities	Strategic framework of the Union of Towns and Municipalities in the field of Smart City	-	Municipality level	http://prosperujiciobecbudouc.nosti.cz/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Strategicky-ramec-Svazu-mest-a-obci-v-oblasti-Smart-City_implementation-cast.pdf
N25 Need for adaptation to the climate change	Strategic framework of the Union of Towns and Municipalities in the field of Smart City	ERDF, CF	Municipality level	http://prosperujiciobecbudouc.nosti.cz/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Strategicky-ramec-Svazu-mest-a-obci-v-oblasti-Smart-City_implementation-cast.pdf
N25 Need for adaptation to the climate change	Development program of the territorial district of the Central Bohemian Region, for the period 2018-2024 (outlook to 2030)	ERDF, CF	Regional level	https://s-ic.cz/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/Program-rozvoje-kraje_podklady-pro-aktualizaci-strategie-v2.pdf
N25 Need for adaptation to the climate change	Rural Development Programme of the Czech Republic	ERDF, CF	State	http://eagri.cz/public/web/file/473409/Program_rozvoje_venkova_schvalene_zneni.pdf
N26 Need to use of soil and land in the sustainable way	Strategic framework of the Union of Towns and Municipalities in the field of Smart City	ERDF, EAFRD	Municipality level	http://prosperujiciobecbudouc.nosti.cz/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Strategicky-ramec-Svazu-mest-a-obci-v-oblasti-Smart-City_implementation-cast.pdf

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
N26 Need to use of soil and land in the sustainable way	The State Environmental Policy of the Czech Republic 2012-2020	ERDF	State	https://www.databaze-strategie.cz/cz/mzp/strategie/s-tatni-politika-zivotniho-prostredi-cr-2012-2020-akt-2016
N26 Need to use of soil and land in the sustainable way	Concept for protection against the consequences of drought for the territory of the Czech Republic (2017)	ERDF	State	https://www.databaze-strategie.cz/cz/mze/strategie/k-oncepcie-na-ochranu-pred-nasledky-suchoa-pro-uzemi-ceske-republiky
N26 Need to use of soil and land in the sustainable way	National Action Plan to Reduce the Use of Pesticides in the Czech Republic (2012)		State	https://www.databaze-strategie.cz/cz/mze/strategie/n-rodni-akcni-plan-ke-snizeni-pouzivani-pesticidu-v-ceske-republice
N27 Need for transition to the circular economy and bioeconomy	Strategic framework of the Union of Towns and Municipalities in the field of Smart City		Municipality level	http://prosperujiciobecbudoucnosti.cz/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Strategicky-ramec-Svazu-mest-a-obci-v-oblasti-Smart-City_implementation-cast.pdf
N27 Need for transition to the circular economy and bioeconomy	Development program of the territorial district of the Central Bohemian Region, for the period 2018-2024 (outlook to 2030)		Regional level	https://s-ic.cz/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/Program-rozvoje-kraje_podklady-pro-aktualizaci-strategie-v2.pdf

3.7 Pilot 7 Slovakia, Slovakia

3.7.1 Description of respective governance structures

Based on a new typology of rural areas developed by the European Commission (Eurostat), Slovakia is 50.3% prevailing in predominantly rural areas, 38.4% in transitional areas and 11.2% in predominantly urban areas. Of the total area of the SR according to individual types of regions, the largest share is 59%, also in predominantly rural area, 36.8% share is in transition regions, and the lowest share- 4.2% is predominantly in urban regions. Total rural regions thus account for 95.8% of the territory of the country. Behalf of these facts, the SK pilot includes whole Slovakia as single region.⁷⁰

Rural Development in Slovakia is managed nationally through **one Rural Development Programme (RDP)**, funded under the [European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development \(EAFRD\)](#) and national contributions. **The Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Slovak Republic** is the top government body, responsible for drafting and implementing laws and regulations in the field of agriculture and rural development in Slovakia.⁷¹

On the basis of Council Regulation (EC) No. 1305/2013 on support for rural development by European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD), each member state has an obligation to establish a **national rural network (NRN)**, which groups the organizations and authorities involved in rural development.

Governance of NRN is covered by specific department of **Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Slovak Republic**. The Rural Development Programme of Slovak Republic 2014 - 2020 defines a structure of NRN and Regional Units of NRN as an executive element of the network, which is performed by **Agency for Rural Development (ARVI)**. Network Unit – head office is included in the structure of Agency for Rural Development in Nitra as a separate Department of the National Network for Rural Development. Most of the team of NRN is decentralized and various regional antennas operate in 8 regions of Slovakia, where they are located within existing organizations focused on rural development, and it is reflected in the requirement to use existing structures and capacities. The Central Unit is responsible for coordination of the regional antennas/coordinators.

⁷⁰ Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Slovak Republic
<https://www.mpsr.sk/en/index.php?navID=29>

⁷¹ European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD), website
https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/country/slovakia_en

Figure 7. National rural development network in Slovak.

The Slovak Rural Network⁷² established its objectives in line with the mandatory NRN objectives, set by the EU Regulation. The NRN is opened to everyone. There is no special selection process, but there is a subscription process according to 5 specific categories: agriculture, forestry, municipalities–villages, LEADER/CLLD and EIP.

⁷² National Rural Networks, website <http://www.nsrv.sk/>

Figure 8. The map of 110 LAGs in Slovakia

Local action groups⁷³ are perspective platforms of the inter-municipal cooperation and, within the fragmented settlement structure of Slovakia, they represent the possibility for consolidation of the local self-governments and support for the development of the regions.⁷⁴

Except LAGs, there are 29 **Regional Development Agencies** in Integrated network⁷⁵. The main objective of the Regional Development Agencies is to support an economic and social development in Slovakia Self Governing Regions. Regional development Agencies connect public sector, self administration, private sector and third sector within the one public body. All entities involved can be fully focused on constant development of their region.

The Agricultural Paying Agency - APA is a budgetary organization financed through the budget of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Slovak Republic.⁷⁶

Main tasks of APA include collecting applications for funding from RDP and direct payments for approved assistance schemes, evaluation of eligibility for funding, reimbursement of funding, audit of compliance with conditions for use of requested funding and monitoring of compliance with contract conditions. In addition it also provides for market organisation through CAP facilities, administration of national subsidies.

⁷³ Local Action Group as a Tool of Inter-municipal Cooperation: Case Study of Slovakia, May 18, 2019 <https://www.unipo.sk/public/media/32579/529%20LOCAL%20ACTION%20GROUP%20AS%20A%20OOL%20OF%20INTER-MUNICIPAL%20COOPERATION%20-%20CASE%20STUDY%20OF%20SLOVAKIA.pdf>

⁷⁴ The list of LAGs <http://www.nsrv.sk/?pl=91>

⁷⁵ Regional Development Agencies website <https://isrrask.webnode.sk/o-nas/>

⁷⁶ The Agricultural Paying Agency <http://www.apa.sk/en/>

The following institutions and organisations are involved in the Agricultural advisory system in Slovakia: The National Council of the Slovak Republic, The Government of the Slovak Republic,

Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development with the Council for Agricultural Extension, The Department of Science and Research of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, The Agricultural Paying Agency (APA), The Agroinstitut Nitra – Lifelong Learning and accreditation of the advisors, Regional Info-terminals, The National Forestry Centre (The Institute of Forestry Extension and Lifelong Learning, Zvolen), Other sector institutions (research institutions) Accredited extension experts, acting individually or in extension agencies.

History: A document in the area of rural development politics at the national level with title of “**Conceptual Policy for Rural Development in the Slovak Republic by the year 2005**” was adopted in the year 1998. The basic objective of the document was to ensure an adequate standard of living and improvement of quality of life of the rural population, sufficient job opportunities and adequate incomes by means of economic activities in the areas of agriculture, forestry, water management, food processing industry, traditional crafts, services and tourism, creation of an appropriate social climate, protection and formation of a healthy environment. This document was the basis framework for the elaboration of strategy in the **Pre-accession Programme SAPARD**. The main realisation instrument for rural development in the pre-accession period was the Agriculture and Rural Development Plan of the SR – SAPARD Programme. This programme contained three priorities and nine measures within them. **NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT PLAN OF THE SLOVAK REPUBLIC 2004-2006:** An integrated approach to addressing rural development was carried out in cooperation with objectives, priorities and measures of the National Development Plan (NDP), which was the basic programming document of the SR for drawing funds from structural funds of the EC in period 2004-2006.

Implementation and achievement of the objective in the field of agricultural production and quality of life of the rural population was being realised through the Sectoral Operational Programme Agriculture and Rural Development 2004-2006 (hereinafter referred to as the SOP).

SECTORAL OPERATIONAL PROGRAMME AGRICULTURE AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT 2004-2006

The Sectoral Operational Programme was a programming document for drawing funds from EAGGF and FIFG Guidance Sections.

The support was being realised on the territory of the whole Slovakia with the exception of Bratislava region. **The Rural Development Plan of the Slovak Republic 2004-2006** (hereinafter referred to as the RDP) was a programming document elaborated in compliance with Council Regulation (EC) No 1257/1999 for drawing of funds from the Guarantee Section of the EAGGF.

For the programme period of years **2007 – 2013 the National Strategic Reference Framework** was drawn up as a basic document for drawing of financial resources from the structural funds and the Cohesion Fund of EU. In 2008 the Government of SR adopted the new Act No. 539/2008 Coll. on the promotion of regional development. This act defined **the National Regional Development Strategy of SR** (hereinafter “National Strategy”) as a basic document for the promotion of regional development at the national level.

The National Strategy was a basic document for the preparation of a programme document for the use of financial resources from the EU funds for period of years **2014 – 2020**.

3.7.2 Mission statement and the needs of pilot regions

Mission statement for Slovakia region pilot:

To increase the attractiveness of the region, well-being of the existing rural population and attract newcomers, while not affecting the symbiosis between city and rural areas, by introducing policies reflecting the needs of local entrepreneurs and demand of local population, safeguarding the environment and biodiversity at the same time. Introducing a new way of decision making and implementation of public policies in cooperation and consultation with all relevant stakeholders during all stages.

Based on T4.3 Slovakia Region Pilot’s SWOT/Needs analysis, the needs of the pilot were identified as follows:

	No.	Needs
1. Business, economy & innovation	1	Need to promote job creation with adequate pay and with a view to supporting small and medium-sized enterprises, eco-firms and sustainable business (circular economy).
	2	Need to offer good opportunities for creating start-ups and new businesses as well as adequate services for entrepreneurial support with the aim to use the potential of the area for new, innovative companies and creative professionals.
	3	Need to increase a financial aid for innovative/new rural activities
	4	Need to consider an adequate special taxation scheme to attract and creating new businesses.
	5	Need to develop a long term vision for the development and stability of rural areas and agriculture with the aim to restore the self-sufficiency. Need to improve transparency of direct payments for farmers and rural development program projects. Need to pay special attention and give special support to young, family and small farmers.
2. Environment & biodiversity	6	Need to change the support in the agricultural area from per hectare basis on added value and environmental sustainability. Need to give more emphasis on domestic local production which is more sustainable and healthy respecting the local food traditions.
	7	Need to valorise more high nature value areas as environment and nature play an important role.
	8	Need to have sustainable settlements, regions and landscape in the context of climate change, specifically improving access to drinking water, sewerage and clean resources available, sustainable urban development, preventing climate change and, last but not least, protecting terrestrial life.
	9	Need to prevent devastation of forest and logging especially in national parks.
3. Living condition,	10	Need to find solutions for problems with the integration of some part of populations, minority, minorities, and new entrants.

	No.	Needs
quality of life and standard of living	11	Need to improve the adequacy of housing opportunities in rural areas.
	12	Need to improve the quality of living conditions and to provide basic services, such as repairer, electrician, woodwork, leatherwork, hairdresser, babysitter etc.
	13	Need for activities for poverty reduction and social inclusion including to improve access to accommodation for people at risk of poverty.
	14	Need to finalize long lasting land consolidation schemes and improve the access to land for young, small and new farmers.
	15	Need to improve the quality of education, including vocational education and lifelong learning and to strengthen the social status of teachers and educators for dignified life, work and economic growth and the balancing of social inequalities.
4. Recreation / social activities	16	Need to improve availability and diversity of recreational and social activities.
	17	Need to make rural areas more attractive for young people by providing them a space where they can meet each other and socialize. Need to have recreational space for families with children.
	18	Need to organize local projects driven and owned by local people.
	19	Need to promote community gardens, school gardens run by students and school community and organize excursions and trips for schools at local farms.
	20	Need to create and develop local action groups / communities.
5. Availability of public and other services	21	Need to improve quality of public services, for example to create and support tele-working opportunities, improve the mobility possibilities to the main city and the connections between rural and urban areas, increase good medical (primary attention) services and adequate public support for the provision of e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services, simplify the rules for direct sales of products from farms and restore local market halls and places.
	22	Need to encourage cooperation of different public sectors, such as agriculture, education, health, environment, regional development, transport etc.
	23	Need to have a state run promotion of healthy nutrition with special attention to schools, hospitals, social establishment that could procure directly from local farmers.
	24	Need to have a state run promotion of establishments for tourism based on making Slovakia attractive as tourist destination unknown to many.
6. Demographic & human capital	25	Need to improve the dependency ratio by increasing the number of working people in the area; there are not enough working people to support the dependent population (i.s. children, elderly) and support generation exchange in agriculture.
	26	Need to improve development community and voluntary sector development focused on social needs and creation of new opportunities
	27	Need to provide incentives for young people to come to live and work in rural areas through scholarships, providing accommodation in vocational schools etc.
7. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	28	Need to create opportunities for young people to participate in decision making.
	29	Need to increase the number of sufficiently lively communities In the area and citizen-driven local activities and need to promote local organizations promoting regional specialties, crafts, traditions.
	30	Need to change social thinking about employment in agriculture through targeted promotion.
	31	Need to organize local social and cultural and artistic events and fairs, events for students, children, families and young generation.

No.	Needs
32	Need to motivate to use modern ways of presenting cultural heritage with the use of new technologies and progressive marketing methods including involve local actors in commercial exploitation of cultural heritage and promote access to the digitized heritage to the general public and business entities, taking into account the needs of disabled people.

3.7.3 Matching needs with policy measures in Needs-Policy Canvas

After further (phone, face to face meeting and online meeting) discussions with the members of the Slovakia Region Pilot's stakeholders panel and policy makers, the list of needs from section 3.2.2 was modified and reduced to the following top 6 needs:

- **N1** Promote job creation with adequate pay and with a view to supporting small and medium-sized enterprises, eco-firms and sustainable business (circular economy).
- **N5** Develop a long term vision for the development and stability of rural areas and agriculture with the aim to restore the self-sufficiency. Need to improve transparency of direct payments for farmers and rural development program projects. Need to pay special attention and give special support to young, family and small farmers.
- **N8** Have sustainable settlements, regions and landscape in the context of climate change, specifically improving access to drinking water, sewerage and clean resources available, sustainable urban development, preventing climate change and, last but not least, protecting terrestrial life.
- **N 11** Improve the adequacy of housing opportunities in rural areas.
- **N 21** Need to improve quality of public services, for example create and support tele-working opportunities, improve the mobility possibilities to the main city and the connections between rural and urban areas, increase good medical (primary attention) services and adequate public support for the provision of e-health, e-day-care and/or e-learning services, simplify the rules for direct sales of products from farms, and restore local market halls and places.
- **N 29** Increase the number of sufficiently lively communities in the area and citizen-driven local activities and need to promote local organizations promoting regional specialties, crafts, traditions.

Table 14. Needs-Policy Canvas, Slovakia

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/program me/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
N01: Need to promote job creation with adequate pay and with a view to supporting small and medium-sized enterprises, eco-firms and sustainable business (circular economy).	Rural development program of Slovakia	EAFRD	EU level, Local /grassroot level	https://www.mpsr.sk/rozvoj-vidieka-a-priame-platby-rybne-hospodarstvo/prv-sr-2014-2020/47-43-935
N01: Need to promote job creation with adequate pay and with a view to supporting small and medium-sized enterprises,	Rural development program of Slovakia	EAFRD	National level	https://www.mpsr.sk/rozvoj-vidieka-a-priame-platby-rybne-hospodarstvo/prv-sr-2014-2020/47-43-935

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
eco-firms and sustainable business (circular economy).				2020/47-43-935, www.vupp.sk/04komodity.htm
N01: Need to promote job creation with adequate pay and with a view to supporting small and medium-sized enterprises, eco-firms and sustainable business (circular economy).	Program of Development of the Nitra Self-Governing Region	ERDF, ESF	Regional level	https://www.unsk.sk/zobraz/sekciu/dokumenty-regionalneho-rozvoja
N01: Need to promote job creation with adequate pay and with a view to supporting small and medium-sized enterprises, eco-firms and sustainable business (circular economy).	human resources development	ERDF, LEADER	Regional level	http://www.unatin.ocu.sk/dokumenty/U%C5%88at%C3%ADn%20PHSR-1.pdf
N01: Need to promote job creation with adequate pay and with a view to supporting small and medium-sized enterprises, eco-firms and sustainable business (circular economy).	Program of economic and social development of the village	ERDF	Regional level	www.obecsuchan.sk
N01: Need to promote job creation with adequate pay and with a view to supporting small and medium-sized enterprises, eco-firms and sustainable business (circular economy).	Public policy	ERDF	National level	https://www.zabiedovo.sk/programy-a-plany.phtml?id3=114182
N01: Need to promote job creation with adequate pay and with a view to supporting small and medium-sized enterprises, eco-firms and sustainable business (circular economy).	maintaining the traditional rural environment	-	Local /grassroot level	N/A
N01: Need to promote job creation with adequate pay and with a view to supporting small and medium-sized enterprises, eco-firms and sustainable business (circular economy).	Forest Management Program	EAFRD	Local /grassroot level	http://www.forestportal.sk/lesne-hospodarstvo/hospodarska-uprava-lesov/program-starostlivosti-olesy/Stranky/default.aspx
N05: Need to develop a long term vision for the development and stability of rural areas and agriculture with the aim to restore the self-sufficiency. Need to improve transparency of direct payments for farmers and rural development program projects. Need to pay special attention and give special support to young, family and small farmers.	Rural development program of Slovakia	EAFRD	EU level, Local /grassroot level	https://www.mpsr.sk/rozvoj-vidieka-a-priame-platby-rybné-hospodarstvo/prv-sr-2014-2020/47-43-935
N05: Need to develop a long term vision for the development and stability of rural areas and agriculture with the aim to restore the self-sufficiency. Need to improve transparency of direct payments for farmers and rural development program projects. Need to pay special attention and give special support to young, family and small farmers.	Rural development program of Slovakia	ERDF	National level	www.vupp.sk/04komodity.htm

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/program me/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
N05: Need to develop a long term vision for the development and stability of rural areas and agriculture with the aim to restore the self-sufficiency. Need to improve transparency of direct payments for farmers and rural development program projects. Need to pay special attention and give special support to young, family and small farmers.	Program of Development of the Nitra Self-Governing Region	ERDF, ESF	Regional level	https://www.unsk.sk/zobraz/sekciu/dokumenty-regionalneho-rozvoja
N05: Need to develop a long term vision for the development and stability of rural areas and agriculture with the aim to restore the self-sufficiency. Need to improve transparency of direct payments for farmers and rural development program projects. Need to pay special attention and give special support to young, family and small farmers.	The economic development program of the municipality supports the development of the business environment in the municipality	ERDF	Regional level, Local /grassroot level	www.bohelov.sk
N05: Need to develop a long term vision for the development and stability of rural areas and agriculture with the aim to restore the self-sufficiency. Need to improve transparency of direct payments for farmers and rural development program projects. Need to pay special attention and give special support to young, family and small farmers.	human resources development	ERDF, LEADER	Regional level	http://www.unatin.ocu.sk/dokumenty/U%C5%88at%C3%ADn%20PHSR-1.pdf
N05: Need to develop a long term vision for the development and stability of rural areas and agriculture with the aim to restore the self-sufficiency. Need to improve transparency of direct payments for farmers and rural development program projects. Need to pay special attention and give special support to young, family and small farmers.	Development of services and economic base of the municipality with emphasis on the use of the potential of the municipality	ERDF	Local /grassroot level	http://habovka.sk/page.php?id=161
N05: Need to develop a long term vision for the development and stability of rural areas and agriculture with the aim to restore the self-sufficiency. Need to improve transparency of direct payments for farmers and rural development program projects. Need to pay special attention and give special support to young, family and small farmers.	Forest Land Management	EAFRD	National level	http://www.forestportal.sk/lesne-hospodarstvo/hospodarska-uprava-lesov/program-starostlivosti-o-lesy/Stranky/default.aspx
N05: Need to develop a long term vision for the development and stability of rural areas and agriculture with the aim to restore the self-sufficiency. Need to improve transparency of direct payments for farmers and rural development program projects. Need to pay special attention and	Forest Management Program	EAFRD	Local /grassroot level	http://www.forestportal.sk/lesne-hospodarstvo/hospodarska-uprava-lesov/program-starostlivosti-o-lesy/Stranky/default.aspx

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
give special support to young, family and small farmers.				
N05: Need to develop a long term vision for the development and stability of rural areas and agriculture with the aim to restore the self-sufficiency. Need to improve transparency of direct payments for farmers and rural development program projects. Need to pay special attention and give special support to young, family and small farmers.	NGO Christian in Rural Areas	-	Regional level	https://www.facebook.com/krestanNaVidieku/
N08: Need to have sustainable settlements, regions and landscape in the context of climate change, specifically improving access to drinking water, sewerage and clean resources available, sustainable urban development, preventing climate change and, last but not least, protecting terrestrial life.	Rural development program of Slovakia	EAFRD	EU level, Local /grassroot level	https://www.mpsr.sk/rozvoj-vidieka-a-priame-platby-rybne-hospodarstvo/prv-sr-2014-2020/47-43-935
N08: Need to have sustainable settlements, regions and landscape in the context of climate change, specifically improving access to drinking water, sewerage and clean resources available, sustainable urban development, preventing climate change and, last but not least, protecting terrestrial life.	Subsidy schemes / programs in the field of agriculture and rural development	EAFRD	National level	https://www.mpsr.sk/podpory-vyzvy/257
N08: Need to have sustainable settlements, regions and landscape in the context of climate change, specifically improving access to drinking water, sewerage and clean resources available, sustainable urban development, preventing climate change and, last but not least, protecting terrestrial life.	Forest Management Program	EAFRD	Local /grassroot level	http://www.forestportal.sk/lesne-hospodarstvo/hospodarska-uprava-lesov/program-starostlivosti-o-lesy/Stranky/default.aspx
N08: Need to have sustainable settlements, regions and landscape in the context of climate change, specifically improving access to drinking water, sewerage and clean resources available, sustainable urban development, preventing climate change and, last but not least, protecting terrestrial life.	Public policy	EAFRD	National level	https://www.zabiedovo.sk/programy-a-plany.phtml?id3=114182

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/program me/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
N08: Need to have sustainable settlements, regions and landscape in the context of climate change, specifically improving access to drinking water, sewerage and clean resources available, sustainable urban development, preventing climate change and, last but not least, protecting terrestrial life.	Program of Development of the Nitra Self-Governing Region	ERDF, ESF	Regional level	https://www.unsk.sk/zobraz/sekcii/dokumenty-regionalneho-rozvoja
N011: Need to improve the adequacy of housing opportunities in rural areas.	Rural development program of Slovakia	EAFRD	EU level, Local /grassroot level	https://www.mpsr.sk/rozvoj-vidieka-a-priame-platby-rybne-hospodarstvo/prv-sr-2014-2020/47-43-935
N011: Need to improve the adequacy of housing opportunities in rural areas.	Program of economic and social development of the town of Holič for the years 2015-2021.	ERDF, ESF	Local /grassroot level	https://www.holic.sk/index.php/dokumenty-k-stiahnutiu/strategie/finish/37-strategie-dokumenty/6905-program-hospodarskeho-a-socialneho-rozvoja-mesta-holic-na-roky-2015-2021
N011: Need to improve the adequacy of housing opportunities in rural areas.	The economic development program of the municipality of Bolešov supports development projects to improve the possibility of suitable housing in rural areas	ERDF	International level	www.bohelov.sk
N011: Need to improve the adequacy of housing opportunities in rural areas.	Program of Development of the Nitra Self-Governing Region	ERDF	Regional level	https://www.unsk.sk/zobraz/sekcii/dokumenty-regionalneho-rozvoja
N011: Need to improve the adequacy of housing opportunities in rural areas.	Community plan of the village	ERDF, LEADER	Local /grassroot level	www.miklusovce.sk
N11: Need to improve the adequacy of housing opportunities in rural areas.	Program of economic and social development of the village Pataš	ERDF, ESF	Local /grassroot level	www.patas.sk
N011: Need to improve the adequacy of housing opportunities in rural areas.	Development of human resources, development of socio - cultural environment, local patriotism	ERDF, LEADER	Local /grassroot level	http://habovka.sk/page.php?id=161

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
N011: Need to improve the adequacy of housing opportunities in rural areas.	Community life and Services for the local population - OZ KNV in cooperation with municipal councils	-	National level	https://www.facebook.com/kreStanNaVidieku/
N21: Need to improve quality of public services, for example create and support tele-working opportunities, improve the mobility possibilities to the main city and the connections between rural and urban areas, increase good medical (primary attention) services and adequate public support for the provision of e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services, simplify the rules for direct sales of products from farms and restore local market halls and places.	Rural development program of Slovakia	EAFRD	EU level, Local /grassroot level	https://www.mpsr.sk/rozvoj-vidieka-a-priame-platby-rybne-hospodarstvo/prv-sr-2014-2020/47-43-935
N21: Need to improve quality of public services, for example create and support tele-working opportunities, improve the mobility possibilities to the main city and the connections between rural and urban areas, increase good medical (primary attention) services and adequate public support for the provision of e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services, simplify the rules for direct sales of products from farms and restore local market halls and places.	Program of Development of the Nitra Self-Governing Region	ERDF, ESF	Regional level	https://www.unsk.sk/zobraz/sekciu/dokumenty-regionalneho-rozvoja
N21: Need to improve quality of public services, for example create and support tele-working opportunities, improve the mobility possibilities to the main city and the connections between rural and urban areas, increase good medical (primary attention) services and adequate public support for the provision of e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services, simplify the rules for direct sales of products from farms and restore local market halls and places.	Program of economic and social development of the town of Holič for the years 2015-2021. Concept of development of information systems	ERDF, ESF	EU level, Local /grassroot level, regional level, national level	https://www.holic.sk/index.php/dokumenty-k-stiahnutiu/strategicke/finish/37-strategicke-dokumenty/7542-koncepcia-rozvoja-informacnych-systemov-mesta-holic https://www.holic.sk/index.php/dokumenty-k-stiahnutiu/strategicke/finish/37-strategicke-dokumenty/6905-program-hospodarskeho-a-socialneho-rozvoja-mesta-holic-na-roky-2015-2021

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
N21: Need to improve quality of public services, for example create and support tele-working opportunities, improve the mobility possibilities to the main city and the connections between rural and urban areas, increase good medical (primary attention) services and adequate public support for the provision of e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services, simplify the rules for direct sales of products from farms and restore local market halls and places.	Public policy	-	National level	N/A
N21: Need to improve quality of public services, for example create and support tele-working opportunities, improve the mobility possibilities to the main city and the connections between rural and urban areas, increase good medical (primary attention) services and adequate public support for the provision of e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services, simplify the rules for direct sales of products from farms and restore local market halls and places.	The city of Detva does not have a special strategy for this issue, partly the issue is addressed in the Plan of economic and social development of the city and its action plan	ERDF, LEADER	Regional level	https://uradna-tabula.detva.sk/phsr-mesta-detva-na-roky-2015-2023.phtml?id3=121906
N21: Need to improve quality of public services, for example create and support tele-working opportunities, improve the mobility possibilities to the main city and the connections between rural and urban areas, increase good medical (primary attention) services and adequate public support for the provision of e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services, simplify the rules for direct sales of products from farms and restore local market halls and places.	Built and accessible technical and social infrastructure, neat and quality environment	ERDF, LEADER	Local /grassroot level	http://habovka.sk/page.php?id=161
N21: Need to improve quality of public services, for example create and support tele-working opportunities, improve the mobility possibilities to the main city and the connections between rural and urban areas, increase good medical (primary attention) services and adequate public support for the provision of e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services, simplify the rules for direct sales of products from farms and restore local market halls and places.	N/A	-	Local /grassroot level	N/A

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
N21: Need to improve quality of public services, for example create and support tele-working opportunities, improve the mobility possibilities to the main city and the connections between rural and urban areas, increase good medical (primary attention) services and adequate public support for the provision of e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services, simplify the rules for direct sales of products from farms and restore local market halls and places.	N/A	-	Local /grassroot level	N/A
N21: Need to improve quality of public services, for example create and support tele-working opportunities, improve the mobility possibilities to the main city and the connections between rural and urban areas, increase good medical (primary attention) services and adequate public support for the provision of e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services, simplify the rules for direct sales of products from farms and restore local market halls and places.	N/A	-	Local /grassroot level	N/A
N21: Need to improve quality of public services, for example create and support tele-working opportunities, improve the mobility possibilities to the main city and the connections between rural and urban areas, increase good medical (primary attention) services and adequate public support for the provision of e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services, simplify the rules for direct sales of products from farms and restore local market halls and places.	Ministries of Agriculture, Education, Transport, Health in cooperation with associations of towns and municipalities.	-	National level	https://www.facebook.com/krestanNaVidieku/
N21: Need to improve quality of public services, for example create and support tele-working opportunities, improve the mobility possibilities to the main city and the connections between rural and urban areas, increase good medical (primary attention) services and adequate public support for the provision of e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services, simplify the rules for direct sales of products from farms and restore local market halls and places.	N/A	-	National level, regional level	N/A

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
N29: Need to increase the number of sufficiently lively communities in the area and citizen-driven local activities and need to promote local organizations promoting regional specialties, crafts, traditions.	Program of economic and social development of the town of Holíč for the years 2015-2021. Concept of development of information systems	ERDF, ESF	EU level, Local /grassroot level, regional level, national level	https://www.holic.sk/index.php/dokumenty-k-stiahnutiu/strategicke/finish/37-strategicke-dokumenty/7542-koncepcia-rozvoja-informacnych-systemov-mesta-holic https://www.holic.sk/index.php/dokumenty-k-stiahnutiu/strategicke/finish/37-strategicke-dokumenty/6905-program-hospodarskeho-a-socialneho-rozvoja-mesta-holic-na-roky-2015-2021
N29: Need to increase the number of sufficiently lively communities in the area and citizen-driven local activities and need to promote local organizations promoting regional specialties, crafts, traditions.	Economic development program of the village Bohelov	ERDF	Local /grassroot level, Regional level	www.bohelov.sk
N29: Need to increase the number of sufficiently lively communities in the area and citizen-driven local activities and need to promote local organizations promoting regional specialties, crafts, traditions.	N/A	-	N/A	N/A

3.8 Pilot 8 Häme, Finland

3.8.1 Description of respective governance structures

Finland is a sparsely populated country with rural characteristics. The rural areas are diversified, and the countryside does not fit to a single, clear-cut definition. In national level rural areas cover 95 % of the country, 1,6 million people live in rural areas, 40 % of all companies in Finland are in rural areas and average population density is 18,01 persons/km².

⁷⁷ Making good rural policy requires the recognition of the diversity of rural areas.

In 2013, Finland completed a new **Urban-Rural Classification** (figure 9), which is based on spatial data sets. Instead of administrative boundaries, the country in this system is divided into areas that are better suitable for policy purposes and spatial analyses. There are two main categories and altogether seven classes. Urban areas are formed from three subclasses, ie 1) inner, 2) outer and 3) peri-urban areas, while rural areas consist of four subclasses, ie 4) local centres in rural areas, 5) rural areas close to urban areas, 6) rural heartland areas and 7)

⁷⁷ Rural policy in Finland. <https://www.ruralpolicy.fi/>

sparsely populated rural areas. Häme Pilot region locates in southern part of Finland and most of the region is classified as rural area close to urban area.⁷⁸

Figure 9. In urban-rural classification system areas are divided into seven classes from the most densely populated areas to sparsely populated rural areas. Classification is used in directing rural development programme. Source: Finnish Environment Institute.

In a country with vast rural areas, a systematic rural policy is needed. In Finland, rural policy consists of national rural policy linked to regional policy and EU co-funded rural development. Finnish rural policy can be divided into a broad and narrow rural policy.

- *The broad rural policy* is a practice according to which the rural areas and their residents should be considered in all actions in the society and different administrative branches.

⁷⁸ Urban-Rural Classification system. Finnish Environment Institute. Joint website for Finnish Environment Administration. Environment.fi. https://www.ymparisto.fi/en-US/Living_environment_and_planning/Community_structure/Information_about_the_community_structure/Urbanrural_classification

- *The narrow rural policy* means operational level of the policy, the practical instruments employed by the government and society to develop the countryside – such as project funding for rural development.⁷⁹

Figure 10. Administration of rural policy in Finland. (Source: MMM – Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry AKIS report)

Administration of rural policy in Finland is described in figure 10. **Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry** is the managing authority for EAFRD in Finland. The ministry is responsible for the preparation of the Rural Development Programmes, planning of measures, legislation, financing and allocation of fund to be used in the regions.^{80, 81}

The rural policy is coordinated by the **Rural Policy Council**, appointed by the Finnish government for the term 1 May 2016–31 December 2020. The Council consists of 35 members, representing all policy areas pertaining to everyday rural life and entrepreneurship. Among the tasks of the Rural Policy Council is to improve the structures and practices of rural policy and rural development work based on networks and partnerships and in a way that supports a location-based policy.⁶²

⁷⁹ Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry of Finland. <https://mmm.fi/en/rural-policy>

⁸⁰ Rural network webpage. <https://www.maaseutu.fi/en/the-rural-network/rural-development-program/managing-authorities>

⁸¹ Lehto D. (2014): AKIS and advisory services in the Republic of Finland. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the PRO AKIS project. Online resource: https://430a.uni-hohenheim.de/fileadmin/einrichtungen/430a/PRO_AKIS/Country_Reports/Country_Report_Finland_05_06_14.pdf

The Finnish Food Authority was founded in 2019 by combining three government organizations. Among other tasks it is responsible for the use of the funds provided by the European Union's agricultural guarantee and rural development funds in Finland, operates as the EU's paying agency and monitors the implementation of EU and national grants. In addition, this authority develops and maintains the information systems used in rural business administration, develops online services, maintains and develops the registers used in the field, and produces information management services for other public authorities.⁸²

Rural Network Support Unit of Finland maintains and further develops the activity of the Rural Network. The tasks include convening the networks, promoting internationalization, organization of events and training, communication, and compilation and dissemination of good practices.⁶⁴

There are 15 **Centres for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment (ELY-Centre)** in Finland. Together with the six Regional State Administrative Agencies they function as the country's regional state administrative authorities. ELY Centres finance investments of farms and other enterprises, non-productive investments and development projects in the respective regions. In Häme pilot region responsible authority is Häme ELY Centre and it covers both Päijät-Häme and Kanta-Häme regions.⁶⁴

Regional councils (19 in Finland) are joint municipal authorities in charge of regional development, regional land use planning and promoting regional interests. Häme Pilot region covers the area of **Regional Council of Häme** and **Regional Council of Päijät-Häme**.^{83, 84}

Leader groups finance projects and investments of enterprises in line with the local development strategies. Five Leader groups are operating in Häme pilot region.⁸⁵

Local government authorities consider applications for environment payment commitments, natural handicap payments and animal welfare payments. In total Häme pilot region has 20 municipalities, of which 11 are located in Kanta-Häme and 9 in Päijät-Häme.

Häme pilot region has two **regional village associations** (Hämeen kylät ry and Päijät-Hämeen kylät ry). Regional village associations are non-profit association of villages and they e.g. implement policies to promote rural areas vitality, provide expert statements to authorities, work in collaboration with the Suomen Kylät ry (Finnish Villages Associations) provide training and education to local volunteers and stakeholders and implement projects EU, EAFRD, and national initiatives. In Häme there are about 240 villages and most of them have **village association**.^{86, 87}

⁸² Finnish Food Authority. <https://www.ruokavirasto.fi/en/about-us/what-is-the-finnish-food-authority/>

⁸³ Regional Council of Häme. <https://www.hameenliitto.fi/>

⁸⁴ Regional Council of Päijät-Häme: <https://paijat-hame.fi/>

⁸⁵ Häme Leader. <http://www.leaderhame.fi/leader-ryhmat/>

⁸⁶ Hämeen kylät ry. <https://www.hameenkylat.fi/>

⁸⁷ Päijät-Hämeen kylät ry. <https://www.phkylat.fi/>

Development of rural policy in Finland started in the 1970's to try to manage big structural changes that took place in 1960-70's (figure 4). Village activities were promoted, and rural areas became a focus of research. In 1980's first national rural development project was launched, and first village associations were founded. During EU-era, starting from 1995, there has been 5 consecutive rural policy committees and rural policy programmes. The 6th rural policy programme 2016-2020 is led by Rural Policy Council and the minister in charge of rural policy. The 7th Rural Policy Programme is being prepared and will start in 2021. Key themes are place-based policy and sustainable development.⁸⁸

Figure 3. Historical perspective into development of the national rural policy in Finland. The need for a national rural policy was launched by big structural changes in 1960's and 70's. The national Rural Policy is bound both to the Regional Policy and the EU Rural and Regional Policy (since 1995).¹⁰

3.8.2 Mission statement and the needs of pilot regions

Mission statement for Häme pilot is:

The pilot will use PoliRural results to boost the region's attractiveness by introducing business-friendly policies that can encourage new entrepreneurs to create products and services on circular economy and well-being, which in the future may become a significant source of employment.

In preceding regional needs gathering phase of PoliRural project (the results presented in D4.2), 21 needs were recognized in Häme pilot region. The needs were ranked according to their relevance to Häme pilot mission statement in co-operation with Häme stakeholder panel and PoliRural partners HAMK and S&L. Six most relevant needs were selected for policy

⁸⁸ The national rural policy of Finland. <https://www.slideshare.net/Maaseutupolitiikka/the-national-rural-policy-of-finland>

mapping exercise. The code “NX” refers to needs gathering in previous PoliRural deliverable D4.2 *Grassroot needs and factors of rural attractiveness*.

Needs selected for policy evaluation are:

- Supporting multi-locality in living and working. (N07)
- Supporting new business opportunities in farms and rural areas (N12)
- More emphasis on education and RDI to circular economy solutions in the field of bioeconomy (N20)
- Need to make it easier for newcomers to get adopted into the community. (N16)
- Inventing ways to get young people to live and work in Häme region. (N09)
- To improve and secure accessibility of public services in rural areas. (N01)

3.8.3 Matching needs with policy measures in needs-policy canvas

The matching process was made in collaboration with regional stakeholder panel and policy makers. Because of the COVID19 restrictions starting from March 2020, face-to-face meetings with stakeholders were not possible. Häme pilot needs and corresponding policies were discussed with regional stakeholder panel in online workshop and online meetings (table 13). Workshop was organised on 6th May 2020 through Teams platform. There were 20 participants and interactive collaboration was made through Padlet application (figure 11). The assignments in the workshop were: better definition for each need, how the needs are addressed in current policies and programmes and how they should be addressed in the future. The results of policy mapping in Häme pilot region are listed to table 14.

Table 15. Communication with policy makers and stakeholders in Häme.

Date	Topic of the meeting	Type of the meeting (face-to-face, online, workshop)	Target group	Number of attendees
6/5/2020	Matching needs with corresponding policies	Online meeting via Teams (online workshop)	Stakeholder panel	20

Figure 11. The results of a PoliRural online workshop in Häme pilot region dealing with needs and matching interventions and policies.

Table 16. Needs-Policy Canvas, Häme, Finland

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
N07 Supporting multi-locality in living and working.	Regional plan of Päijät-Häme 2014 (Päijät-Hämeen maakuntakaava 2014, selostus)	-	Regional level	https://paijat-hame.fi/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/maka2014_SELOSTUS_20190514.pdf
	Regional plan of Kanta-Häme 2040 (Kanta-Hämeen maakuntakaava 2040)	-	Regional level	https://www.hameenliitto.fi/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/oas_2040_nettiin_27_6_2019.pdf , https://www.hameenliitto.fi/alueide nkaytto-ja-saavutettavuus/aluasuunnittelu/maakuntakaava-2040/
	Häme 2018+ program	ERDF, ESF	Regional level	https://www.hameenliitto.fi/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Hame-ohjelma_2018.pdf
	Land Use and Construction law (Maankäyttö- ja rakennuslaki)	-	National level	https://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/ajantasa/1999/19990132#L27
	A Countryside of Opportunities - National Rural Policy Programme 2014-2020	EAFRD, ESF	National level	https://tem.fi/documents/1410877/2859687/Mahdollisuuksien+maaseutu+25022014.pdf

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
	Regional strategy of Päijät-Häme 2018-2021	ERDF, ESF	Regional level	https://paijat-hame.fi/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Maakuntastrategia_ja_ohjelma_2018-2021_nettiin.pdf
	Rural development programme for southern Päijät-Häme region (Leader)	EAFRD	Local /grassroot level	http://www.etpaha.fi/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/Etel%C3%A4isen-P%C3%A4ij%C3%A4t-H%C3%A4meen-maaseudun-kehitt%C3%A4misohjelma-2014-2020.pdf
	Municipal building code	-	Local /grassroot level	E.g. Hartola municipality (http://www.hartola.fi/liitteet/Asuminen_ja_ymparisto/rakennusvalvonta/rakennusjarjestys.pdf)
N12 Supporting new business opportunities in farms and rural areas.	Green Growth Häme-Regional Rural Plan 2014-2020	EAFRD	Regional level	https://www.doria.fi/handle/10024/93521
	The Government's entrepreneurship strategy	-	National level	file:///C:/Users/slento/Downloads/Yritt%C3%A4jyysstrategia%20LUONNOS%20versio%209.3.2020%2003.pdf
	Regional strategy of Päijät-Häme 2018-2021	ERDF, ESF	Regional level	https://paijat-hame.fi/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Maakuntastrategia_ja_ohjelma_2018-2021_nettiin.pdf
	Häme 2018+ program	ERDF, ESF	Regional level	https://www.hameenliitto.fi/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Hame-ohjelma_2018.pdf
	EMO ry Leader strategy 2014-2020	EAFRD	Local /grassroot level	https://www.emory.fi/uploads/materialit/emo%20leader-strategia%202014-2020.pdf
	Lounaplussa ry development strategy 2014-2020 (Leader group)	EAFRD	Local /grassroot level	http://lounaplussa.fi/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/1430386899_LounaPlussan_kehittamisohjelma_2014_2020_lopullinen_hakemus_100614.pdf
	Rural development programme for southern Päijät-Häme region (Leader group)	EAFRD	Local /grassroot level	http://www.etpaha.fi/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/Etel%C3%A4isen-P%C3%A4ij%C3%A4t-H%C3%A4meen-maaseudun-kehitt%C3%A4misohjelma-2014-2020.pdf
	Local time - Local development strategy in	EAFRD	Local /grassroot level	https://www.linnaseutu.fi/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/STRATEGIA_UUSIN_112016_2017.pdf

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
	Hämeenlinna region for 2014-2020			
	Together - Strategy for Päijänne-Leader group 2014-2020	EAFRD	Local /grassroot level	https://www.paijanne-leader.fi/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/paijanneleader2014_strategia.pdf
N20 More emphasis on education and RDI to circular economy solutions in the field of bioeconomy (from field to field).	National Implementation Plan for the 2030 Agenda	-	National level	https://kestavakehitys.fi/documents/2167391/2186383/A2030+implementation+in+Finland+ONEPAGER+13.9.2016+FINAL.pdf/62b5efbc-294e-49e3-904a-9ae546bce2cc/A2030+implementation+in+Finland+ONEPAGER+13.9.2016+FINAL.pdf
	Sustainable growth from bioeconomy THE FINNISH BIOECONOMY STRATEGY	EAFRD, ERDF	National level	http://biotalous.fi/wp-content/uploads/2014/08/The_Finnish_Bioeconomy_Strategy_11062014_1.pdf
	Sustainable growth and jobs 2014 - 2020 - Finland's structural funds programme (ERDF)	ERDF, ESF	National level	http://www.rakennerahastot.fi/web/en/programme_for_sustainable_growth_and_jobs
	Green Growth Häme-Regional Rural Plan 2014-2020	EAFRD	Regional level	https://www.doria.fi/handle/10024/93521
	Regional strategy of Päijät-Häme 2018-2021	ERDF, ESF	Regional level	https://paijat-hame.fi/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Maakunta_strategia_ja_ohjelma_2018-2021_nettiin.pdf
	Häme 2018+ program	ERDF, ESF	Regional level	https://www.hameenliitto.fi/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Hame-ohjelma_2018.pdf
	Lounapussan ry development strategy 2014-2020 (Leader group)	EAFRD	Local /grassroot level	http://lounaplussa.fi/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/1430386899_LounaPlussan_kehittamisohjelma_2014_2020_lopullinen_hakemus_100614.pdf
	Circular economy roadmap for Kanta-Häme region	ERDF	Regional level	https://www.hamk.fi/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Kanta-H%C3%A4meen-kiertotalouden-nykytilan-kuvaus.pdf
	The Päijät-Häme Bio-based Circular Economy Action Plan	ERDF	Regional level	https://www.interregeurope.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/tx_tevprojects/library/file_1559896937.pdf

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
	Frush event - for start-ups in circular economy	-	Local /grassroot level	https://www.facebook.com/pg/FRUSH30100/about/?ref=page_internal
N16 Need to make it easier for newcomers to get adopted into the community.	Green Growth Häme-Regional Rural Plan 2014-2020	EAFRD	Regional level	https://www.doria.fi/handle/10024/93521
	Häme 2018+ program	ERDF, ESF	Regional level	https://www.hameenliitto.fi/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Hame-ohjelma_2018.pdf
	Lounaplussa ry development strategy 2014-2020 (Leader group)	EAFRD	Local /grassroot level	http://lounaplussa.fi/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/1430386899_LounaPlussan_kehittamisohjelma_2014_2020_lopullinen_hakemus_100614.pdf
	Local time - Local development strategy in Hämeenlinna region for 2014-2020	EAFRD	Local /grassroot level	https://www.linnaseutu.fi/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/STRATEGIA_UUSIN_112016_2017.pdf
	Strengthening villages - Strengthening communities: National Program for Local Development 2014 - 2020	EAFRD	National level	https://suomenkylat.fi/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/Paikallisen_kehitt%C3%A4misenohjelma20142020.pdf
	Rural development programme for southern Päijät-Häme region (Leader group)	EAFRD	Local /grassroot level	http://www.etpaha.fi/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/Etel%C3%A4isen-P%C3%A4ij%C3%A4t-H%C3%A4meen-maaseudun-kehitt%C3%A4misenohjelma-2014-2020.pdf
N09 Inventing ways to get young people to live and work in Häme region.	Häme 2018+ program	ERDF, ESF	Regional level	https://www.hameenliitto.fi/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Hame-ohjelma_2018.pdf
	Green Growth Häme-Regional Rural Plan 2014-2020	EAFRD	Regional level	https://www.doria.fi/handle/10024/93521
	EMO ry Leader strategy 2014-2020	EAFRD	Local /grassroot level	https://www.emory.fi/uploads/media/emo%20leader-strategia%202014-2020.pdf
	Regional strategy of Päijät-Häme 2018-2021	ERDF, ESF	Regional level	https://paijat-hame.fi/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Maakunta_strategia_ja_ohjelma_2018-2021_nettiin.pdf

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
	Together - Strategy for Päijänne-Leader group 2014-2020	EAFRD	Local /grassroot level	https://www.paijanne-leader.fi/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/paijanneleader2014_strategia.pdf
N01 To improve and secure accessibility of public services in rural areas.	Regional strategy of Päijät-Häme 2018-2021	ERDF, ESF	Regional level	https://paijat-hame.fi/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Maakuntastrategia_ja_ohjelma_2018-2021_nettiin.pdf
	Green Growth Häme-Regional Rural Plan 2014-2020	EAFRD	Regional level	https://www.doria.fi/handle/10024/93521
	Häme 2018+ program	ERDF, ESF	Regional level	https://www.hameenliitto.fi/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Hame-ohjelma_2018.pdf
	EMO ry Leader strategy 2014-2020	EAFRD	Local /grassroot level	https://www.emory.fi/uploads/materiaalit/emo%20leader-strategia%202014-2020.pdf
	Mannerheim League for Child Welfare Häme district action plan 2020	-	Local /grassroot level	https://hameenpiiri.mll.fi/ https://bin.yhdistysavain.fi/1558502/4URcldrDOiL4j48QaG00SvV3D/Toimintasuunnitelma_2020.pdf

3.9 Pilot 9 Central Greece, Greece

3.9.1 Description of respective governance structures

Greece covers an area of 132 049 km², of which 62.6 % is predominantly rural and where 31.9% of the population live. The percentage of rural population has been decreasing since the 1960s and in the 1990s rural population was less than one third of the total population⁸⁹. The agricultural sector in Greece is characterised by one of the highest proportions of small-scale family farms in Europe. Over half of the country's 709.500 agricultural holdings have less than 2 hectares and the small and fragmented land parcels constitute one of the main characteristics of Greek agriculture. The average age of farmers is higher than in most European countries while, at the same time, their education is lower. The lack of a skilled workforce is a barrier to growth for farms. Only 5.2% of farm managers are less than 35 years old and merely 5.5% of all farm managers have agricultural training. The indicator measuring the standard of living of farmers stands at 80% of the standard of living of persons employed in other sectors. Agriculture contributes 4.3% of the Greek Gross Value Added (2018) of the

⁸⁹ <http://enrd.ec.europa.eu/enrd-static/fms/pdf/BC9DBA4E-FD9F-AC8F-E72D-B5C0CAE18C17.pdf>

country. In terms of employment, agriculture accounts for 12% and the agri-food sector for 4% of the total. The economic importance of the sector is therefore significant and enhancing its competitiveness by overcoming its structural, environmental and climatic limitations remains a key challenge. Areas with natural constraints make up 70.75% of the Utilized Agricultural Area (UAA), of which 44.19% is mountainous regions. Forests make up 50% of the total land area of the country and organic farming covers 3.8% of the UAA. Irrigated land accounts for 19.8% of the UAA and 86% of water use in Greece is consumed in agriculture, often with considerable water losses. Greece's unemployment rate is 16.6% (2019) and lies above the EU average⁹⁰.

In Greece the AKIS is highly fragmented and ineffective. Decentralisation and the financial crisis, which implies the further downsizing of the state, resulted in a tripartite extension structure: the headquarters of MRDF (including the Dir. of Extension), isolated from the lower levels; regional and sub-regional services under the Ministry of Interior; and, local offices under the Municipalities. Although the tasks of all the sub-national levels emanate from MRDF, such a structure, along with the breakaway of research and (farmers') training from the Ministry into semi-autonomous organisations has led, at best, to extremely weak linkages and thus coordination and cooperation among the main public AKIS components.⁹¹

In Greece the main AKIS actors can be depicted according to the (administrative) level of operation: national, regional and local.

- At the national level the main actors are: the Ministry of Rural Development and Food (MRDF/ ex-Ministry of Agriculture), ELGO DIMITRA (incorporating the ex-semi-autonomous organisations NAGREF, OGEEKA, AGROCERT and ELOGAK2), Higher Education Institutes (HEIs) , private companies (branches of transnational companies) and PASEGES (Pan-Hellenic Confederation of Unions of Agricultural Co-operatives).
- At the regional level the main actor is the regional Directory of Agricultural Economy and at the sub-regional (ex-Prefectural) level, the Directorate of Agricultural Economy & Veterinary and local Development Agencies; NAGREF and OGEEKA DIMITRA also operate institutes and research stations, and local farmers' training centres (KEGE), respectively, at this level. Unions of Cooperatives (PASEGES branches) are also found at regional or sub-regional level. Finally, private consultants-agronomists and private input shops (run by agronomists) are found usually at sub-regional/ex-prefectural level.

⁹⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/food-farming-fisheries/key_policies/documents/rdp-factsheet-greece_en.pdf

⁹¹ Koutsouris, A. (2014): AKIS and advisory services in Greece. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the PRO AKIS project. Online resource: https://430a.uni-hohenheim.de/fileadmin/einrichtungen/430a/PRO_AKIS/Country_Reports/Country_Report_Greece_03_06_14.pdf

- At the local (municipality) level the main actors are: The Municipal Agricultural Production Offices (ex-Agricultural Extension/Rural Development Offices), local cooperatives (Coops Union branches) and, of course, individual farmers.

In Greece there is actually neither a national policy framework nor a coordination mechanism or agreements between the aforementioned AKIS actors. Indeed, it is a common understanding that, despite rhetoric and marginal, fragmented actions, MRDF has long since ceased to put together an overall national strategy for agriculture and rural development; instead MRDF rather plays the role of an intermediary transferring and controlling the implementation of EU policies (CAP Regulations and relevant financial resources/subsidies) in the country.

On the other hand, during the last 25 years, in the name of the downsizing of the state, decentralization (Decentralisation Laws I-Kapodistrias and II-Kallikratis; see below), and lately the economic crisis, the previously existing structures under one authority (from the national to the sub-regional to the local level), i.e. the Ministry of Agriculture, have become (semi)autonomous and/or transferred under new administrative structures/authorities (e.g. the Ministry of Interior; see below). As a result, nowadays, the overall picture is that of a highly fragmented, uncoordinated and dysfunctional AKIS.

Figure 12. AKIS diagram for Greece.

Table 17. Overview of organisations creating the AKIS

Status of the organisation	Type of organisation	Public funds			Farmers			Private	NGO
		EU funds	National funds	Regional funds	Farmers' levies	Farmers' contribution	Billing services	Other products (inputs, outputs)	Foundation
Public sector	Advisory department of the Ministry of agriculture	X	X						
	Local/regional agencies	X	X						
	Other (specify)								
Research and Education	University	X	X						
	Research Institute								X
	Other education bodies (specify)								
Private sector	Upstream industries							X	
	Downstream industries							X	
	Independent consultant						X		
	Private agricultural advice company						X		
	Farmers' owned advice company								
	Other (specify)								
Farmer based organizations	Farmers' cooperative	X	X			X			
	Chambers of agriculture								
	Farmers' circles/groups	X				X			

Status of the organisation	Type of organisation	Public funds			Farmers			Private	NGO
	Other								
NGO									

3.9.2 Mission statement and the needs of pilot regions

The Greek Pilot's Mission was agreed to be:

Demonstration of new interventions that improve training opportunities and digital skills, facilitate the adoption of new farm management practices (e.g. smart farming), develop social capital between newcomers and local populations, and facilitate access of the many of region's resources (e.g. infrastructure, funding and financing).

The mission of the pilot will address several of the identified needs in multiple ways. Digitalization will attract young people to rural areas and facilitate the modernization of business structures in the agri-food sector, allowing the improvement of existing infrastructures.

The top 6 ranked needs are the following:

1. Increase of population especially young people
2. Provide more training opportunities (e.g. seminars, e-learning courses, Lifelong learning training). Lack of educational and consulting services for gaining digital and technological skills in agriculture. Increase funding to educational and research institutions and structures.
3. Support of start-up business and motivate young people to inhabit region
4. Guarantee of an adequate access to internet in remote areas and increase the number of free access hot-spots in public places (in ports, schools, sports/recreation areas, churches, etc.)
5. Improve public transportation and accessibility between remote areas within the region.
6. Increase initiatives and organized actions for promotion (publicity, marketing activities and projects, agritourism) and effective exploitation of high natural and historical value areas.

3.9.3 Matching needs with policy measures in Needs-Policy Canvas

There are not existing policies directly addressing the need N01("Increase of population especially young people"), however there is a number of policies which affecting indirectly the particular need. Specifically, policies regarding start-up businesses (N03), training

opportunities (N02) and Internet accessibility(N04) could affect significantly the population of young people.

Table 18. Needs-Policy canvas, Central Greece

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/program me/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
N01 Increase of population especially young people	-	-	-	-
N02 Provide more training opportunities (e.g. seminars, e-learning courses, Lifelong learning training). Lack of educational and consulting services for gaining digital and technological skills in agriculture. Increase funding to educational and research institutions and structures.	ERECTION OF MUSIC SCHOOL OF CHALKIDA	ERDF	Regional level	http://anaptyxi.gov.gr/ErgoPopup?mis=5021484 There are other 10 similar projects concerning the construction of infrastructure, mainly schools
	Construction of a multipurpose hall at the 2nd Primary School of Aliartou of the Municipality of Aliartou - Thespieon	ERDF	Regional level	http://anaptyxi.gov.gr/ErgoPopup?mis=5002018
	PRACTICAL TRAINING of university students of Central Greece	ERDF	Regional level	http://anaptyxi.gov.gr/ErgoPopup?mis=5032775
N03 Support of startup business and motivate young people to inhabit region	START UP ENTREPRENEURSHIP - A**** D****	ERDF	Regional level	http://anaptyxi.gov.gr/ErgoPopup?mis=5021570 20 more similar individual start-ups
	START UP ENTREPRENEURSHIP - NOMADPRODUCTIONS I.K.E	ERDF	Regional level	http://anaptyxi.gov.gr/ErgoPopup?mis=5023488
	Strengthening of Self-Employment of Higher Education Graduates II. G.Z*** A.P***	ERDF	Regional level	http://anaptyxi.gov.gr/ErgoPopup?mis=5042434 175 more similar start-ups
	Strengthening of Self-Employment of Higher Education Graduates G*** S***	ERDF	Regional level	http://anaptyxi.gov.gr/ErgoPopup?mis=5028757 176 similar start-ups
	OAED: Companies Subsidy Action for 30-49 age	ERDF	Regional level	http://anaptyxi.gov.gr/ErgoPopup?mis=5015257 200 similar funded schemes

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
	Programme for the subsidy of companies for the employment of 1.295 young unemployed aged 25-29	ESF (https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1176&langId=en)	Regional level	http://anaptyxi.gov.gr/ErgoPopup?mis=5033439 4 more similar funded schemes
	OAED: Programme for the subsidy of companies for the employment of 1.459 young unemployed aged 18-24	ESF (https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1176&langId=en)	Regional level	http://anaptyxi.gov.gr/ErgoPopup?mis=5041584 3 more similar funded schemes
N04 Guarantee of an adequate access to internet in remote areas and increase the number of free access hot-spots in public places (in ports, schools, sports/recreation areas, churches, etc.)	Digital convergence: The programme "Digital Convergence" involves Community support for Greek regions that are eligible under the Convergence objective	EU Investment & National Public Contribution	National level	https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/atlas/programmes/2007-2013/greece/operational-programme-digital-convergence
	Construction of Lamia - Xiniada section of the Central Greece Motorway (E65)	CF	Regional level	http://anaptyxi.gov.gr/en-us/PROJECTS-GRANTS# https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/projects/Greece/lamia-xyniada-section-of-central-greece-motorway-under-construction
N05 Improve public transportation and accessibility between remote areas within the region	REHABILITATION CONSTRUCTION WORKS ALONG THE LAMIA-KARPENISI NATIONAL ROAD, TO THE ROAD SECTION STARTING FROM THE KASTRI GATE TO THE MAKRAKOMI GATE, PHASE B'.	CF	Regional level	http://anaptyxi.gov.gr/ErgoPopup?mis=5001297
	CONSTRUCTION OF ROAD CONNECTING NATIONAL ROAD WITH GLYFA'S FERRY, FROM KILOMETRIC POSITION: 8+120 TO KILOMETRIC POSITION: 11+627,05	ERDF	Regional level	http://anaptyxi.gov.gr/ErgoPopup?mis=5000307

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/program/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
	Improvement of Lamia Road - Itea - Antirrio, Section: End of Gravia Bypass - Bauxite Mine intersection	ERDF	Regional level	http://anaptyxi.gov.gr/en-us/PROJECTS-GRANTS# https://anaptyxi.gov.gr/ErgoPopup?mis=5021489
N06 Increase initiatives and organized actions for promotion (publicity, marketing activities and projects, agritourism) and effective exploitation of high natural and historical value areas.	Information and Publicity of PEP Regional Greece 2014-2020	ERDF	Regional level	http://anaptyxi.gov.gr/ErgoPopup?mis=5000330
	PUBLICITY ESF:DIMOSIOTIT A PROBOLI KAI PLIROFORISI EKT	ERDF	Regional level	http://anaptyxi.gov.gr/Subject?mis=5000592&aa=1
	CONSULTING SUPPORT FOR ESF	ESF	Regional level	http://anaptyxi.gov.gr/ErgoPopup?mis=5000539

3.10 Pilot 10 Apulia, Italy

3.10.1 Description of respective governance structures

Apulia is the easternmost region of all Italy and is located in the South and is the eighth region by demographic size. It borders Molise to the north-west and Campania and Basilicata to the west and is bathed by the Adriatic Sea to the east and north and by the Ionian Sea to the south. The local institutional set-up comprises 6 provinces and 258 municipalities. The resident population is 4,029,053 inhabitants with a population density of 206.2 inhabitants/sq. Km⁹². In recent years the resident population has experienced a significant decrease.

Apulian agriculture is characterized by a strong variety of production situations. Apulia is one of the Italian regions with the most hectares of utilized agricultural area (UAA), equal to 65.8% of the overall regional area and 10.2% of the national UAA⁹³. The food sector has always been one of the strongest areas of the Apulian economy. Apulia's key resource is the richness of its raw materials: its fruit, vegetables and cereals, favoured by the Mediterranean climate, are

⁹² <http://dati.istat.it/Index.aspx?QueryId=18550>

⁹³ <https://www.crea.gov.it/>

grown in a range of crop types and varieties throughout the region for most of the year. One of the strategies has been the development of the “Prodotti di Qualità Puglia” label, an umbrella label uniting a range of different product categories and specific types, including many recognised with certifications of origin (DOC, DOCG, IGP, STG) and others without designation. Furthermore, there are extremely varied and diversified "rural systems" which are characterized by the presence of a multiplicity and variety of resources that make them unique. In support of this, the rural development program for the 2014-2020 period included the enhancement of forest areas, the conversion of agricultural land into organic crops and compliance by the beneficiaries of the measures with commitments to improve the agro-environmental-environmental conditions of the territory. It is the main programming tool - both in terms of opportunities and financial resources - to increase the competitiveness of the agricultural entrepreneurial system, support growth, improve living conditions, safeguard the environment of rural areas. In the agricultural context, the Agricultural Development Services (SSA) operate which perform functions such as the promotion of research and experimentation in agriculture and the transfer of results to the agricultural entrepreneurs.

The Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System in Apulia (AKIS) is characterized by the presence on the territory of numerous institutions and qualified subjects, public and private, engaged in research and technological development, dissemination, consultancy and training in the agricultural sector and the agri-food sector. These actors present themselves as a mosaic of subjects and actions that are poorly integrated at a territorial level and, often, far from the productive world. The topics on which research projects have focused in recent years range from those more closely related to company production cycles to transversal subjects, with a prevalence of projects on issues relating to agricultural production, quality and transformation. However, it is noted that the production of innovations directly applicable and usable by agricultural entrepreneurs is very limited and, again, how it is not widespread among entrepreneurs agricultural and forestry awareness on the real strategy and importance linked to the introduction of innovations in the company. Research bodies have activated a dense network of international collaborations with prestigious institutions.

The current governance structures and institutions that make/influence policies on rural development in Apulia are summarised in table 17.

Table 19. Governance structures related to rural policy and rural development in Apulia

Status of organisation	Type of organisation	Organisation
Public sector	National Government	Ministry of Economy and Finance Ministry of Economic Development Ministry of Education Ministry of University and Research Ministry of Labour and Social Policies

Status of organisation	Type of organisation	Organisation
		Ministry of Agricultural, Food and Forestry Policies Ministry of the Environment and Protection of the Territory and the Sea
	Government Agencies	Institute of Services for the Agricultural Food Market (ISMEA) Agricultural Disbursement Agency (AgEA)
	Local/regional agencies	Regional Agency for Irrigation and Forestry Activities (ARIF) Regional Agency for Prevention and the Environment (ARPA)
Research and Education	Vocational/ Further Education	Agricultural technical institutes
	Universities & Higher Education Institutes	University of Bari University of Foggia University of Salento
	Research Institutes & Foundations	National Institute of Statistics (ISTAT) Council for Agricultural Research and Agricultural Economy Analysis (CREA) Higher Institute for Environmental Promotion and Research (ISPRA) National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development (ENEA)
Private sector	Private agricultural, entrepreneurial consultants	Numerous private actors
	Cooperatives	Numerous cooperatives ⁹⁴
	Others	23 Local Action Group (LAGs)
Farmer based Organisations & NGOs	Land manager representative bodies	Confagricoltura Coldiretti Cia

Rural Development in Apulia is managed nationally through one Rural Development Programme (RDP), funded under the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national contributions. For this reason, we make use of participatory local development (community-led local development, CLLD) called L.E.A.D.E.R which is the most important and innovative tool of Community policies for integrated and sustainable local development of rural areas. LEADER, which stands for *Liaison Entrée Actions de Développement de l'Économie Rural* (the link between rural economic development actions), is based on the so-called "bottom-up" approach and focuses on LAGs (local action groups) formed by a public partnership -private that has the task of developing and implementing a pilot, innovative, multisectoral and integrated development strategy at the local level (SSL - Local Development Strategy). Rural development policy requires Member States or Regions to prepare programs multi-year (RDP) according to the needs of their rural areas.

⁹⁴ <http://dati.mise.gov.it/index.php/lista-cooperativo/list/1>

From this point of view, there is big news in the 2014-2020 programming compared to the 2007-2013 programming: A Member State (Art. 6 Reg. 1305/2013) can present a single one National program for the whole of its territory or a series of regional Programs. Based on the agreement on the allocation of funds, signed on January 16, 2014, by the Conference State-Regions, 21 Rural Development Programs have been developed in Italy at the level of Regions and Autonomous Provinces and a National Program for four measures deemed strategic⁹⁵:

- a) risk management, provides mechanisms and strategies that make the intervention applicable throughout the national territory, including through the activation of a "Mutual Fund" and income support measures in the event of a crisis.
- b) animal biodiversity, which allows financing the national program for the management of the Herd Books and the genetic improvement. The reorganization of the breeding system must respect the principle of separation between the biodiversity improvement activities, placed at the national charge, from those of consultancy to be activated at the regional level.
- c) irrigation infrastructure, which is taking a noticeable amount relevance following the frequent excesses of rain or water scarcity (drought) that are repeatedly affecting Italian agriculture. The measure provides for interventions connected to irrigation structures and not to environmental remediation in the sense on the other hand, as these interventions cannot be charged to the agricultural sector.
- d) National rural network.

Compared to the 2007-2013 programming, the menu of measures of the new development policy rural was simplified. It went from 40 to 20 measures, with broader definitions of the past and greater autonomy of choice granted to the Member States within the single measure:

- Measure 1: knowledge transfer and information actions, visits to farms and forests.
- Measure 2: consulting, replacement and farm management assistance services.
- Measure 3: agricultural and food quality schemes.
- Measure 4: investments in physical assets.
- Measure 5: agricultural potential restructuring damaged by natural disasters, climate adversity and prevention actions.
- Measure 6: development of farms and businesses.
- Measure 7: basic services and village renewal in rural areas.
- Measure 8: investments in forestry technologies and in the transformation, mobilization and marketing of forest products.
- Measure 8.1: forestation and afforestation.
- Measure 8.2: setting up of agroforestry systems.

⁹⁵ 4th Report of AKIS - <https://scar-europe.org/index.php/akis-documents> .

- Measure 8.4: prevention and restoration of forests damaged by fires, natural disasters and catastrophic events.
- Measure 8.5: investments aimed at increasing the resilience and environmental value of ecosystems forestry.
- Measure 9: the establishment of associations and producer organizations.
- Measure 10: agri-climatic-environmental payments.
- Measure 11: organic agriculture.
- Measure 12: Natura 2000 payments and water framework directive.
- Measure 13: allowance for less-favoured areas subject to natural or other specific constraints.
- Measure 14: N14 Promote the adoption of cultivation, fishing and aquaculture techniques in rural areas compatible with the natural landscape with low environment impact”.
- Measure 15: forest-climatic-environmental services and forest conservation.
- Measure 16: cooperation.
- Measure 16.7: leader of local action groups.
- Measure 17.1: crop, animal and plant insurance.
- Measure 17.2: mutual funds for bad weather, for epizootic diseases and phytopathogens, for parasitic infestations and for environmental emergencies.
- Measure 17.3: income stabilization tool.

The measures are divided into sub-measures and/or operations, each specifically intended for specific categories of users (the so-called Beneficiaries) invited to present, according to the rules indicated in dedicated calls, their requests for financial support.

The Regions have built their SSLs based on the characteristics of agriculture and rural areas of their territories. The programming priorities of Apulia SSL are referring to:

1. Promote knowledge transfer and innovation in the agricultural sector and forestry and rural areas.
2. Strengthen farm profitability and competitiveness in all region’s agriculture in all its forms and promoting innovative technologies for farms and agriculture sustainable forest management.
3. Promote the organization of the food supply chain, including processing and marketing of agricultural products, animal welfare and risk management in the sector agricultural.
4. Preserve, restore and enhance the ecosystems connected to agriculture and agriculture Forestry.
5. Encourage the efficient use of resources and the transition to a low-emission economy of carbon and resilient to the climate in the agri-food and forestry sector.
6. Work towards social inclusion, poverty reduction and development cheap in rural areas

The beneficiaries of the interventions carried out under the Rural Development Program are the farmers, operators of the agri-food and forestry system, entrepreneurs and aspirants' entrepreneurs operating in rural areas in single or associated form, entities and institutions public, local partnerships. In turn, the 23 Local Action Groups (LAGs), present in Apulia, presented their action plan based on the needs of their reference area.

With regard to the post-2020 PAC path, in Italy, the Ministry of Agricultural, Food and Forestry Policies (Mipaaf), in collaboration with the Regions and Autonomous Provinces - and with the support of the National Rural Network - started the in-depth study and comparison activities indispensable for building the framework in which to define intervention strategies, regardless of the national or regional characteristics they will assume.

In addition to the Autonomous Regions and Provinces, the work of the table is attended by central administrations competent on issues directly or indirectly affected by the reform of agricultural policy (Ministry of the Environment and Protection of the Territory and the Sea - MATTM, Ministry of Economic Development - MISE, Ministry of Health, Presidency of the Council of Ministers with the Department of Civil Protection and the Department for Cohesion Policies), statistical and research bodies (ISTAT, ISPRA, ENEA).

The first phase of development, conducted by the work of the technical table, took place between May and December 2019, led to the drafting and sharing of 11 Policy Briefs and 10 SWOTs. These contents have structured the current state of Italian agriculture and rural areas around the information content of the reference framework (see the CAP monitoring and performance evaluation framework), suitably enriched with other controls and analyse in order to describe in a more precise way salient and characterizing aspects at national, regional and territorial level.

This methodology - while requiring a greater effort in terms of coordination from the initial stages of the work - functionally defined the essential elements for the strategy, based on a coherent approach and a common and shared language. The documents produced concerned, therefore, an excellent work base for the Regions and Autonomous Provinces, which have carried out the subsequent phases of comparison and deepening at the territorial and sectoral level, as far as further elements characterizing the agricultural, food and food system emerge forestry of our country.

3.10.2 Mission statement and the needs of pilot regions

The Innovagritech Pilot's Mission is *to promote the enhancement of natural and social resources available in the area, by adopting measures that facilitate new business activities, including through the provision of technical and financial assistance to established populations and those who consider making it their new home.*

The needs identified by the SWOT/needs analysis are shown below:

- **N05** Promote social inclusion and improve the quality of life of disadvantaged people;

- **N07** Control of the main abandonment phenomena by implementing integrated development processes of production activities in the internal areas;
- **N11** Promote the employment of women and young people and the abandonment of rural areas;
- **N01** Encourage the creation of infrastructure connections between rural and urban areas, therefore towards the main city of the region;
- **N02** Promote the spread of telematic technologies in order to promote remote assistance for families and businesses;
- **N03** Strengthening local services aimed at leisure and the culture of the rural community in favour of the disadvantaged and/or disabled people;
- **N04** Identify and classify areas susceptible to recreational uses and urban greenery, to design and implement improvement works that contribute to the increase in the quality of life;
- **N06** Promote the birth of social enterprises and the spread of social agriculture;
- **N08** Promote generational change and development opportunities for family plans;
- **N09** Promote technological innovation linked to the Green Economy;
- **N10** Encourage the creation of new businesses and support youth and female entrepreneurship and the birth of innovative start-ups;
- **N12** Encourage the creation of lively communities and local activities led by young people and women;
- **N13** Promote the enhancement and protection of the historical-cultural-environmental heritage and protected areas;
- **N14** Promote the adoption of cultivation, fishing and aquaculture techniques in rural areas compatible with the natural landscape with low environment impact.

3.10.3 Matching needs with policy measures in Needs-Policy Canvas

Table 20. Needs-Policy canvas, Apulia

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme /strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
N01 Develop a framework for coordinated program development and activities directed towards identifying and incorporating the specific need of the economic sectors in rural areas	Rural Development Programmes (RDPs) Puglia 2014-2020	EAFRD	Regional level	https://psr.regione.puglia.it/en/il-programma
N02 Provide consultancy services for entrepreneurial support (technology, finance, HR, marketing, sales etc)	Rural Development Programmes (RDPs) Puglia 2014-2020	EAFRD	Regional level	https://psr.regione.puglia.it/en/il-programma

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme /strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
N03 Establish separate funds for financial support of innovative/new rural activities;	Rural Development Programmes (RDPs) Puglia 2014-2020	EAFRD	Regional level	https://psr.regione.puglia.it/en/il-programma
N04 Establish institutions at local or regional level competent to address the specific needs of the different areas of rural development	Rural Development Programmes (RDPs) Puglia 2014-2020	EAFRD	Regional level	https://psr.regione.puglia.it/en/il-programma
N05 Develop a systematic approach for making rural areas more attractive for young people by addressing various critical issues: education, day-care, extracurricular activities, employment and career prospects, social and recreational activities	Rural Development Programmes (RDPs) Puglia 2014-2020	EAFRD	Regional level	https://psr.regione.puglia.it/en/il-programma
N06 Development of rural road Infrastructure	Rural Development Programmes (RDPs) Puglia 2014-2020	EAFRD	Regional level	https://psr.regione.puglia.it/en/il-programma
N07 Provide better opportunities for higher /professional education	Rural Development Programmes (RDPs) Puglia 2014-2020	EAFRD	Regional level	https://psr.regione.puglia.it/en/il-programma
N08 Offer elderly people recreational activities and spaces to meet and socialize	Rural Development Programmes (RDPs) Puglia 2014-2020	EAFRD	Regional level	https://psr.regione.puglia.it/en/il-programma
N09 Create measures to encourage youth participation in decision-making and contribute to policy making	Rural Development Programmes (RDPs) Puglia 2014-2020	EAFRD	Regional level	https://psr.regione.puglia.it/en/il-programma

3.11 Pilot 11 Gevgelija-Strumica, North Macedonia

3.11.1 Description of respective governance structures

The **Republic of North Macedonia** is situated in the South - Western part of the Balkan Peninsula and in the South - Eastern part of Europa. The country has a total territory of 25 713 km² out of which water area is 857 km² while the land area is 24 856 km².

The country is divided into **8 non-administrative planning regions** (NUTS 3), 80 municipalities (LAU 1) and 1 767 settlements (LAU 2). According to the OECD definition of rural areas¹, there are 6 predominantly rural NUTS 3 regions and 2 - intermediate rural NUTS 3 regions.

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As a result of the country's topography and climatic conditions, separate agricultural regions are identified, each with its own soil, terrain and micro-climate specifics which influence the choice of agriculture production. The informal division identifies 10 **agricultural regions** which correspond to the country's geographical valleys: Skopsko Pole, Kumanovsko-Lipkovsko Pole, Kochansko Pole, Ovche Pole, Polog, Pelagonija, Tikvesko Pole, Strumichko pole, Ohrid-Prespa Lake Region and Gevgelisko Valandovsko Pole (See Figure 1). These regions are characterized with intensive agriculture activity and above 90% of the agriculture holdings are performing their activity in these regions.

Polirural Pilot 11 is focused on the Southeastern region of North Macedonia, Gevgelija-Strumica, see Figure 13.

Figure 13. Administrative planning regions in North Macedonia

The country's **administrative system** is organized on a state and local level. In the state governance context, the state powers are separated into legislative (the Parliament),

⁹⁶ Annual agriculture and rural development report for 2018, <http://www.mzsv.gov.mk/cms/Upload/docs/%D0%93%D0%97%D0%982018.pdf>

executive (the President of the Republic and the Government) and judicial (Judicial Council of the Republic). The Government is composed of Ministries and other state agencies and institutions. Local governance is organized by local self-government units on a municipal level.

Agriculture presents the main economic sector in the rural economy of North Macedonia. The annual gross value added in agriculture for 2018 was 53.389 billion denars (868 million EUR). The agro-food sector is still one of the biggest contributors to the national economy accounting for up to 13% in the national GDP. The main indicators⁹⁷ of the North Macedonia agriculture are presented in Table 19.

Table 21. Main indicators of agriculture in North Macedonia

Number of agricultural holdings	178 125
Total utilised area, ha	320 738
Livestock units	381 361
Household members engaged at individual agricultural holdings and employees at business entities	441 829
AWU – Total	242 988

Source: State statistical office of the Republic of North Macedonia

Land ownership structure in the country is predominantly private. Individual agriculture holdings cultivate 80% of arable land and the rest is cultivated by agriculture enterprises (out of which around 36 000 ha are cultivated by privatized former Agriculture Combinats) and public enterprises.

In terms of the **structure of total employment** in the country, data for 2012 show that 24,8% of people were employed in the primary sector (agriculture, forestry and fishing), 23,4% in the secondary sector (industry and construction) and 51,8% in the tertiary sector (services and others). Agricultural sector, including forestry and fisheries accounts for 18,7% in the total employment in 2013 which is more than two-thirds higher than the EU 27 average of 5,2%.

The **formal institutional framework** in charge for the agriculture and rural development sector in North Macedonia is consisted of:

- Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Economy;
- Regional units of the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Economy;
- Agency for Financial Support of Agriculture and Rural Development;
- State Inspectorate for Agriculture; and

⁹⁷ State Statistical Office of the Republic of North Macedonia, <http://www.stat.gov.mk>

- National Extension Agency.

The leading institution directly involved in creating policies for rural development is the **Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Economy of North Macedonia**⁹⁸. The Ministry operates through a certain organizational structure led by the Minister, Deputy Minister and the General Secretary of the Ministry, which are political positions.

The system of policy creation is supported also by an **external institutional structure** for developing policies for rural development consisted of the following stakeholders:

- Academia
- NGOs
- Projects supported from international development agencies (USAID, SIDA, GIZ, etc).

Additionally, ten years ago the Ministry had an initiative to organize working groups per each agricultural sub sector also called **subsector groups and the Council for Agriculture and rural development** with a main purpose to insure a direct involvement of the interest groups/users in the process of the policy development. The involvement of these additional bodies is formally regulated in the Law for Agriculture and Rural Development.

The objectives of the **national agricultural policy** stated in the so-called **National Strategy for Agriculture and Rural Development (2014-2020)** of the Republic of North Macedonia are aimed at:

- providing stable production of cheap food with high quality, and providing the population with sufficient amounts of food;
- increasing the competitiveness of agriculture;
- ensuring a stable level of income in the agricultural economy;
- sustainable development of rural areas and
- optimal use of natural resources respecting the principles for protecting nature and environment.

These objectives are achieved through **policy measures and instruments** for:

- *organizing and supporting agricultural markets;*
- *direct payments and*
- *rural development.*

The process of planning, monitoring the implementation and assessing the impact of policy measures and instruments is in jurisdiction of the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Economy of North Macedonia.

⁹⁸ Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Economy of North Macedonia, <http://www.mzsv.gov.mk/>

The institutions in charge for implementing policy measures and instruments, including control are the **Agency for Financial Support of Agriculture and Rural Development, The states Inspectorate for Agriculture and the National Extension Agency (NEA)**.

The financing of the national agricultural policy is done by:

- Budget of the Republic of North Macedonia;
- Budget of the European Union;
- Donations and projects and
- Other sources.

For the needs of planning, monitoring and implementing of the national agricultural policy, the Ministry establishes a **partnership with social and economic partners in the field of agriculture and rural development**⁹⁹. This partnership is realized through:

- *Council for Agriculture and Rural Development;*
- *Sub sectoral permanent working groups;*
- *The Inter-Ministerial Body for Rural Development;*
- *The Committee for Monitoring the Multiannual Program for the Use of Financial Funds by the Pre-Accession Instrument of the European Union for Agriculture and Rural Development; and*
- *National Rural Network.*

Current leading document in creating the policy for rural development is the **national strategy for agriculture and rural development for the period 2014-2020**¹⁰⁰. The National Strategy for Agriculture and Rural Development for the period 2014-2020 (NSARD 2014-2020) reflects the continuity of country's priorities for development of the agriculture and the rural areas, and to provide support to the agricultural sector to achieve sufficient level of competitiveness to cope with challenges of the open and changeable market and, also to boost the development of rural areas. **The priorities set at EU level and IPA II objectives are consistent with the NSARD 2014-2020.**

The National Strategy for Agriculture and Rural Development is a basic strategic document for achieving the goals of the **Law for Agriculture and Rural Development in North Macedonia**. The national strategy includes an analysis of the current situation in the field of agriculture, processing of agricultural products and rural areas, medium-term development guidelines and plan for implementation, expected outcomes and the necessary financial resources for the implementation of national agricultural policy.

⁹⁹ Law for agriculture and rural development in North Macedonia, http://ipard.gov.mk/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/Zakon_za_zemjodelstvo_i_ruralen_razvoj_0.pdf

¹⁰⁰ National strategy for agriculture and rural development in North Macedonia 2014-2020, <http://www.mzsv.gov.mk/CMS/Upload/docs/NSZRR2014-2020.pdf>

The National Strategy is adopted by the Government of the Republic of North Macedonia on the proposal of the Minister of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Economy for a period of seven years.

The way how the National Strategy for Agriculture and Rural Development is implemented is presented in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Implementing structure of the National strategy for agriculture and rural development. Source: National strategy for agriculture and rural development for the period 2014-2020

The government is adopting a national program for agriculture and rural development that contains:

- instruments, measures and activities for implementation of the measures;
- schedule and deadlines for implementation; and
- indicative financial framework for their implementation.

At the suggestion of the Minister, the Government adopts an **annual program for financial support**¹⁰¹ for agriculture and an annual program for financial support for rural development supporting the implementation of the national program.

¹⁰¹ Programme for financial support of the rural development in North Macedonia for 2018, <http://www.mzsv.gov.mk/CMS/Upload/docs/%D0%9F%D1%80%D0%BE%D0%B3%D1%80%D0%B0%D0%BC%D0%B0%D0%B7%D0%B0%D1%84%D0%B8%D0%BD%D0%B0%D0%BD%D1%81%D0%B8%D1%81%D0%BA%D0%B0%D0%BF%D0%BE%D0%B4%D0%B4%D1%80%D1%88%D0%BA%D0%B0%D0%BD%D0%B0%D1%80%D1%83%D1%80%D0%B0%D0%BB%D0%BD%D0%B8%D0%BE%D1%82%D1%80%D0%B0%D0%B7%D0%B2%D0%BE%D1%98%D0%B7%D0%B0%2018%D0%B3%D0%BE%D0%B4%D0%B8%D0%BD%D0%B0.pdf>

At the suggestion of the Minister, the Government adopts a multi annual **program for using the funds from the Pre-Accession Assistance Instrument**¹⁰² for Agriculture and Rural Development from the European Union in accordance with the agreements with the European Union for the use of pre-accession instruments for financial support.

In the **previous programming period (2007-2013)** the country benefited as a pre-accession country from support under IPARD. Throughout the **IPARD Programme implementation**, the rejection rate was around 65% reflecting a very low absorption rate (around 5% of the available funds are paid to beneficiaries). Overall, the high rate of rejection (at application and contract level) and corresponding low rate of absorbing the available funds under IPARD I is largely due to the problems of the applicants to collect and submit the required documents and the low degree of quality of the submitted projects. Rarely the reason for rejecting was identified non-eligibility of the applicants in terms of definition of beneficiaries (falling under the definition of SME). The reasons for cancellation of contracts from the side of the IPARD Agency were due to identified “conflict of interest” between suppliers and from the side of the beneficiaries the most frequent reason was lack of funds to start or finalise the investment.

The country has benefited from a number **donor-funded aid programs**. During the period 2007-2013, the project “Strengthening and accession to the EU of Macedonian agriculture” funded through **World Bank loan** in the amount of 15 million EUR has been implemented. Other active **donors and projects** implemented in the period 2007-2013 are: UNICEF, Turkish Cooperation and Coordination Agency – TIKA, Turkey, USAID, SIDA, Sweden, Norway, FAO, Netherlands, IFAD (International Fund for Agricultural Development), GIZ and KfW- Germany.

3.11.2 Mission statement and the needs of pilot regions

The mission statement of the Gevgelija-Strumica pilot region is *developing policy measures that will ensure sustainable agricultural extension that will deliver high quality service in an efficient and effective way.*

The main needs for the Gevgelija-Strumica pilot region according to swot analysis based on the survey and literature review are the following:

- *N01 Develop a framework for coordinated program development and activities directed towards identifying and incorporating the specific need of the economic sectors in rural areas;*
- *N02 Provide consultancy services for entrepreneurial support (technology, finance, HR, marketing, sales etc);*
- *N03 Establish separate funds for financial support of innovative/new rural activities;*

¹⁰² IPA Rural development programme 2014-2020,
http://ipardpa.gov.mk/Root/mak/docs/Zakonodavstvo/IPARD%20II%20Programme_ENG.pdf

- N04 Establish institutions at local or regional level competent to address the specific needs of the different areas of rural development;
- N05 Develop a systematic approach for making rural areas more attractive for young people by addressing various critical issues: education, day-care, extracurricular activities, employment and career prospects, social and recreational activities;
- N06 Development of rural road Infrastructure;
- N07 Provide better opportunities for higher /professional education;
- N08 Offer elderly people recreational activities and spaces to meet and socialize;
- N09 Create measures to encourage youth participation in decision-making and contribute to policy making;

3.11.3 Matching needs with policy measures

The ranking of the needs was made based on policy mapping and discussion with stakeholders from the Regional panel during the online meeting held on 29.4.2020.

Table 22. Communication with policy makers and stakeholders

Date	Topic of the meeting	Type of the meeting (face-to-face, online, workshop)	Target group	Number of attendees
29/4/2020	Discussing about swot, steepv, needs and policy, innovation hub	Online meeting via Zoom	Panel members	10

Table 23. Needs-Policy Canvas, Gevgelija-Strumica, North Macedonia.

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
N01 Develop a framework for coordinated program development and activities directed towards identifying and incorporating the specific need of the economic sectors in rural areas	National strategy for agriculture and rural development for the period 2014-2020	-	National level	http://arhiva.mzsv.gov.mk/NSZRR%202014-2020.pdf
N02 Provide consultancy services for entrepreneurial support (technology, finance, HR, marketing, sales etc)	National strategy for agriculture and rural development for the period 2014-2020	-	National level	http://arhiva.mzsv.gov.mk/NSZRR%202014-2020.pdf
N03 Establish separate funds for financial support of innovative/new rural activities;	EU INSTRUMENT FOR PRE-ACCESSION: RURAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMME 2014-2020	IPA	National level	http://arhiva.mzsv.gov.mk/NSZRR%202014-2020.pdf

N04 Establish institutions at local or regional level competent to address the specific needs of the different areas of rural development	EU INSTRUMENT FOR PRE-ACCESSION: RURAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMME 2014-2020	IPA	National level	http://arhiva.mzsv.gov.mk/NSZRR%202014-2020.pdf http://ipardpa.gov.mk/Root/mak/_docs/Zakonodavstvo/IPARD%20II%20Programme_ENG.pdf
N05 Develop a systematic approach for making rural areas more attractive for young people by addressing various critical issues: education, day-care, extracurricular activities, employment and career prospects, social and recreational activities	National strategy for agriculture and rural development for the period 2014-2020; EU INSTRUMENT FOR PRE-ACCESSION: RURAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMME 2014-2020	IPA	National level	http://arhiva.mzsv.gov.mk/NSZRR%202014-2020.pdf http://ipardpa.gov.mk/Root/mak/_docs/Zakonodavstvo/IPARD%20II%20Programme_ENG.pdf ;
N06 Development of rural road Infrastructure	National strategy for agriculture and rural development for the period 2014-2020; EU INSTRUMENT FOR PRE-ACCESSION: RURAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMME 2014-2020	IPA	National level	http://arhiva.mzsv.gov.mk/NSZRR%202014-2020.pdf http://ipardpa.gov.mk/Root/mak/_docs/Zakonodavstvo/IPARD%20II%20Programme_ENG.pdf ;
N07 Provide better opportunities for higher /professional education	EU INSTRUMENT FOR PRE-ACCESSION: RURAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMME 2014-2020	IPA	National level	http://ipardpa.gov.mk/Root/mak/_docs/Zakonodavstvo/IPARD%20II%20Programme_ENG.pdf
N08 Offer elderly people recreational activities and spaces to meet and socialize	National strategy for agriculture and rural development for the period 2014-2020; EU INSTRUMENT FOR PRE-ACCESSION: RURAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMME 2014-2020	IPA	National level	http://arhiva.mzsv.gov.mk/NSZRR%202014-2020.pdf http://ipardpa.gov.mk/Root/mak/_docs/Zakonodavstvo/IPARD%20II%20Programme_ENG.pdf
N09 Create measures to encourage youth participation in decision-making and contribute to policy making	National strategy for agriculture and rural development for the period 2014-2020	-	National level	http://arhiva.mzsv.gov.mk/NSZRR%202014-2020.pdf

3.12 Pilot 12 Galilee, Israel

3.12.1 Description of respective governance structures

Israel have two peripheral regions, the Negev in the south and the Galilee in the north near the Lebanese and Syrian borders. In the south the central city is Beer-Seva with over 220,000 residents, while to cities in the Galilee are much smaller, 50,000 in Sefat, 20,000 in Kiryat-Shmona and many Kibbutzim and Moshavim. Beer-Seva has connection by train to the centre as well as good highways, while no train to Galilee even planned. This give the impression that the Galilee is a periphery and has a role on its development.

In Eastern Galilee, there are many small municipality, associated as a cluster for activities of mutual interest, but each is govern separately. The Eastern Galilee Cluster is an association of municipalities, established to promote regional perception and strategic collaborations between the local authorities in the Eastern Galilee and between them and the central government (government offices). The cluster is part of the national cluster venture led by the Ministry of the Interior and the Ministry of Finance. Collaboration between the Cluster member authorities began in 2006, prior to its official establishment, when local leadership realized that it would find it difficult to deal with the peripheral challenges, and began meeting regularly to offer integrated solutions and address systemic problems. This association had a major role in the establishment of the Faculty of Medicine in Safed in 2009. Subsequently, the government helped to form the cluster with governmental support.

3.12.2 Mission statement and the needs of pilot regions

The Galilee plan for a Smart Region

When examining the geographical distribution of the various economic sectors in Israel, we must distinguish between results that are the consequence of economic forces at work in Israel and wishful thinking. The premise we must accept is that high-tech companies tend to concentrate in certain geographical areas, frequently in urban metropolises. This phenomenon has many advantages, both for the companies themselves and for the regional economy. The trend has grown over the past decade, for reasons that include increasing technological complexity necessitating greater collaboration, and because of the increasing attraction of workers to vibrant urban areas. The other side of the coin is that the region in which they are concentrated benefits from accelerated growth and high-quality employment. Similar “centralization” trend in high-tech also exists in Israel: more than 60% of all high-tech jobs in Israel are located in the Tel Aviv and central regions, and as Diagram no. 1 illustrates (figure 15), approximately 77% of the companies operate in this area. Diagram no. 2 reveals

that this trend has even intensified in recent years with the growth in high-tech employment in Tel Aviv constituting approximately 70% of the total increase in this sector in Israel¹⁰³.

Figure 15. Source: Startup nation Central and CBS Data, Personnel Survey

It is not surprising therefore that approximately half the jobs in mass manufacturing industries and about 80% of all farmed agricultural land is located in the north and south of Israel¹⁰⁴. The high availability and low cost of land in these areas lead to specialization in mass manufacturing, agriculture and food, and we believe that these advantages should be leveraged and strengthened by connecting them to Israel's advanced innovation system.

Although the geographical distribution described here is based on economic logic and relative regional advantages, it creates several economic and social challenges for the Galilee economy. The first of these challenges is a significant productivity disparity between the country's periphery and centre that is reflected in salaries, which are approximately 35% lower than the average in central Israel. A further challenge arises in light of the shortage of skilled high-tech workers. Due to the concentration of high-tech in the centre of the country, skilled workers living in the periphery have lower access to high-tech employment. Consequently, the Israeli high-tech industry fails to fully utilise the human capital potential in the periphery.

The formation of the Galilee smart region can be considered a manifestation of the concept "at the right time, in the right place, and with the right persons." Because populations will continue to be highly concentrated in cities, the challenges of the Galilee pilot is becoming increasingly serious when trying to promote the development of the Galilee peripheral region. Although numerous definitions of the "Smart Region" concept have been proposed, generally,

¹⁰³ https://innovationisrael.org.il/en/reportchapter/innovation-driven-economy-periphery#footnote3_hgmgrks

¹⁰⁴ CBS Data, Annual Yearbook 2017, Table 20.12, excluding high-tech, and the Ministry of Agriculture & Rural Development, Agricultural and Rural Planning Policy Paper (2015)

a Smart Region exhibits a resident-centric approach where information and communication technologies are used to resolve problems resulting from the distance from the Centre, to achieve the goals of operational maximization and energy consumption minimization.

Thus, the Galilee can be considered a region most qualified to discuss smart region and implementation of IoT technologies. Unlike the past, where industries typically emphasized products, in the future, industries are expected to focus on diverse applications that involve substantial innovation. This should provide Galilee's industries and agricultural entities, with opportunities to implement digitalization and "being in the right place".

As a result of the Polirural project activities we foresee the implementation of the IoT's methodologies over the coming few years. With the publication of this proposal, the Galilee aims to illustrate the feasibility of the approach for realising the smart region concept to various industries and entities in the region. Therefore, we established a task-oriented "smart region team" to respond to different applications in order to implement and advance the development. The "smart region team" is not a formal unit in organizational structure; instead, it is an application team, from various entities in the Galilee, which focuses on smart applications. This unit will be led by MIGAL, during these collaborations, technologies and their practical applications in all aspects of life will be explored. This should allow decision makers to understand how to implement the Smart Region concept. Additionally, we plan to promote the mature development of related applications through continuous communication and practice. This is expected to enable us to assist various entities with achieving the vision of the Smart Region.

3.12.3 Matching needs with policy measures in Needs-Policy Canvas

Table 24. Communication with stakeholders

Date	Topic of the meeting	Type of the meeting (face-to-face, online, workshop)	Target group	Number of attendees
08/03/2020	Examining needs with corresponding policies	Face to face	Planning future steps Meeting with the Council Mayor	3
19/04/2020	Discussion about SWOT and policy mapping	Zoom call (online meeting)	Stakeholders, researchers and economical experts	16
01/05/2010	Discussion about policy mapping	Meeting (seating apart)	Formal Mayor and researchers	3
07/05/2020	Discussion about policy mapping	Zoom call (online meeting)	Stakeholders from several sectors	19

Based on the preliminary discussions and the meetings with stakeholders of the different sectors in the Galilee, we began taking actual steps for implementing the ideas presented by

the partners from the different sectors. The stakeholders were from the industry, academia, research institutes, tourism entity; education; the agriculture sector; SME in computers; the municipality; the cluster of the Upper Eastern Galilee municipalities; VC; entrepreneur; and citizens having experience in strategy development.

In order to explain how the Polirural project face the ideas of rural development we presented to the stakeholders where the Polirural project can lead us to, as well as an initial plan for activity that was a result of the former meetings. The programme proposed by some participants try to establish an important direction for upgrading the region for 2030. This is a result of the SWOT analysis done and some scenarios for bringing youngster to the Galilee. Discussion were presented on activities and programmes that already exist in the Galilee as well as ideas where we have to focus and how we may further develop the ideas. The next stage is to form several small working groups, which will concentrate more deeply on specific needs and benefits in the topics of industry, high schools' education, entrepreneurs recruiting to the Galilee, upgrading the agriculture in the region, research and higher education.

Table 25. Needs-Policy Canvas, Galilee, Israel.

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
Climate smart and innovative agriculture	TOMORROW'S AGRICULTURE BEGINS IN ISRAEL	-	National level	https://innovationisrael.org.il/en/article/tomorrows-agriculture-begins-israel
Climate smart and innovative agriculture	Develop the agricultural sector	-	International level	https://www.oecd.org/israel/publicationsdocuments/reports/7/
Find a balance between nature and agriculture	Innovative environmental technologies in Israel	-	National level	https://innovationisrael.org.il/en/article/innovative-environmental-technologies-israel
Ecology	New environmental protection and sustainability innovation lab	-	National level	https://innovationisrael.org.il/en/news/new-environmental-protection-and-sustainability-innovation-lab
Ecology	New innovation lab will focus on environmental protection and sustainability	-	National level	https://mfa.gov.il/mfa/innovativeisrael/economy/pages/new-innovation-lab-will-focus-on-environmental-protection-and-sustainability-16-december-2019.aspx
Ecology	Long-Term Master Plan for the National Water Sector	-	National level	http://www.water.gov.il/Hebrew/Planning-and-Development/Planning/MasterPlan/DocLib4/MasterPlan-en-v.4.pdf
Ecology	Sinking Israel-Jordan relations leave Dead Sea, a natural wonder, low and dry	-	National level	https://www.timesofisrael.com/sinking-israel-jordan-relations-leave-dead-sea-a-natural-wonder-low-and-dry/
Ecology	There's a Way to Save Jordan. But It Might Kill the Dead Sea	-	National level	https://www.haaretz.com/israel-news/premium.MAGAZINE-there-s-a-way-to-save-jordan-but-it-might-kill-the-dead-sea-1.7138994

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
Ecology	As Sea of Galilee fills to bursting, Israelis' joy overflows	-	National level	https://www.timesofisrael.com/as-sea-of-galilee-fills-to-bursting-israelis-joy-overflows/
Ecology	For the first time in 17 years, Sea of Galilee is nearly full	-	National level	https://www.israelhayom.com/2020/03/23/for-the-first-time-in-17-years-sea-of-galilee-is-nearly-full/
Support farmers, and encourage young farmers	Moving Forward with the Galilee	-	National level	https://www.kkl-inf.org/people-and-environment/community-development/galilee/
Support youngster migrant to Galilee	KKL-JNF's Israel 2040 vision reaches hundreds and thousands of readers on YNET.	-	National level	https://www.kkl-inf.org/about-klk-inf/green-israel-news/march-2020/israel-2040-israeli-relocation-y-net-article/
Higher education	The Azrieli Faculty of Medicine in the Galilee	-	Regional level	https://medicine.biu.ac.il/en/node/26
Higher education	Local agricultural policy	-	Regional level	http://english.telhai.ac.il/
Higher education	International Cooperation	-	Regional level	http://english.telhai.ac.il/international-programs/
Further develop rural tourism	The treasures awaiting a visit in the Galilee	-	Local /grassroot level	https://www.israel21c.org/the-treasures-awaiting-a-visit-in-the-galilee/
Develop the rural advance industry	Program for Encouraging the Establishment and Expansion of Hi-Tech Companies' Activity in the Periphery	-	National level	https://innovationisrael.org.il/en/article/program-encouraging-establishment-and-expansion-hi-tech-companies-activity-periphery
Develop the rural advance industry	From a high-tech industry to a Smart Economy	-	National level	https://innovationisrael.org.il/en/reportchapter/high-tech-industry
Develop the rural advance industry	R&D INCENTIVE PROGRAMS	-	National level	http://economy.gov.il/Publications/Publications/DocLib/RnD_IncentivePrograms_English.pdf
Develop the rural advance industry	Regional development of the Galilee	-	National level	https://jerusalemstitute.org.il/en/publications/galilee-biotechnology-sector/
Economic development	Council for Higher Education (2009), "the Galilee, Israel: Self-Evaluation Report"	-	International level	https://www.oecd.org/israel/44345452.pdf
Economic development	Strengthening Israel's Regions: Creating New Sources of Capital For Economic Development in the Negev and Galilee	-	Local /grassroot level	https://milkeninnovationcenter.org/publications/strengthening-israels-regions-creating-new-sources-of-capital-for-economic-development-in-the-negev-and-galilee/
Economic development	An Innovation Driven Economy in the Periphery	-	National level	https://innovationisrael.org.il/en/reportchapter/innovation-driven-economy-periphery
Digitalization of the Galilee	The National Digital Program	-	National level	https://www.gov.il/BlobFolder/news/digital_israel_national_plan/en/The%20National%20Digital%20Program%20of%20the%20Government%20of%20Israel.pdf

Need (from T4.3, table 3, 3-6 needs that are ranked highest)	Title of the policy/programme/strategy	Structural or investment fund	Level at which the policy is launched	Contact/Website of the policy
Digitalization of the Galilee	The National Digital Program of the Government of Israel	-	National level	http://digital-israel.mag.calltext.co.il/magazine/83/pages/9
Human Centric - digitalization	Strategy for upgrading the Galilee	-	Regional level	http://nocamels.com/2020/04/coronavirus-time-human-centric-digital/
Digitalization of the Galilee	Digitizing the Value Chain	-	Regional level	https://www.israelindustry40.com/ii42020
Digitalization of the Galilee	Strategy for upgrading the Galilee	-	Regional level	http://www.iati.co.il/files/files/IATI%20Israeli%20Life%20Sciences%20Industry%202019%20Report.pdf
Digitalization of the Galilee	10 Israeli companies scouring digital data to save our lives	-	Regional level	https://www.israel21c.org/10-israeli-companies-scouring-digital-data-to-save-our-lives/
Digitalization of the Galilee	Advertisement Jerusalem Post HI-TECH NEWS Transforming the Galilee into a food-tech stronghold	-	Regional level	https://www.jpost.com/business-and-innovation/tech/transforming-the-galilee-into-food-tech-stronghold-482830

4 Conclusion and next steps

This deliverable and policy mapping exercise (T4.4) has reached the goal of juxtaposing rural needs with corresponding policy measures in 12 PoliRural pilot regions. In this deliverable the Needs-Policy Canvases are presented in table format. In following project phases, it is possible to create more visual canvas presentations for disseminating the results in PoliRural Innovation Hub and web page. This deliverable also presents the rural policy structures in PoliRural pilot regions and thus allows access to explore pilot areas more in-depth and use the information in the becoming steps of the project.

PoliRural pilot regions are different in terms of size and rural characteristics. Also needs and barriers related to rural attractiveness vary. That's why there is variation between the level of which the policy mapping is made. In the 1st official Review the Monitor's paid attention to the need of matching relevant EU funds to the national/regional level implementation. This was then refined by each pilot. From this matching it can be seen that the European Rural Development Fund (ERDF), European Social Fund (ESF) and the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) are the most important funds that occur in this Needs-Policy Canvas. Also Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance (IPA) is used in the case of the North Macedonia pilot.

Table 26. Number of Pilots (out of 12) that used certain Structural or Investment Fund in Needs-Policy Canvases

Due to relatively short time allocated for the task, deeper analysis and conclusions of the policy mapping results are not included into this deliverable but will appear in next task T4.5 Evaluation of Regional Policy Measures and in the Deliverable 4.5. Perceived Effectiveness of Rural Interventions - 12 Regions, where a comparative analytical view on the evaluation work on 12 pilots is done based on the work done in T4.4 and the Needs-Policy Canvas. Needs-Policy Canvases are also used as a base for the Driver's analysis work conducted in Work Package 5: Future Rural Outlook. Policy documents and data sources that are recognised during policy mapping process will be collected to PoliRural regional library in SEMEX (<https://semex.io/>) to improve the quality of text mining tool (WP2).

Some challenges were faced during the policy mapping process. Firstly, the schedule for preceding task T4.3 Regional Needs Gathering and Analysis was extended with three months to last at the end of May 2020 (M12) (in original plan due date was M9). This means that pilot regions were doing policy mapping partly simultaneously with needs gathering. Another remarkable challenge was caused by COVID19 pandemic (declared by WHO from 11 March 2020) and its consequences like transition to teleworking and the restrictions to face-to-face meetings. Pilot participants were forced to come up with new ways to work with policy makers and stakeholders to replace face-to-face meetings.

Annex 1. Needs-Policy mapping all pilots, excel

Annex 2. Comments to Monitors Review and Advisory Board Review

Comment made by the monitors	Explanation	Advisory Board's Comments	Reply to the AB's Comment
<p>This deliverable is very detailed and contains a lot of valuable information - mapping policy interventions to key needs. It demonstrates diversity across the different pilots. However, gaps remain. A catalogue of EU policy measures is lacking in order to ensure a systematic coverage of relevant policy measures assessed in the pilot regions. For that reason, inconsistencies and the lacking systematic understanding of relevant EU policy programmes and their national/regional level implementation needs to be addressed.</p> <p>For example. Some areas focus on RDP measures (Flanders) while other regions list the name of the programme but do not link it with EU-funding schemes or mix with references to RDP but not to other structural funds such as ERDF or CEF or ESF.</p>	<p>This is addressed on p.10 and p.11. All pilots (excluding Israel) have added structural and investment fund related to the policy to the new column on policy mapping canvas.</p>	<p>D4.4 was rejected by the European Commission and was revised based on the comments from the monitors. The monitors' comments deal mainly with the need to connect the mapping process and the formulation of the pilots' policy to the guiding policy of the European Union, and to provide internal and external validity to the field work through scientific knowledge. The response to the monitors' comments was contained in the introduction by addressing each pilot region, and in the adoption of the recommendation for the establishment of the Advisory Board in the spring of 2021. The response to the monitors' comments seems adequate, although it could have been expanded in the introduction.</p>	<p>The response to monitor's comments was refined in chapter 2.3.</p>
<p>2.1 Refers to the Pro-AKIS project and asks partners to study the national Pro-AKIS reports in order to assess the governance structures for rural development. Attention! The Pro-AKIS project focused on farm advisory systems. This is only one</p>	<p>On p.10 is it explained why the Pro-AKIS was used here.</p>	<p>Advisable to make a more detailed description in the "Executive Summary" so that we can understand the main points of the document beyond just its purpose and structure. The summary should include a breakdown of the characteristics of the various pilots, with an</p>	<p>Executive Summary is extended a bit more to open up the meaning of this work done and what information may be found in this D4.4. It also briefly described where this information gathered will</p>

<p>specific element of the agricultural policy with impact on the farm level. Pro-AKIS describes the governance structures related to farm advice</p>		<p>emphasis on both the common and the unique characteristics of each area and should also include illustrative diagrams.</p>	<p>be used in later stages of the project</p>
<p>2.3 matching needs with current policies with a particular focus on new entrants. Here more detail is needed: which policies, funded under which umbrella? All EU-co-funded Structural Fond need to be included, not only the EAFRD (see Table 2 for Flanders). National Rural Networks will play a role in the pilot areas. What about other programmes such as Interreg Europe or LIFE?</p>	<p>This is addressed in p.10 and 11. It has to be noted that each pilot area defined its own needs from a “bottom-up” perspective and the matching of the policy measures is done based on this. The importance of different measures varies a lot between different regions and this consideration of the most important policies of each pilot region is done independently on the basis of needs-gathering done in every region.</p>	<p>There is a lack of integrative observation, drawing conclusions both from the mapping process and policymaking and from its products as detailed in the document.</p> <p>Through a comparative analysis of the background data of the pilot regions, needs-mapping, and policy, it will be possible to obtain an integrative and broad picture of the entire project.</p>	<p>Conclusions from the mapping process are widened in the “Conclusion and the next steps”-chapter.</p> <p>Clustering and comparative analyse work have been part of T4.2 (D4.2) and T4.5 (D4.5) in WP4. Together with all of these mutually supportive work integrative and broad picture of the whole project can be obtained and the big picture of Current Rural Situation achieved.</p>
<p>The project consortium will need internal or external support from experts with a good overview of current regional development programmes of rural EU areas and beyond for this scientifically based review and consultation</p>	<p>Advisory Board is being set and starts its work on Spring 2021.</p>		